

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

Reference: 101087984

Co-funded by
the European Union

HerStory Transnational Map

WP3: D3.2

HerStory Consortium

Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Author	Modification
1	0	10/01/2025	Emily Psara	First version
1	1	15/01/2025	Alicia García-Holgado	Reviewing and preparing the final version

HerStory - Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies is a project funded under European Union Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values (CERV) Programme (Ref. 101087984). The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	1
2. HerStory Transnational Map	2
2.1. Salamanca, Spain	2
2.2. Fort-de-France, France.....	42
2.3. Nicosia, Cyprus.....	52
2.4. Athens, Greece.....	67
2.5. Sofia, Bulgaria	80
2.6. Velenje, Slovenia.....	98
2.7. Vilnius, Lithuania	109
2.8. Lecco, Italy	121
3. Treasure Hunt Paths	135
3.1. Salamanca, Spain	135
3.2. Fort-de-France, France.....	139
3.3. Nicosia, Cyprus.....	143
3.4. Athens, Greece.....	146
3.5. Sofia, Bulgaria	153
3.6. Velenje, Slovenia.....	174
3.7. Vilnius, Lithuania	178
3.8. Lecco, Italy	181

1. Introduction

The HerStory Transnational Map is designed to be accessible to a broad audience by offering content in both the national languages of each partner city and English. This bilingual approach ensures that users whose first language is not the local one, as well as tourists, can easily access and engage with the rich histories and contributions of influential women across European cities. By offering both local languages and English, the map fosters an inclusive experience, enabling diverse audiences to explore the significant stories of women's achievements. All materials used to develop the city maps have been translated into English to ensure broader accessibility.

This commitment to accessibility aligns with the core objectives of the project, which directly contribute to key CERV priorities by promoting diversity and gender equality. The stories featured on the map showcase the achievements of women from a variety of cultural, geographical, and historical contexts, helping to fill gaps in mainstream historical narratives and celebrate the richness of diverse female contributions.

The transnational map is accessible through the HerStory Platform: <https://map.herstoryproject.eu>.

2. HerStory Transnational Map

Below is the material provided by each partner in English for preparing the transnational map. The original version in the national language of each partner city is available in the national maps report (WP3 D3.1).

2.1. Salamanca, Spain

In English	
Number	1
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Roman Bridge, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.957941590904795, -5.67011768456432
Images	
Description	<p>The Vacceas were brave women who threw themselves into the fight to defend their land, and gave proof of their courage. In 220 BC Salamanca was known as Helmantica and was the scene of fighting between the Carthaginians and the Romans. At that time, the Carthaginian army, commanded by the general Hannibal Barca, had occupied Helmantica by surprise, without giving the Vacceans time to defend themselves. Three hundred talents of silver and as many hostages together with a promise of submission and compliance was the price Hannibal accepted in exchange for</p>

	<p>lifting the siege of the city. Promises that the Vacceans forgot when the Carthaginian general left. But they were wrong to think that Hannibal would consent to such contempt. Learning of the insubordination he returned to Helmantica. The Vacceans this time surrendered unconditionally, being forced to abandon their arms, property and slaves and leave the city as prisoners.</p> <p>The women, on the other hand, showed no sign of despondency, standing upright, wrapped in their loose tunics, they passed unsearched by the soldiers. Taking advantage of this advantage, the brave women of the Vaccea, with the daggers and swords of their men hidden under their tunics, when the time came to act, took out their daggers and swords and handed them to their husbands, companions, sons and brothers, to undertake the reconquest of the city together. One of the women even took an active part in the fight. Thus they managed to defeat Hannibal's invincible army, who, admiring the women's bravery, spared the city and did not destroy it.</p>
Links	https://mujeresypatrimonio.org/blog/ciudad-vieja-de-salamanca/ https://mujeresypatrimonio.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/2-PUENTE-ROMANO.mp3

Number	2
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	El Arco de Aníbal (not exist), C/ Tentenecio, 19, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.95957, -5.66764
Images	

Description

The Vacceas were brave women who threw themselves into the fight to defend their land, and gave proof of their courage. In 220 BC Salamanca was known as Helmantica and was the scene of fighting between the Carthaginians and the Romans. At that time, the Carthaginian army, commanded by the general Hannibal Barca, had occupied Helmantica by surprise, without giving the Vacceans time to defend themselves. Three hundred talents of silver and as many hostages together with a promise of submission and compliance was the price Hannibal accepted in exchange for lifting the siege of the city. Promises that the Vacceans forgot when the Carthaginian general left. But they were wrong to think that Hannibal would consent to such contempt. Learning of the insubordination he returned to Helmantica. The Vacceans this time surrendered unconditionally, being forced to abandon their arms, property and slaves and leave the city as prisoners.

The women, on the other hand, showed no sign of despondency, standing upright, wrapped in their loose tunics, they passed unsearched by the soldiers. Taking advantage of this advantage, the brave women of the Vaccea, with the daggers and swords of their men hidden under their tunics, when the time came to act, took out their daggers and swords and handed them to their husbands, companions, sons and brothers, to undertake the reconquest of the city together. One of the women even took an active part in the fight. Thus they managed to defeat Hannibal's invincible army, who, admiring the women's bravery, spared the city and did not destroy it.

Links

<https://mujeresypatrimonio.org/blog/ciudad-vieja-de-salamanca/>
<https://mujeresypatrimonio.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/3-ARCO-DE-ANIBAL.mp3>

Number	3
City name	Salamanca

Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Toro. Roman Bridge, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.95930189016762, -5.669183528860277
Images	
Description	<p>The Vacceas were brave women who threw themselves into the fight to defend their land, and gave proof of their courage. In 220 BC Salamanca was known as Helmantica and was the scene of fighting between the Carthaginians and the Romans. At that time, the Carthaginian army, commanded by the general Hannibal Barca, had occupied Helmantica by surprise, without giving the Vacceans time to defend themselves. Three hundred talents of silver and as many hostages together with a promise of submission and compliance was the price Hannibal accepted in exchange for lifting the siege of the city. Promises that the Vacceans forgot when the Carthaginian general left. But they were wrong to think that Hannibal would consent to such contempt. Learning of the insubordination he returned to Helmantica. The Vacceans this time surrendered unconditionally, being forced to abandon their arms, property and slaves and leave the city as prisoners.</p> <p>The women, on the other hand, showed no sign of despondency, standing upright, wrapped in their loose tunics, they passed unsearched by the soldiers. Taking advantage of this advantage, the brave women of the Vaccea, with the daggers and swords of their men hidden under their tunics, when the time came to act, took out their daggers and swords and handed them to their husbands, companions, sons and brothers, to undertake the reconquest of the city together. One of the women even took an active part in the fight. Thus they managed to defeat Hannibal's invincible army, who, admiring the women's bravery, spared the city and did not destroy it.</p>

Links	https://mujeresypatrimonio.org/blog/ciudad-vieja-de-salamanca/ https://mujeresypatrimonio.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/4-EL-VERRACO.mp3
-------	--

Number	4
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Tower of the Cathedral of Salamanca. Plaza Juan XXIII, s / n, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96054298732715, -5.666766373161533
Images	

Description	<p>Doña Urraca (1080-1126). She was the daughter of Alfonso VI, King of León, Castile and Galicia, and Constanza of Burgundy. In 1102, Alfonso VI entrusted his daughter and her husband with the difficult task of repopulating Salamanca: people came from France, Toro, Portugal, Asturias... who gave the city an intercultural atmosphere. Bishop Jerónimo had the support of the king to carry out the construction of the Cathedral, which is now the old Cathedral of Salamanca. His father King Alfonso VI died in 1109, one year after the death of his only son Sancho Alfonso, so he decided to establish and approve that his successor would be Urraca. It was the first time that the succession to the throne fell to a woman who was also the widow of her first husband. The León nobles demanded a second marriage from the Queen and took Alfonso I, King of Aragon and Navarre, as their sovereign. Both Doña Urraca and "El Batallador" were proclaimed kings of León and Castile.</p>
Links	<p>https://curiosidadesdelahistoriablog.com/2020/11/23/urraca-de-leon-c-1080-1126-el-complicado-reinado-de-una-mujer-en-la-edad-media/ https://catedralsalamanca.org/catedral-vieja/ https://youtu.be/OP9guQDmkr4?si=ckL5JfWBIXYgi06P</p>

Number	5
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Old Cathedral of Santa María de la Sede, C/ Doyagüe, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96026, -5.66616

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>It is worth mentioning the young Infanta Doña Mafalda (1191-1204), daughter of Alfonso VIII and Leonor de Plantagenet, who died at the age of thirteen in Salamanca. The gravestone of Mafalda on the altar of the Old Cathedral of Salamanca is a copy of the original one behind it. Finally, the Infanta was taken to be buried in the Monastery of Las Huelgas.</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>https://catedralsalamanca.org/catedral-vieja/ https://curiosidadesdelahistoriablog.com/2020/11/23/uraca-de-leon-c-1080-1126-el-complicado-reinado-de-una-mujer-en-la-edad-media/ https://lachovapiquirroja.blogspot.com/search?q=Mafalda</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>6</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Salamanca</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722</p>
<p>Name of the point of interest</p>	<p>C/ Latina, 7, 37008 Salamanca</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest</p>	<p>40.96074, -5.66822</p>

Images

Description

Beatriz Galindo, born in the city of Salamanca (1465-1535), had Latin skills that opened the door to a domestic job at court, which represented an important personal advancement for a young woman of humble origins. Queen Isabel's generosity, charitable inclination, and habit of assuming an almost paternal role towards her maids made it easier for Beatriz to enter into a very favourable marriage from a social and economic point of view with Francisco Ramirez, a widower at the time. This marriage, apparently promoted by the queen, has led to speculation that Beatriz's son, Fernando Ramírez Galindo, may have been the son of King Ferdinand, given the preferential treatment and privileges granted to both the child and his mother after the death of Francisco Ramírez, to whom Beatriz was married for nine years.

Beatriz's relationship with the monarchy remained close even after she was widowed, as she lent considerable sums to Ferdinand the Catholic and Charles I, both of whom were in financial straits due to the demands of the wars. While Francisco Ramírez, known as 'the Gunner,' left a more visible mark in terms of administrative and military merits, the figure of Beatriz stood out thanks to her ability to manage and multiply her husband's inheritance. She used these resources to promote important works in Madrid, such as the Hospital de la Concepción de la Madre de Dios and the convents of Concepción Jerónima and Concepción Francisca, ensuring that her name remained linked to these foundations.

	The immense fortune that Beatrice accumulated from her husband's offices and earnings was the foundation of her social and economic success. Following the model of the noble ladies of the time, she invested as a patron in charity, religion and art, which consolidated her reputation and her family's future prestige.
Links	https://dbe.rah.es/biografias/10051/beatriz-galindo https://doi.org/10.14201/shhmo202143271104 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OKI8Nf2eU4o

Number	7
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Patio de Escuelas, 1, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.9614, -5.66728
Images	

Description	Feliciana Enríquez de Guzmán (1570-1647), a prominent Sevillian writer, was praised by Lope de Vega in Laurel de Apolo as a woman advanced in arts and letters, although she remained outside the aesthetic precepts of his Arte nuevo de hacer comedias. Married twice, she chose her own style inspired by the classics, as evidenced by her work Los jardines y campos Sabeos, a tragicomedy in two parts completed in 1619 and publicly performed in 1623 before Philip IV in Seville.
Links	https://dbe.rah.es/biografias/6675/feliciana-enriquez-de-guzman https://youtu.be/bDTJh5oQ_D4?si=IH_mp_7uLj6Ox1FG

Number	8
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Palacio de Anaya, Salamanca, Castilla y León, España
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96180921399135, -5.665774603684318
Images	

Description	<p>Dolores Cebrián Fernández Villegas (1881-1973). She was born in Salamanca and was the daughter of a military man from Salamanca, a doctor and university professor. She studied to be a teacher and later became a teacher in Salamanca, a post she later resigned to become a professor of science in Toledo. She moved to Paris to study Biology at the Sorbonne and, on her return, took up a teaching post at the Institución Libre de Enseñanza in Madrid, a modern school where young people were taught who would take their innovative teacher as a model. Miguel Unamuno (1864-1936), a great friend of the Cebrián family, referred to Dolores as having "the head of a man".</p>	
Links	https://fpabloiglesias.es/entrada-db/13920_cebrian-fernandez-villegas-dolores/	

Number	9	
City name	Salamanca	
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722	
Name of the point of interest	University of Salamanca, Patio de Escuelas, 37008 Salamanca	
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96153, -5.66798	
Images		

Description	<p>Matilde Cherner, born in Salamanca in 1833 to a mother from Aldeadávila and a father from Cadiz, died at her home in Madrid on 15 August 1880. Matilde Cherner was one of the great writers and journalists of 19th century Spain, who had to sign her articles and books with the pseudonym Rafael Luna. She was very multifaceted and politically incorrect for her time, a republican, democrat, federalist and feminist who fought for the equality of women in her philosophy. She was a woman who was fluent in Latin and French and from her writings we can deduce that she was a cultured woman, well read and interested in music. Almost everything she wrote was published in newspapers and magazines. Her social and political commitment and her clear republicanism was a constant throughout her life, which by the way was short, 47 years.</p>	
Links	<p>https://lacronicadesalamanca.com/276505-la-salmantina-que-escribia-con-nombre-de-hombre/</p>	

Number	10
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Pl. de los Bandos, 3, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.966880865427186, -5.664463673116093
Images	

Description	<p>Carmen Martín Gaité (Salamanca, 8 December 1925 - Madrid, 23 July 2000). Spanish writer. She graduated in Philosophy and Arts at the University of Salamanca, where she had her first contact with the theatre, participating as an actress in several plays. In 1950 she moved to Madrid and met Ignacio Aldecoa, who introduced her to the literary circle that would come to be known as the Generation of '55 or Post-war Generation. In 1955 he published his first work, <i>El balneario</i> (The Spa), for which he won the Café Gijón Prize. Two years later, he received the Nadal Prize for <i>Entre visillos</i>. He obtained his doctorate in 1972, presenting his thesis <i>Usos amorosos del XVIII del XVIII en España</i> at the University of Madrid. In 1976 he compiled his poetry in <i>A rachas</i> and two years later he did the same with his short stories in <i>Cuentos completos</i>. At the same time she works as a journalist in newspapers and magazines such as <i>Diario16</i>, <i>Cuadernos hispanoamericanos</i>, <i>Revista de Occidente</i>, <i>El País</i>, <i>El Independiente</i> and <i>ABC</i>, where she is a literary critic and translator. Finally, it is interesting to establish connections between prominent women in history. Saint Teresa of Jesus left a deep imprint on Carmen Martín Gaité, who acted as historical advisor for the TVE television series on the life of Saint Teresa.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.cervantes.es/bibliotecas/documentacion/espanol/ https://youtu.be/uYLqOpyV2x4?si=mS0INFeakeS5polg</p>

Number	11
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Faculty of Philosophy and Letters, University of Salamanca, P.º Francisco Tomás y Valiente, 37007 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96809817465218, -5.678417528865349

Images	
Description	<p>María del Rosario López Piñuelas (Salamanca, 28 October 1943) is a Spanish actress who, as a student of Philosophy and Literature, participated in several plays. She later studied at the Escuela Oficial de Cine (Official Film School). She worked in theatre and television, notably in the series <i>Los camioneros</i>, by Mario Camus; <i>El pícaro</i>, by Fernando Fernán Gómez; <i>Entre visillos</i>, by Miguel Picazo; <i>Fortunata y Jacinta</i>, by Mario Camus; <i>Los gozos y las sombras</i>, by Rafael Moreno Alba; <i>Los pazos de Ulloa</i>, by Gonzalo Suárez, and <i>Un día volveré</i>, by Paco Betriú. She received the Goya Award for Best Supporting Actress in 1997 for <i>Secretos del corazón</i>. She was awarded the Gold Medal for Merit in the Fine Arts in 2008. In 2021, the director Chema de la Peña made a documentary film entitled <i>Me cuesta hablar de mí</i>; this film presents a journey about the actress from her childhood to the present day, with testimonies of López at different stages of her life.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.buscabiografias.com/biografia/verDetalle/5303/Charo%20Lopez https://youtu.be/P3MXWtWY -Q?si=1YhalxBgAOoPQ-ps</p>

Number	12
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Faculty of Philology of the University of Salamanca, Pl. de Anaya, s/n, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96167165007253, -5.665503084274697

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>Helena Pimenta is a Spanish stage director, playwright and theatre director. She was director of the Compañía Nacional de Teatro Clásico from 2011 to 2019. In 1993 she was awarded the Premio Nacional de Teatro. She holds a degree in English and French Philology from the University of Salamanca. During her studies, she read theatre in Spanish, English and French, which would be a solid basis for her later work.</p> <p>Her theatrical vocation was late and she came to it indirectly, using drama as a tool for teaching foreign languages when she was a teacher at the Koldo Mitxelena Secondary School in Rentería. The students found a meeting place around theatre, exploring different disciplines and becoming the protagonists of their own training. This is how Pimenta discovered what would become the centre of her professional and personal life. She is the first woman to head the Compañía Nacional de Teatro Clásico (CNTC) since its foundation, and an expert in Shakespeare's work.</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>https://elpais.com/cultura/2019/09/11/actualidad/1568223229_212366.html https://youtu.be/1NbYeqPozZ8?si=Br-e9_KJloEN0IIQ https://youtu.be/LQNw_wzEZwl?si=xwkAD2z9ImW9BRQy</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>13</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Salamanca</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722</p>
<p>Name of the point of interest</p>	<p>Faculty of Geography and History, University of Salamanca, C. Cervantes, s/n, 37001 Salamanca</p>

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96309776049542, -5.667906068438917
Images	
Description	Teresa Vicente Mosquete, PhD in Geography and Master in European Communities and Human Rights. Professor of Geography at the University of Salamanca and of the multidisciplinary programme Interdisciplinary Gender Studies. Participant in the Socrates teaching exchange programme since 1996 at the Universities of Lyon II, London Guildhall, Iceland, Pisa, Budapest, Rome, Tre, Riga and Porto. Her research interests are geography and gender, and the history of geographical thought and the evolution of geography.
Links	https://acortar.link/z9nJJa

Number	14
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Courtyard of Minor Schools, University of Salamanca, Patio de Escuelas, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96162, -5.66763

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>María de Maeztu was a teacher, pedagogue, headmistress, lecturer, feminist and like so many other women, she was forgotten by a history that denied her the place and recognition she deserved. As her words record, her life was destined to improve the situation of Spanish women through education, through a comprehensive education that would encourage and favour their "equal and integral" participation in the society and culture of the Spain of her time. A member of a family of thinkers and artists, she was a student teacher, a disciple of Ortega y Gasset and a scholarship holder of the Junta para la Ampliación de Estudios to complete her studies in various European countries, Belgium, Switzerland, Italy and England, which greatly influenced her training and her ideas on education.</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>https://laescueladelarepublica.es/biografias/maria-de-maetzu/ https://www.rtve.es/play/videos/mujeres-para-un-siglo/mujeres-para-siglo-maria-maetzu-educacion/713453/ https://youtu.be/jNBppY-qOk?si=-0ibk-f-n0tl81bp</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>15</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Salamanca</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722</p>
<p>Name of the point of interest</p>	<p>Av. de Filiberto Villalobos, 97, 37007 Salamanca</p>

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.97143616261621, -5.676390713420022
Images	
Description	<p>Luisa, a member of the Medrano family linked to the Bravo de Lagunas de Aienza family, would have had a solid education, possibly obtained in Salamanca or under the tutelage of a private teacher. However, she did not hold a chair at the University. Despite his talent and presumed royal support, social and regulatory restrictions limited his opportunities. Her life was marked by obstacles that hindered the full development of her intellectual potential, reflecting the gender inequality of the time. She married late, after her time in Salamanca, and died before 44. These facts underline her importance as a representative figure of the difficulties faced by women in history.</p>
Links	<p>https://revistas.uva.es/index.php/invehisto/article/view/3878 https://doi.org/10.14201/shhmo2022441187217</p>

Number	16
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Faculty of Law, University of Salamanca, P.º Francisco Tomás y Valiente, s/n, 37007 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.969324465495745, -5.676479913428847

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>María Telo Núñez (Cáceres 1915-Madrid 2014) was a Spanish jurist of renowned prestige who stood out mainly for her activism in defence of democracy and the struggle for women's equality. She received an Honorary Doctor from the University of Salamanca and was awarded the Clara Campoamor Prize. She was also a member of several national and international associations and organisations whose aims included the defence of women's rights and her active participation in the General Codification Commission. Her legal and political work was decisive in the reform of the Civil Code in favour of women's rights and equality. She is the author of the book "Mi lucha por la igualdad jurídica de la mujer" (My fight for women's legal equality).</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>https://pares.mcu.es/ParesBusquedas20/catalogo/description/12765731 https://youtu.be/IPkt-tEbNA8?si=jN0T0qRQLByAiUrd</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>17</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Salamanca</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722</p>
<p>Name of the point of interest</p>	<p>CEMUSA, Aulario de San Isidro, University of Salamanca, Pl. San Isidro, 1, 37002 Salamanca</p>

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96249808651586, -5.666548799999961
Images	
Description	Dr. Ana Díaz Medina was Professor of History at the University of Salamanca. For more than four decades and until her retirement, she developed a valuable teaching and research activity at the University of Salamanca. Since 2002, she has been director of the Centre for Women's Studies at the University of Salamanca (CEMUSA). She promoted numerous activities and initiatives through the CEMUSA. One of these initiatives was the CEMUSA journal.
Links	https://fundacionadm.weebly.com/dra-dordf-ana-diacuteaz-medina.html

Number	18
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	House-Museum Unamuno, C/ Libreros, 25, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.961423787273944, -5.6674071556920245

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>Magdalena Garretas Sastre (Vizcaya 1912-Barcelona 2011). After finishing her high school studies at the Instituto Femenino in Bilbao, she went to Salamanca as a scholarship holder at the Colegio de Santiago. In Salamanca, she studied Philosophy and Letters between 1930 and 1934 and graduated with an Extraordinary Prize. She was an assistant to Miguel de Unamuno, teaching until the University of Salamanca was closed due to the war. Subsequently, she passed the exams for the Greek secondary school teaching posts, becoming a teacher in Cádiz. She taught until her retirement in 1982.</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>http://ramiro53-64.blogspot.com/2015/10/magdalenas-garretas-sastre.html</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>19</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Salamanca</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722</p>
<p>Name of the point of interest</p>	<p>House of Santa Teresa de Jesús. C/ Condes de Crespo Rascón, 25, 37002 Salamanca</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest</p>	<p>40.96796487273366, -5.665372697959441</p>

Images

Description

Santa Teresa de Jesús (Gotarrendura, Ávila, 1515 - Alba de Tormes, 1582). She was the first woman to be awarded an Honorary Doctorate by the University of Salamanca. Spanish religious and mystical writer, also known as Saint Teresa of Avila. Teresa de Jesús is the religious name adopted by Teresa de Cepeda y Ahumada, daughter of Alonso Sánchez de Cepeda, a probable descendant of Jewish converts, and Beatriz de Ahumada, a member of a noble family from Ávila. Her life and spiritual development can be traced through her autobiographical works, which include some of her major works: Book of Life (written between 1562 and 1565), the Spiritual Relations, the Book of Foundations (begun in 1573 and published in 1610) and her nearly five hundred Letters.

Fray Luis de León had the opportunity to examine, correct and approve the autograph of the so-called 'Big Book', the title that the Saint used to refer to her work 'Life'. This text was written by Saint Teresa in her cell in the Monastery of San José de Ávila between 1563 and 1565, and at a time when she was approaching fifty years of age.

From a literary perspective, it is relevant to point out that it was in the 'Casa de Santa Teresa' in Salamanca where the Saint found the inspiration to compose her famous poem 'I live without living in me'. Saint Teresa of Jesus is presented as a figure with a significant message for contemporary women, offering teachings that transcend time. It is important to highlight her friendly charisma; she was a loyal friend, prioritising friendship over her position of authority.

	In her work 'The Foundations', Teresa recounts the suffering and tears that accompanied the farewells, expressing her grief at leaving her 'daughters and sisters', aware that she would never see them again. Her sadness at saying goodbye contrasts with her determination to continue her work. In addition, it is pertinent to highlight her leadership skills.
Links	https://www.biografiasyvidas.com/biografia/t/teresa_dejesus.htm https://youtu.be/dpilbfjBdms?si=HFPfUH09aZf9LqZT

Number	20
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	House of Doña María la Brava. Pl. de los Bandos, 7, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96702977134769, -5.6649780020135205
Images	
Description	Born in the palace of Monroy in Plasencia, she moved to Salamanca until the end of her days. The life of María de Monroy is set in the context of the conflict between noble factions in the city of Salamanca in the mid-15th century. The story tells of the revenge taken by María de Monroy, who led a group of armed men from Villalba de los Llanos in pursuit of her sons' murderers. Having dispatched spies, they managed to discover their whereabouts in Portugal. María and her men arrived at the house where the brothers Gómez and Alonso had sought refuge, and there she took her revenge on them, returning later to Salamanca with the heads of both, which she threw on the tombs of her sons, buried in the church of Santo Tomé. The people nicknamed María Rodríguez de Monroy, María la Brava, who has become an archetype of female fortitude and severity in the face of such a singularly gruesome event.
Links	https://dbe.rah.es/biografias/43027/maria-rodriguez-de-monroy https://youtu.be/nivPGAOMVII?si=nkmRGrTxAJOHZBeA

Number	21
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	C/ Doña Gonzala Santana, 37001 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.964522931812134, -5.661725909205492
Images	
Description	<p>Gonzala Santana, a wealthy woman from Salamanca, who was known among the citizens as 'La pollita de oro' (the little golden chick), due to her generosity and fortune. She was born in Valladolid in 1844, because her father, José Santana, was a rich farmer from Alaejos. But she considered herself to be from Salamanca, because her mother, Petra Delgado, was from Salamanca. She was orphaned when she was young and rich. We are talking about the end of the 19th century. Despite the wealth she possessed, Gonzala did not forget the world in which she lived, and she was fully aware that she was fortunate, so her altruism was considerable, giving money to those who needed it and asked for it, changing their destiny.</p> <p>Gonzala Santana financed the construction and maintenance of the chapel of Nuestra Señora de los Dolores, located in the Vera Cruz Chapel in Salamanca, motivated both by her religious devotion and by her financial resources. She was known as 'La Pollita de Oro', a nickname that referred to her unmarried status and her outstanding fortune.</p> <p>Among her many contributions were the acquisition of the organ for the Purísima Church and the construction of the María Auxiliadora School. She also made a significant donation by donating an aeroplane. Gonzala Santana resided in the house currently occupied by the Hotel Eunice.</p>

	According to the newspapers of the time, every morning there were long lines of people lining up as far as the Plaza Mayor, who came to ask for his help. He also made a significant contribution to education, enabling 200 children to attend university.
Links	https://lacronicadesalamanca.com/280926-la-rica-heredera-que-repartio-su-fortuna-en-becas/ https://youtu.be/shqR1znLrh8?si=g_AByhhLOTf8DSRJ

Number	22
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	House where she lived. Pl. de Monterrey, 3, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96544497475316, -5.66665810201415
Images	
Description	Gonzala Santana, a wealthy woman from Salamanca, who was known among the citizens as 'La pollita de oro' (the little golden chick), due to her generosity and fortune. She was born in Valladolid in 1844, because her father, José Santana, was a rich farmer from Alaejos. But she considered herself to be from Salamanca, because her mother, Petra Delgado, was from Salamanca. She was orphaned when she was young and rich. We are talking about the end of the 19th century. Despite the wealth she possessed, Gonzala did not forget the world in which she lived, and she was fully aware

	<p>that she was fortunate, so her altruism was considerable, giving money to those who needed it and asked for it, changing their destiny.</p> <p>Gonzala Santana financed the construction and maintenance of the chapel of Nuestra Señora de los Dolores, located in the Vera Cruz Chapel in Salamanca, motivated both by her religious devotion and by her financial resources. She was known as 'La Pollita de Oro', a nickname that referred to her unmarried status and her outstanding fortune.</p> <p>Among her many contributions were the acquisition of the organ for the Purísima Church and the construction of the María Auxiliadora School. She also made a significant donation by donating an aeroplane. Gonzala Santana resided in the house currently occupied by the Hotel Eunice.</p> <p>According to the newspapers of the time, every morning there were long lines of people lining up as far as the Plaza Mayor, who came to ask for his help. He also made a significant contribution to education, enabling 200 children to attend university.</p>
Links	<p>https://lacronicadesalamanca.com/280926-la-rica-heredera-que-repartio-su-fortuna-en-becas/</p> <p>https://youtu.be/shqR1znLrh8?si=g_AByhhLOTf8DSRJ</p>

Number	23
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Plaza Mayor, 1, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.965650179995635, -5.664105071136101

Images

Description

Berenguela of Castile (1180 - 8 November 1246) was Queen of León (1197-1204) and of Castile (1217-1246). The first-born daughter of Alfonso VIII of Castile and Eleanor of England, she was recognised as heir to the throne until the birth of her brother Sancho in 1181, who died the same year, restoring Berenguela's position as successor.

In 1188, when she was about eight, she was betrothed to Prince Conrad of Germany, an arrangement that did not prosper. Later, in 1197, she married Alfonso IX of León, her second cousin, to consolidate peace between the two kingdoms. This union was annulled in 1204 by Pope Innocent III due to consanguinity, although the children born of this marriage, including Ferdinand III, were considered legitimate.

After the death of her brother Henry I in 1217, Berenguela assumed the throne of Castile, but soon abdicated in favour of her son Ferdinand III, thus unifying the kingdoms of Castile and León. Until she died in 1246, she exercised considerable political influence, advising her son and taking an

	active part in the kingdom's administration. She was buried in the monastery of Las Huelgas in Burgos.
Links	https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf https://dbe.rah.es/biografias/8477/berenguela-de-castilla https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B4HWI1v9d5o&ab_channel=EsferaHispanica

Number	24
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Plaza Mayor, 1, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.965650179995635, -5.664105071136101
Images	
Description	She was governor of Salamanca from 1369 to 1381 due to her marriage to Enrique de Trastámara, who became king of Castile after defeating his brother Pedro I "The Cruel". During the war she actively supported her husband. As King of Castile, Juana led the siege of Zamora, which was surrendered in 1373.
Links	https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf https://dbe.rah.es/biografias/13535/juana-manuel https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jyUvOf_KuQo&ab_channel=BioPicChannel

Number	25
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Plaza Mayor, 1, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.965650179995635, -5.664105071136101
Images	
Description	Doña Leonor de Aragón (1358-1382) was Lady of Salamanca for one year, a position she held when her husband, Juan I, succeeded her father Enrique II of Trastámara in 1379. Her death in 1382 endangered peace between Aragon and Castile.
Links	https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf

Number	26
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Plaza Mayor, 1, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.965650179995635, -5.664105071136101
Images	
Description	Doña María de Aragón (1396-1445) became governor of Salamanca in 1440-1445, married to King Juan II. During these years the city, like the rest of the kingdom, was at loggerheads between the detractors and supporters of Álvaro de Luna, the King's chief adviser. In an attempt to defuse these clashes, the King handed over the government of the city to his wife, who tried to mediate between the two sides, but her untimely death frustrated his efforts.
Links	https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tx2cXdvnIac&ab_channel=BioPicChannel

Number	27
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Plaza Mayor, 1, 37002 Salamanca

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.965650179995635, -5.664105071136101
Images	
Description	<p>Doña María of Portugal (1313-1357) was a leading figure of medieval Iberian royalty, the daughter of King Alfonso IV of Portugal and Beatriz of Castile. She married Alfonso XI of Castile in 1328, consolidating an alliance between the two peninsular kingdoms. However, their marriage was marked by tensions due to the monarch's extramarital affair with Leonor de Guzmán, who gained a predominant place at the Castilian court. Maria of Portugal was noted for her fight for the rights of her son, Pedro I of Castile, and her firm defence of the legitimacy of the line of succession, confronting the political intrigues of her time. Her figure reflects the complexities of marital alliances and power disputes in 14th-century Castile.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RGaUGibo01o&ab_channel=BioPicChannel</p>

Number	28
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Plaza Mayor, 1, 37002 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.965650179995635, -5.664105071136101

Images

Description

María de Molina (1260-1321) was a key figure in the politics of the kingdom of Castile during the 13th and 14th centuries. A member of the León nobility, she married Sancho IV of Castile, making her queen consort between 1284 and 1295. Her political influence transcended her reign, playing a crucial role as regent in times of dynastic crisis. She was queen three times: first as queen consort during the reign of Sancho IV; then as queen regent between 1295 and 1301 after the death of her husband, leading the kingdom during the minority of her son Ferdinand IV; and finally as queen regent again between 1312 and 1321, after the death of Ferdinand IV, assuming the government on behalf of her grandson Alfonso XI. As lieutenant, she had administrative and judicial control over several lands in León and Castile, using this power to consolidate royal authority in a context of internal rebellions and external threats. Her diplomatic and strategic skills and her ability to form alliances made her a fundamental pillar in the stability and continuity of the Castilian monarchy. María de Molina is remembered as a skilful mediator and politician, whose legacy is strengthening the Trastámara dynasty and the preservation of the unity of the kingdom at critical moments.

Links

<https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf>
<https://archivohistoria.com/maria-de-molina/>

	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qfEu7x7zJU&ab_channel=BioPicChanne !
--	--

Number	29
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Church of Sancti-Spiritus. Rda. de Sancti-Spíritus, 24, 37001 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96585115475159, -5.658807158381673
Images	
Description	They lived in a convent next to the church of Sancti Spíritus, but unlike other convents, only women of the nobility could enter this one. Furthermore, there was no enclosure, so they could go out into the street and receive visitors. King Alfonso X "The Wise" granted them the title of Commanderesses in 1268.
Links	https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf

Number	30
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722

Name of the point of interest	Church of San Esteban, Pl. Concilio de Trento, s/n, 37001 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96128252736372, -5.663443269706166
Images	
Description	According to legend, these women were locked in cells in the walls of the churches; and it is said that in Salamanca there were walled women in the churches of Sancti Spiritus, San Esteban, Santa María, San Sebastián and San Juan de Bárbalos. However, there are those who say that they were not walled in and that they were dedicated to visiting the sick, making liturgical clothes and clothes for the offices, etc.
Links	https://www.ciudaddesaberes.es/guias/Las%20mujeres%20de%20la%20Historia%20de%20Salamanca.pdf

Number	31
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Convent of Las Dueñas, Pl. Concilio de Trento, s/n, 37001 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96128252736372, -5.663443269706166

Images

Description

"La Negrita" (1676-1748) She was a princess called Chikaba who was kidnapped and brought from Africa as an exotic gift for King Charles II. He gave her as a gift to the Marquis of Mancera, who granted her freedom. In 1704 she entered the Penitencia convent as a servant and became famous for having the gift of prophecy and for performing miracles. She was the first black woman in Spain to enter a cloistered convent.

Links

Number	32
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Central Food Market of Salamanca, Pl. del Mercado, 0, 37001 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.964685163364, -5.663227957244231

Images	
Description	<p>The market was filled with the voices and cries of Romana "La merenguera" who sweetened the lives of the people of Salamanca with her "¡Merengues, rosquillas, a cuaaaaarto! Romana was a woman much loved and respected by all the residents of Salamanca and she represents all those artisan women who were great entrepreneurs in our city.</p>
Links	

Number	33
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	C. Lucero, 2, 37001 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96171914888304, -5.660128064103848
Images	
Description	<p>The 'damianitas' of Salamanca were the first nuns of the Order of Saint Clare in the city, established around 1230. Initially, a group of women, led by Doña Urraca, practised religious life together in a small hermitage called Santa María. Inspired by the life of Saint Clare and the sisters of the Monastery of San Damiano in Assisi, some of them travelled to Italy to learn first-hand about their way of life. On their return, they returned the Rule written by St. Clare and two corporals made by her, which are still kept in the monastery.</p>
Links	https://www.claune.org/2017/10/02/hermanas-clarisas-de-salamanca/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Number	34
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Iglesia de San Esteban, Pl. Concilio de Trento, s/n, 37001 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.96128252736372, -5.663443269706166

Images	
Description	<p>Inés de Alimógenes, a 14th century noblewoman from Salamanca, was a prominent benefactor of the Convent of San Esteban in Salamanca. Together with her husband, Juan Alfonso Godínez, she financed the construction of the main chapel and the chapel of Santo Domingo in the convent church, thus ensuring a burial place for her family. In addition, his contributions enabled the construction of the abbey and the convent's fence, contributing significantly to its expansion and consolidation. His patronage was crucial for the architectural and spiritual development of the convent during the first third of the 14th century.</p>
Links	<p>https://revista-norbaarte.unex.es/index.php/NRA/article/view/700?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p>

Number	35
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Patio de Escuelas, 1, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.9614, -5.66728
Images	

Description	<p>Graduate in Law from the University of Salamanca (1975). She was a researcher at the Université Libre de Bruxelles (1977-1978). Doctorate from the Complutense University of Madrid (UCM) in 1979. Her thesis on The Committee of Representatives of the European Communities was published by the Centro de Estudios Políticos y Constitucionales in 1980.</p>	
Links	<p>https://colegiodeemeritos.es/araceli-mangas-martin/</p>	

Number	36
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Patio de Escuelas, 1, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.9614, -5.66728
Images	

Description	<p>María Dolores Gómez Molleda (1922-2017) was a prominent Spanish historian, professor of Contemporary History at the University of Salamanca. Her academic work focused on studying social and political movements in 20th-century Spain, with special attention to the Second Republic and the Civil War. Gómez Molleda is renowned for her methodological rigour and commitment to historical research, contributing significantly to the knowledge of contemporary Spanish history. Her legacy lives on in numerous publications and the training of generations of historians.</p>	
Links	<p>https://revistas.usal.es/uno/index.php/0213-2087/article/view/17997/18354</p>	

Number	37
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Patio de Escuelas, 1, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.9614, -5.66728
Images	

Description	<p>Josefina Cuesta Bustillo (Villamolón, 1947 - Salamanca, 2021) was a prominent historian, professor of Contemporary History at the University of Salamanca, and a pioneer in memory studies in Spain. After earning her doctorate with a thesis in International Social History, she furthered her training at the École des Hautes Études in Paris under the direction of Pierre Nora, where she acquired fundamental tools to introduce and develop this field in Spain. To her focus on historical memory, she added a commitment to gender studies, leading research on women's cultural networks and women's access to higher education, consolidating her place as a central figure in the dismissal of the role of women in contemporary history. Her achievements include founding the collection Memoria de Mujer, through which she published key works such as La Residencia de Señoritas and other women's cultural networks. Her collaboration with institutions such as the Fundación Ortega-Marañón underlined her ability to combine academic rigour with generosity and social commitment, leaving a lasting legacy in the study of memory and women's rights.</p>	
Links	<p>https://ortegaygasset.edu/ellas-querian-saber-in-memoriain-josefina-cuesta-bustillo/ https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Josefina_Cuesta_Bustillo</p>	

Number	38
City name	Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the City	40.97461125159016,-5.670096568261722
Name of the point of interest	Patio de Escuelas, 1, 37008 Salamanca
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	40.9614, -5.66728

Images

(Foto: Ángela Carraffa de Nava, primera Doctora en Filosofía y Letras, 1892 / Consuelo Flecha)

Description

Ángela Carraffa de Nava (Valladolid, 15 March 1873-Salamanca, 10 March 1950) was one of the pioneers in access to Spanish universities. Despite numerous difficulties, she was able to study at the University of Salamanca and the Central University of Madrid. She was the first woman in Spain to obtain a doctorate in philosophy and literature.

Links

https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/%C3%81ngela_Carraffa_de_Nava

2.2. Fort-de-France, France

In English

Number	1
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	Port de Fort-de-France

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.595848832900323, -61.05919738559836
Images	<p style="text-align: center;">Martinique 19. - FORT-de-FRANCE. - Les Charbonnières</p> <p><small>Source: Ville de Paris - Bibliothèque Marguerite Durand</small></p>
Description	<p>On March 25, 2017, the roundabout at the entrance to the port of Fort-de-France was named "Le Rond-Point des Charbonnières", in tribute to these women who in the 19th and 20th century played an important role in the social and working-class history of Martinique. Their job was to carry 40-kilo baskets on their heads to supply coal to the bunkers of the Compagnie Générale Transatlantique steamships that made the transatlantic crossing to export rum and sugar. It was a difficult, arduous and poorly-paid job. They were the first to organize themselves as a trade union and mutual aid and solidarity fund, and thus had a strong impact on the world of labor and trade unions.</p>
Links	-

Number	2
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	Place Paulette Nardal
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.607069811703838, -61.067930852749285

Images

Description

This square is named after Paulette Nardal (1896-1985), a writer, journalist, poet and activist from Martinique. She was the eldest of seven sisters, in the order Paule, known as Paulette, Emilie, Alice, Jane, Lucy, Cécyl and Andrée. Their father, Paul Nardal, grandson of a freed slave, was the island's first black engineer. Their mother, Louise Achille, was a mulatto schoolteacher.

In 1920, Paulette arrived in Paris to study English at the Sorbonne University. She became the first black woman to study at this French institution. Every Sunday, she and her sisters Jane and Andrée hosted a literary salon in their Clamart apartment, where they discussed the black question. Césaire, Senghor, Damas and a host of other prominent figures would attend, enabling them to lay the groundwork for the theory of Négritude, a cultural, political and literary movement that emerged in Paris in the 1930s.

In 1931, along with Haitian writer Léo Sajous and Guyanese writer René Maran, Paulette and Jane co-founded *La Revue du Monde Noir*, a bilingual French-English journal that served as a platform for black intellectuals and inspired intersectional feminism.

The Nardal sisters, and Paulette and Jeanne in particular, were key figures in the intellectual and cultural Négritude movement in Martinique and France. They played a key role in the recognition and valorization of black culture and identity, and in the fight against racism and social injustice. But like many women, their ideas and contributions have been overshadowed or attributed to men.

Links

<https://rfi.my/9EWghttps://www.radiofrance.fr/franceculture/podcasts/toute-une-vie/paulette-nardal-la-negritude-et-ses-soeurs-1896-1985-2706916>

Number	3
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	Loge émancipation féminine
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.60402580434711, -61.073072762897304
Images	
Description	<p>This building, located in the former Rue du Commerce, was the site of the “Émancipation féminine” lodge to which Claude Carbet (1893-1968) belonged, a Freemason who marked the birth of feminism in Martinique.</p> <p>Born Olympe Tricot, Claude Carbet caused a scandal when she began a 27-year relationship with Marie-Magdeleine Carbet (1902-1996), born Louise Eugénie Anna Marie-Magdeleine. Both women adopted the surname Carbet, an identification with their Martinican identity.</p> <p>On March 1, 1931, Claude Carbet gave a public lecture on “Female emancipation and human rights”, during which she denounced all forms of inequality, defended homosexuals, women’s right to control their own bodies and demanded the right to vote.</p>
Links	-

Number	4
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	« La Maison de Solange »

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.605684859773726, -61.071088045512546
Images	
Description	<p>“La Maison de Solange” is a space of the Union des Femmes de la Martinique (UFM), welcoming women over 18 in distress and victims of violence. It was inaugurated on October 24, 2014 and bears the name of Solange Fitte-Duval (1921-2014), president of the UFM from 1973 to 1993. She led numerous actions for the promotion and emancipation of Martinican women and is considered a pioneer of feminism in Martinique. She was also responsible for the “Femmes Martiniquaises” newspaper.</p>
Links	-

Number	5
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	Union des Femmes de la Martinique (UFM)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.604352911159646, -61.06860559140327
Images	

Description	<p>Jane Léro was a Martinican activist and feminist. She is known for her advocacy for women's rights and the promotion of gender equality in Martinique. She founded l'Union des Femmes de la Martinique (UFM), the first feminist organization.</p> <p>She is a significant figure in the social and political movements in Martinique during the 1940s and 1950s. Jane Léro also participated in local feminist movements and was a vocal advocate against gender inequalities and social injustices. She played an important role in raising awareness about the specific issues faced by Martinican women at that time and her work contributed to paving the way for future advancements in the fight for gender equality in the society.</p>
Links	https://youtu.be/EZ5lrGQf9ns

Number	6
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	École maternelle Suzanne Roussi
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.610764006286647, -61.08834063663805
Images	
Description	<p>Suzanne Roussi-Césaire, née en Martinique, était une écrivaine, une poétesse, une militante anticolonialiste et féministe et une personnalité culturelle. Elle a cofondé la revue littéraire "Tropiques" (1941-1945) avec son mari Aimé Césaire, offrant ainsi une tribune aux intellectuels et artistes caribéens. Comme beaucoup de femmes dans l'histoire, Suzanne Césaire a été éclipsée par la célébrité de son mari. Ses idées ont été non seulement peu lues et rarement analysées, mais aussi parfois mal attribuées. De plus, souvent racialisée et exotisée, Suzanne Césaire a été essentiellement associée au statut d'épouse d'Aimé Césaire. Elle est pourtant l'auteur d'une œuvre trop longtemps méconnue et pourtant essentielle à l'histoire littéraire de la Caraïbe.</p>
Links	

Number	7
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	Avenue Léona Gabriel
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.612389858503553, -61.04677363108858
Images	
Description	Léona Gabriel-Soïme (1891-1971), also known by the pseudonym Mademoiselle Estrella, was a Martinican biguine singer and is considered a monument of Martinican popular song.
Links	

Number	8
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	Rue Lumina Sophie
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.605910492383838, -61.04558428750041

Images	
Description	<p>Lumina Sophie also called Surprise was a Martinican activist and poet. She was an advocate for women’s rights, education, and workers’ rights. Surprise used her poetry to address social and political issues, and she was an influential figure in the cultural and political spheres of Martinique. She spoke out against the segregation and racism that persisted in Martinique after the abolition of slavery and took part in the southern insurrection of September 1870. She was arrested a few days later. After two trials, she was sentenced to forced labour for life. After giving birth in prison, she was transferred to the penal colony of Guyana where she died on December 15th, 1879.</p>
Links	

Number	9
City name	Fort-de-France (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279
Name of the point of interest	Rue Marie-Thérèse Gertrude
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.603104222944864, -61.085320009367194

Images	
Description	<p>Marie-Thérèse Gertrude is a scientific figure and primary school teacher. She entered the Sorbonne and became the first woman from Martinique and one of the first women in France to hold a chair in the Faculty of Science.</p>
Links	<p>https://youtu.be/HaB3NvRDOBw</p>

Number	<p>10</p>
City name	<p>Fort-de-France (Martinique)</p>
Latitude & Longitude of the City	<p>14.606182852364812, -61.0696303605279</p>
Name of the point of interest	<p>Rue Marie-Thérèse Lung-Fou</p>
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	<p>14.621533336423438, -61.074056683203565</p>
Images	
Description	<p>Marie-Thérèse Lung Fou (1909-1981) was a Martinican sculptor, draughtswoman, poet and storyteller. A native of Trois Ilets, she entered the École Nationale des Beaux-Arts in Paris in 1934. She quickly won numerous prizes and awards, and became the first sculptress from the French West Indies to be recognized.</p>

Links	https://awarewomenartists.com/artiste/marie-therese-julien-lung-fou/
Number	11
City name	Morne-Vert (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.703468915603043, -61.1277937524818
Name of the point of interest	Mairie du Morne Vert (Luce Lemaistre)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.70781916349246, -61.14424373108716
Images	
Description	Luce Lemaistre was Martinique's first female mayor. She was elected in 1949 in the new commune of Morne-Vert. Although her term was not long (2 years), at that time it was something important as women had just obtained the right to vote (in 1944).
Links	

Number	12
City name	Trois-Ilets (Martinique)
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.537693448828449, -61.03483177830107
Name of the point of interest	Collège Suzanne Roussi Césaire
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.539825626942092, -61.04179202098336

Images	
Description	<p>On December 20, 2018, the Collège des Trois-Ilets in the Pagerie district was renamed Suzanne-Roussi-Césaire. It's a tribute to the writer originally from this commune.</p>
Links	

Number	13
City name	Schoelcher
Latitude & Longitude of the City	14.614927068647066, -61.10386471009452
Name of the point of interest	Lycée Lumina Sophie
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	14.610787820976027, -61.09100974745019
Images	
Description	
Links	

2.3. Nicosia, Cyprus

In English	
Number	1

City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Aischilou' Avenue
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.026306416144344, 33.42913539969547
Images	n/a
Description	<p>This avenue provides an opportunity to delve into the history of women in theatre in Nicosia. On one side of the avenue, you'll find the rear aspect of Faneromeni School, while on the other side lies the location where Papadopoulos Theatre once stood. Back in the 1940s, women actors were considered a significant taboo for that era. Male actors often took on female roles. In 1891, a groundbreaking moment occurred when a Cypriot woman, Polixeni Fisentzidi, performed on the theatre stage. She was a student at Faneromeni's Female School. In the following years, both female and male students showcased more theatrical acts.</p> <p>Papadopoulo's Theatre graced this avenue from 1899 to 1967, establishing itself as the most esteemed theatre in Nicosia. Numerous theatrical performances, featuring female actors from both Cyprus and abroad, were held at this venue. Unfortunately, in 1967, the owners made the decision to demolish the theatre to make way for the construction of shops.</p>
Links	n/a

Number	2
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Zena Palace – Theognosia Zena Kanther
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.16820635907112, 33.35955091264231

Images

Description

Zena Palace is one of the first cinemas that existed in Cyprus, located in the center of Nicosia. It took its name from its owner, Princess Zena Kanther De Tyras, who was born in Tala, Paphos, on July 3, 1927, in a poor family. In 1967, Zena Kanther, after being spiritually adopted by Prince Paul Palaiologos-Krive, acquired a noble title, and became “Princess de Tyras.” Since then, along with the enormous wealth she gained from her marriage to the American millionaire Christian Kanther, Zena Kanther has been actively involved in significant philanthropic activities. She is the most prominent Cypriot philanthropist and benefactor of Cyprus, who also volunteered in the liberation struggle against the British.

Links

<https://www.cyprusalive.com/en/princess-zena-kanther-de-tyras>

Number

3

City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Liberty Monument
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.171820804727915, 33.37023840949762
Images	
Description	<p>The Liberty Monument was erected in 1973 to honor the fighters of EOKA during the Cyprus Liberation Struggle of 1955-1959. It is located within the Venetian walls. The grand monument contains several statues. At the top of the structure, a statue represents the “Clocks of Freedom” above two heroic EOKA fighters opening the chains to unlock the prison gate, allowing Greek Cypriot captives, farmers, and clergy to escape from British rule. The bronze figures of men and women of different ages are vividly depicted emerging from the darkness of the prison after a long time and witnessing the light of day. The fact that the official inauguration for this monument never took</p>

	place due to the tragic events of 1974 is a poignant irony. Just when the Cypriot Hellenism saw the light of the sun after a long time and was heading towards the ultimate good of freedom, the violent Turkish invasion suddenly overturned their hopes. The monument becomes a timeless symbol of struggle and hope for freedom.
Links	https://www.gpsmycity.com/attractions/liberty-monument-47404.html

Number	4
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Arsinoyis Street
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.16820635907112, 33.35955091264231

Description	The Arsinoyis Street took its name from Arsinoyi, a historical figure from ancient Cyprus. Arsinoyi was the wife of King Leontokrates of Cyprus during the Ptolemaic dynasty. Also known as Arsinoyi II, she was the queen of Cyprus in the 3rd century BCE and had significant influence in the political and cultural affairs of that era. During her reign, she conducted numerous
--------------------	---

	excavations and projects to improve Cypriot society. The street that bears her name recognizes the importance of Arsinoyi in the history of Cyprus and the Ptolemaic period, while also honoring her contributions to ancient Cypriot culture.
Links	https://www.adequatetravel.com/placeguide/Cyprus/ancient-arsinoe-in-cyprus-overview-prominent-features-history-interesting-facts?expand_article=1

Number	5
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organisations
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.17279284916245, 33.38436410901002
Images	
Description	The “Pancyprian Federation of Women’s Organizations” is an organization founded in Cyprus at the year of 1959 with the aim of promoting women’s rights and empowering women’s voices and participation in society. The Pancyprian Federation of Women’s Organizations operates throughout Cyprus and collaborates with various women’s organizations and communities on the island. The Pancyprian Federation of Women’s Organizations organizes events, conferences, seminars, and educational programs to raise awareness among the public about issues concerning women and to promote gender equality. Additionally, it cooperates with other entities and organizations to achieve its goals in advocating for women’s rights in Cyprus.
Links	https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=125710309243837 https://www.pogocy.com/%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%81%CE%AF%CE%B1/

Number	6
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Kostas and Rita Severis Foundation
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.17596482212924, 33.368745996004336
Images	

Description

The Liberty Monument was erected in 1973 to honor the fighters of EOKA during the Cyprus Liberation Struggle of 1955-1959. It is located within the Venetian walls. The grand monument contains several statues. At the top of the structure, a statue represents the “Clocks of Freedom” above two heroic EOKA fighters opening the chains to unlock the prison gate, allowing Greek Cypriot captives, farmers, and clergy to escape from British rule. The bronze figures of men and women of different ages are vividly depicted emerging from the darkness of the prison after a long time and witnessing the light of day. The fact that the official inauguration for this monument never took place due to the tragic events of 1974 is a poignant irony. Just when the Cypriot Hellenism saw the light of the sun after a long time and was heading towards the ultimate good of freedom, the violent Turkish invasion suddenly overturned their hopes. The monument becomes a timeless symbol of struggle and hope for freedom.

Links

<https://cvar.severis.org/el/museum/foundation/>

Number	7
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Catherine Cornaro
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.04803341378799, 33.442629900744144

Images

Description

Catherine Cornaro was the Queen of Cyprus and the wife of Peter I of Cyprus. Their marriage took place in 1382, and she became the Queen of Cyprus. Peter I and Catherine ruled the kingdom with dignity and success, strengthening Cyprus' relations with neighboring countries and promoting the prosperity of its people. After Peter I's death in 1392, Catherine continued to govern Cyprus as the Queen Mother for their son, James II. However, in 1398, James II removed Catherine from power and exiled her to Sicily, where she passed away at around the age of 60. Catherine Cornaro was known for her kindness and love for the people of Cyprus. Her reign marked a period of prosperity and cultural development for the Cypriot people.

Links

<https://www.cyprusalive.com/el/aikaterini-kornaro>

Number	8
City name	Nicosia

Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Diamantou Charalambous
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.17111098969133, 33.36051609016233
Images	
Description	<p>During the period when Cyprus was under British colonial rule, the island experienced a tumultuous time marked by constant strikes and demands for change. In those years, Cyprus served as a hub for ongoing protests and calls for reform. In May 1940, Diamantou Charalambous, a construction worker, played a revolutionary role. Her actions defied societal norms prevalent during that era.</p> <p>Diamantou courageously challenged gender stereotypes, rejecting the established norms that confined women to the private sphere as obedient mothers and housewives. In May 1940, she actively participated in a demonstration organized by unemployed construction workers in Nicosia. Her involvement led to a brutal assault by the police, who sought to quell the workers' demands for job opportunities from the colonial government. Unfortunately, specific details about the exact location and date of this incident are not available.</p>

Links	https://dialogos.com.cy/i-kipria-gineka-stous-ergatikous-agonas/
Number	9
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Faneromeni School
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.1734641005919, 33.36321541134646
Images	
Description	<p>The Ottoman period in Cyprus was during 1571 – 1878. During the last decades of the Ottoman period in Cyprus, primary education began to develop in the Orthodox community of the island. Faneromeni School was founded in this context, which was the first primary school for girls in Cyprus. The school was intended for the daughters of the wealthy families of the Greek Cypriot community and was founded on the initiative of Archbishop Makarios I in 1859.</p> <p>The general situation for Girls Schools in Cyprus was as follows: In Limassol, the first Girls School was founded in 1911, the second in 1923, and the third in 1938. In Larnaka, the Girls School – Parthenagogio Skalas and Evryviadion</p>

	<p>Girls School – Parthenagogio Evryviadion were merged in 1906 and separated again in 1929. In Pafos, a Girls School was established in 1880. In Famagusta, a Girls School was established in 1887 and in 1926 it was divided into two schools, the second of which operated until 1941. In Kyrenia, the Girls School was opened in 1887 (Michailidou 2017).</p> <p>Regarding Faneromeni School, during its first year 35 female students were studying in all six classes of the school. Twenty years later, in 1880, the School had 152 female students and it was the only school for female students in Nicosia. During its first years the classes were reading, writing, mathematics, religion classes, Greek history classes and handcraft classes. Female students learned the values that a girl should follow in order to compromise with society’s values. Such values were modesty, care, diligence and obedience.</p> <p>Back at that time, women were considered ashamed to work. Because of that, the school committee used to give scholarships to girls with fewer opportunities and from poor villages. In this way, they gave them the opportunity to be educated in order to become teachers.</p> <p>Inside Faneromeni School the first higher institution for female teachers was established back in 1903. Female teachers used to be paid less than male teachers and also, married female teachers weren’t allowed to work and they were obligated to stop working as teachers when they were planning to get married.</p> <p>The Higher institution was shut down in 1937 and the building was a part of the Pancyprian Highschool institute which welcomed only female students. In 1975, was the only year that the school was a mixed-gender school. Back then, directress and female teachers of Faneromeni School, had a crucial involvement in the development of women’s associations. One example was Theano Parouti – Liasidou, who was a directress of the School from 1887 until 1901. Later she quitted because she was about to get married, and Eleni Christou was placed as a directress of the school. Some years later, in 1914, they managed to create a women’s association in Nicosia.</p> <p>In recent years Faneromeni school had a kindergarten, primary school, and high school. Now, it works as a department of the School of Architecture of the University of Cyprus.</p>
Links	n/a

Number	10
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Anna Tiggiridou

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.1734641005919, 33.36321541134646
Images	
Description	<p>Anna Tiggidou was born in Lefkara, attended the Parthenagogeio Faneromenis, and studied dentistry at Ecole Dentaire de Paris. She became the first Cypriot dentist and upon her return to Cyprus, she opened a dental practice in Larnaca (1923-1939). During World War II, she relocated to Lefkara, where she continued her practice until the end. She participated in the Panhellenic Dental Congress in Athens (1955) and married the teacher Achilleas Michael Tiggidis from Lefkara.</p>
Links	https://cyprustimes.com/koinonia/oi-gynaikeies-proties-stin-kypro/

Number	11
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	The Royal Hall
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.17015802637053, 33.365564053675186

Images	
Description	<p>The Royal Hall used to be one of the first cinemas in Nicosia until the end of the 40s. Today, the same building is being used as an event venue. On the 25th of April 1955, the Pancyprian Protest of Female Workers took place there and the protest was about social security and for a better working environment. In the announcement, they were mentioning the right to be absent from work when sick, the security of the widows and orphans, and equal payment between men and women. On the 9th of July 1959, there was another crucial event in this place. The founding conference of the Pancyprian Federation of Women’s associations took place there. At this conference there were 1500 female participants from around Cyprus. This conference was about the right of vote for women, for equal rights between men and women in social and political life, for social security, for legislative security of mothers and children, for equal payment between men and women, for whole education and professional skills of children, for the security of all female workers, and for a peaceful and independent Cyprus.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iukMUH8MCYA https://www.panacoustics.com/the-royal-hall.html</p>

Number	12
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	Ledras Street – Loukia Nikolaidou
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.174013558180086, 33.36152208435962

Images	
Description	<p>Ledras Street is a major shopping street in central Nicosia. Around Ledras Street, Loukia Nikolaidou, the first female painter in Cyprus, had one of her first exhibitions in 1934. Loukia Nikolaidou, was the first female painter that studied Art abroad. She was born in 1909 in Limassol and died in 1994, at Penn in England. Back in the time, she decided to go abroad, in Paris and study Art. During that time, that was a very brave decision since decisions like that were not aligned with what the society would expect from Loukia to do. Societal stereotypes and gender norms would expect Loukia to stay at home and start her own family. She studied in Paris at the Colarossi Academy and then she continued to the School Nationale Superieure des Beaux-Arts. She came back to Cyprus in 1933, and she made her first three exhibitions, both in Nicosia and Limassol. The exhibition in Nicosia, was around Ledras Street, the exact location is unknown. The exhibitions were in 1934, 1935 and 1936. Later on, she continued with other great and famous exhibitions both personal and in collaboration with other famous artists. In 1992, there was an exhibition dedicated to her work at the National Gallery in Nicosia.</p>
Links	https://www.the-real-cyprus.com/ledra-street.html

Number	13
City name	Nicosia
Latitude & Longitude of the City	33.382275
Name of the point of interest	The Shelter for working women
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	35.173102, 33.361791

Images	
Description	<p>The Shelter for working women, has been located in Sokratous 19th Avenue since 1960. Anastasia Koumbaridou had the idea for this initiative, since the women that worked in the area were coming from rural areas and they didn't have any place to rest during their break from work.</p> <p>Anastasia Koumbaridou, asked from the Faneromenis Church to give this place to women for this purpose. Back then, there were beds and other facilities and up to 75 women were having a place to relax and eat during their work-break times. Also, it was also a place where female workers and their trade unions had the opportunity to meet and talk about any working issues. Today, the Shelter is still working but not in the same dynamic as the earlier years.</p>
Links	n/a

2.4. Athens, Greece

In English

Number	1
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.983806067761044, 23.727538580803987
Name of the point of interest	Sappho's Statue-Onassis Cultural Foundation
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.958205349168935, 23.718996365161345

Images

Description

The statue of Sappho in Athens was made by Antoine Bourdelle and is located in Onassis Foundation. Sappho (~ 630 - 570 BC), was a Greek lyric poet from Lesbos, particularly well-known from antiquity to the present day. Sappho wrote love poems, hymns to the gods and epithalamia (wedding songs). Her poetry vibrated with spontaneity and intense emotions. Little is known about her life. It is likely that she was born in Eresos, Lesbos. She was a contemporary of Alcaeus and Pittacus. She was born to an aristocratic family on the island of Lesbos during a great cultural blooming in the area. When the aristocracy of the island was driven into exile from Mytilene due to political unrest, Sappho fled to Sicily. Later, after the fall of tyranny, she returned to Lesbos and gathered around her young women from the aristocracy of the island and the cities of Asia Minor to teach them the arts of music and poetry, in the service of Aphrodite and the Muses. The philosopher Maximus of Tyre (2nd half of the 2nd century AD) describes her as small and dark-haired. She was considered to be homosexual, and that identification accompanies the poet to this day. In modern times, lesbian love has also been associated with her name. After her death, a coin was minted in Lesbos in her image, statues of her were erected in Syracuse and Pergamum, and a cenotaph was built in Syracuse in her memory. It is possible that many of her works were lost due to their not being copied, perhaps because of their low demand after the rise of Christianity and a more strict view of morality.

Links	<p>https://open.spotify.com/episode/3ntZxIRw5QMfS1PFBPkw7n?si=d6adc9ce4b02426f</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=glyzvEYnnKw&itct=CA8QpDAYACITCJO66-PEuNMFVZnTgodvTQJWzIGcmVsbWZ1SLPH1a7S56fb8wE%3D&client=mv-google&gl=US&hl=en</p>
--------------	---

Number	2	
City name	Athens	
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233	
Name of the point of interest	Manto Mavrogenous' Bust-Pedion tou Areos	
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.992839674575556, 23.735111257388976	
Images		

Description	<p>"Manto Mavrogenous' bust was made in 1937 and is located in Pedio tou Areos. It is one of the 21 busts that are dedicated to the Greek heroes of the Greek War of Independence (1821). Manto Mavrogenous (1796- 1840) was a Greek heroine of the Greek War of Independence (1821), that contributed her fortune for the Hellenic cause. She was born in Trieste by an aristocratic family, but her origin was from Mykonos, where she led the rebellion of the island's inhabitants against the Turks. With ships, two equipped with her own money, she pursued the pirates who were ravaging the Cyclades and then fought in Pelion, Fthiotida and Livadia. Manto Mavrogenous' financial support of the Struggle and her general activities, such as her letters to the philhellenic women of France and England, made her name legendary in European philhellenic circles. For her overall contribution to the War, she was honoured by Ioannis Kapodistrias with the rank of Lieutenant General. Later she was persecuted and exiled by the politician Ioannis Kolettis and eventually died penniless in Paros, as she had spent her entire fortune on the struggle.</p>
Links	<p>https://amorphypodbean.com/e/%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%B5%CF%85%CE%B8%CE%B5%CF%81%CE%AF%CE%B1%CE%B6%CE%AD%CE%B7220121%CE%B7-%CE%BC%CE%B1%CE%BD%CF%84%CF%8E%CE%BC%CE%B1%CF%85%CF%81%CE%BF/ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dpnovhWg5aQ</p>

Number	3
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Laskarina Bouboulina's Bust- Pedion tou Areos
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.992839674575556, 23.735111257388976
Images	
Description	<p>Bouboulina was born in Constantinople in 1771. Her father was Stavrianos Pinotsis, an Arvanite from Hydra and her mother was Skevo Kokkini, descendant of the Byzantine Kokkinis family. During her youth, she developed an interest in sailing which was facilitated by her stepfather's liberal attitude to education. She was widowed twice, inheriting a considerable sum of money from her second husband. She later allegedly</p>

	<p>joined the Filiki Etaireia secret society which sought to achieve Greek independence from the Ottoman Empire, being among the few women to do so. Following the outbreak of the Greek War of Independence she commanded a fleet of Spetsiot ships which contributed to several campaigns most notably the siege of Nafplion. Following the defeat of her faction in the Greek civil war in 1824, Bouboulina was briefly imprisoned and expelled to Spetses. She was killed on 22 May 1825, during the course of a family feud.</p>
Links	<p>https://youtu.be/qxrnAy4vg1w?feature=shared</p>

Number	4
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.983806067761044, 23.727538580803987
Name of the point of interest	Domna Visvizi' Bust- Pedion tou Areos
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.992839674575556, 23.735111257388976
Images	
Description	<p>Domna Visvizi (1783–1850) was a Greek maritime captain who fought in the Greek War of Independence. At the outbreak of the war, Visvizi joined her husband Chatzi Antonis Visvizi to fight for the Greek cause onboard the ship Kalomoira. After her husband was killed in battle in July 1822, Visvizi took command of the ship and continued to fight in the war. Among other contributions, Visvizi aided in the Greek capture of the island of Euboea. After running low on funds and being rejected additional funding by the Greek leadership, Visvizi gave over the Kalomoira to the Greek navy in 1824. After the war she was left destitute and with next to no government support lived in poverty until her death in 1850.</p>
Links	<p>https://youtu.be/P90EexjF5ko?feature=shared</p>

Number	5
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Katina Paxinos-Minotis Museum
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.98465732428314, 23.725765297908396
Images	
Description	<p>The Paxinou-Minotis Museum is a museum in Athens that is devoted to the Greek film and stage actress Katina Paxinou (1900-1973). Katina Paxinou was born in Pireaus and she was one of the founding members of the Greek National Theatre. She was the first Greek actress who managed to make it in Hollywood and even on her own terms, to excel in theatre and cinema in Europe and to stand out as a tragedienne of global importance. She was the first non-American actress that won an Academy Award for Best Actress for her performance in the film "For Whom the Bell Tolls".</p> <p>She played in numerous performances of the National Theatre of Greece. She died of cancer in 1973 and is justly considered as the greatest Greek actress of the 20th century. Her husband, the director Alexis Minotis, created a museum in her memory, that after his own death, was named Paxinos Minotis Museum. The Museum and Archive are housed in the Eynardos Mansion, 20 Agios Konstantinos St. and 52 Menandrou Street, in the centre of Athens.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.listenotes.com/podcasts/old-time-horror/44-04-06-the-woman-in-red-izO5WZwD2JB/</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BYM8jCot-yA</p>

Number	6
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Marble Plaque of Antigoni Krontira-Metaxa

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.984069, 23.753931
Images	
Description	This plaque was placed in honor of the educator Antigoni Metaxa - Kronitira or "Aunt Lena" after the naming of this green space. The choice of this particular area as "Aunt Lena's Garden" was made because there is a kindergarten in the same area, and it is adjacent to the "Elena Venizelos" Maternity Hospital. Antigoni Metaxa-Krontira (1905-1971) was an important Greek educator. She studied Educational Science in Paris, and acting at the Drama School of the Athens Conservatory. In 1933 she founded the first children's theatre for children in Greece. She was the author of 54 children's books, including the six volume children's encyclopedia and the Encyclopedia of Greek Mythology for children. She produced vinyl records of fairy tales and songs and the first children's television show. Her goal was to educate children by entertaining them. For all her work she was awarded by the Academy of Athens.
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3kN7ZardAlg

Number	7
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	National Gallery-Opi Zouni
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.975616859261244, 23.749431943596665

Images	
Description	<p>Greek National Gallery was built in 1900 in Athens. It hosts more than 15000 paintings. Opi Zouni's paintings are some of the few that belong to greek women artists. Opi Zouni (1941-2008) was an important Greek painter and artist born in Kairo, with origin from Crete and Santorini. She studied in Greece, in School of Fine Arts. Due to her gender, she could not present her work in Greece. She has held over 70 solo exhibitions in Europe and 450 participations in group exhibitions . She was a representative of geometric art in Greece. Her creations were influenced by Arabic culture but also incorporated Greek elements. Unfortunately, in our country her work wasn't recognized at her time because she was a woman. Today, a lot of her paintings can be found in Greek National Gallery in Athens.</p>
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F6tz2GprNvE

Number	8
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Experimental Special Primary School "Rosa Imvrioti"
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.966197378027225, 23.761450632683637
Images	
Description	<p>This Special Primary School is named by Roza Imvrioti. Roza Imvrioti (1898-1977) was a Greek educator, a pioneer of special education, with a rich social and political activity. She worked as a teacher of literature in middle schools and in 1934 she became the first female middle school principal. She founded the first Experimental Special Primary School in Athens (1937), the first official effort in Greece for the systematic education of children with</p>

	mental difficulties. Today, this school is still named by her name to pay tribute to her contribution and work in the field of special education and can be found in Kaisariani, Athens. She was an elected member of the Council of the International Women's Union. She was exiled and suffered tortures due to her political activity.
Links	n/a

Number	9
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Lela Karagianni's Bust
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.98830157804602, 23.73278742565169

Images	
---------------	--

Description	Lela Karagianni's bust in Exarcheia square was made in 1958, funded by the Association of Greek Women Scientists. Lela Karagianni (1898- 1944) was a legendary fighter of the National Resistance against the German troops in the period 1941- 1944. A protagonist of the «Secret War», although a mother of seven children, she was the first Greek citizen to offer organized resistance against the German enemy. She created the organization named “Bouboulina”, funded by herself. She was imprisoned (with her five children) and executed by the Germans troops. She became a renowned symbol of resistance worldwide. After her death, she was awarded the Award for Virtue and Self Sacrifice by the Academy of Athens and, in 2011, the honorary title of the Law of Nations by Yad Vashem, the Foundation for the Memory of Martyrs and Heroes, while in 2020 she was awarded the
--------------------	--

	honorary rank of Brigadier General. Today, there is a marble bust of her in Exarcheia square in Athens. Also, her house and base of her resistance movement in Plateia Amerikis is considered to be a historical monument that needs special protection.
Links	https://www.ert.gr/ert-arxeio/lela-karagianni-8-septemvriou-1944-2/

Number	10
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Kalliroi Parren's Bust
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.964203331126285, 23.735969295703672
Images	
Description	<p>On June 6, 1992, more than fifty years after her death, Callirroe Parren was honoured by the Hellenic Republic with the unveiling of her bust at the First Cemetery of Athens. Kalliroi Paren (1861-1940) is considered to be one of the first Greek feminists. She also claims the title of the first Greek woman journalist, editor and director of the newspaper "Efimeris ton Kirion". It was written exclusively by women and addressed mainly to women in Athens and Piraeus. This newspaper continued to be published for almost thirty years until 1918 when Callirroe was exiled to Hydra for her political beliefs. The aim of the newspaper was to introduce in Greece the feminist concerns that were already preoccupying women in Western European countries and to awaken the consciousness of the women of the time. She had had a rich social and political activity, represented Greece in a lot of international conferences and was exiled for the political views. Through her own action, Greek government allowed to women to be able to study in the University.</p>
Links	https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=531074417382400

Number	11
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Melina Mercouri's Bust-Plaka
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.96991240608659, 23.731442511040285
Images	
Description	<p>Melina Mercouri's bust was build in 1999 and is located in Plaka, Athens. Melina Mercouri (1895- 1967) is represented in the middle age. She was a charismatic personality and one of the most important Greek women of the 20th century. She was described as "the last Greek goddess" and a woman of flame. She was distinguished as an actress, by playing in theatrical plays and movies that won international awards. She also left her mark as a politician with her fight against the dictatorship, but also with her interventions at international level as Minister of Culture. She initiated the fight for the return of Parthenon Marbles back in Greece, a fight that still continues. Today, there is also a cultural foundation in her memorial that can be found in Polignotou 11, centre of Athens.</p>
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fY4wLf22tIU

Number	12
City name	Athens

Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Tzeni's Karezi Theatre
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.97691607282557, 23.7376275992176
Images	
Description	Tzeni Karezi's Theatre was build in 1978 by Tzeni Karezi and her husband (also an actor) Kostas Kazakos, in order to host their theatre company. Tzeni Karezi (1932- 1992) was an important Greek actress, with rich social and political activity. She came from a conservative family, that didn't allow her that job career. She went against her family wishes and she studied in the Drama School of National Theatre. She managed to be a protagonist in important plays in cinema and theatre. During the Greek Junta in 1967 -1974 was exiled for playing in a theatrical play with resistance messages. She was one of the most commercial and highest paid names in Greece. She died in 1992, due to cancer. In 1992 the foundation "Tzeni Karezi" was created, that offers palliative care for free in cancer patients.
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sqpyg2JAQg8 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iErJ4Lx83Fw&t=67s

Number	13
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98613041817146, 23.72384036218157
Name of the point of interest	Marina Galanou-Publishing Colourful Planet
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.99607435875703, 23.73074420738784

Images	
Description	<p>Marina Galanou had been President of the Greek Transgender Support Association, publisher of the publishing house and bookstore "Colourful Planet", and was with civil society organizations for more than 20 years. Founding member of the Transvestite - Transsexual Solidarity Association (SATTE) and General Secretary from 2003 to July 2014. General Secretary of the Greek Homosexual Community (G.H.C) from 2006 to 2008. Founding Member and President of the Greek Transgender Support Association (GTSA). She had been a Council of Europe Expert on sexual orientation and gender identity and participates in this capacity as a trainer in training seminars for Hellenic Police officers, asylum officers, magistrates, judges and prosecutors, as well as being a member of the legislative preparatory committee for legislation on legal recognition of gender identity. She is the author of two books, "Gender Identity and expression. Definitions, Stereotypes, Myths and Discriminations" and "I am trans - I know my rights", a columnist in print and electronic media, and has worked extensively in all areas of fundamental human rights and freedoms. Appointed by the National Commission on Human Rights as a full member of the National Council Against Racism and Intolerance in November 2019. Marina opened roads. he has been instrumental in trans visibility, helping many trans boys and girls break through fear and assert their place in society. She wrote books, took part in speeches, was a member of institutional bodies, such as the National Council against Racism and Intolerance, had been an expert of the Council of Europe on issues of sexual orientation and gender identity, but above all you could find her on the streets of the struggle for human rights and freedoms.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2WyLdXrekiQ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cZpeGT6FW48</p>

Number	14
City name	Athens
Latitude & Longitude of the City	37.98381281761063, 23.727537014594233
Name of the point of interest	Sofia Vembo' s grave-1st Cemetery of Athens

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	37.96475467826049, 23.73476000400491
Images	
Description	Efi Bembou, known professionally as Sofia Vembo, was a leading Greek singer and actress active from the interwar period to the early postwar years and the 1950s. She became best known for her performance of patriotic songs during the Greco-Italian War, when she was dubbed the "Songstress of Victory".
Links	https://www.boomplay.com/episode/3578820 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0aODluyQib4

2.5. Sofia, Bulgaria

In English

Number	1
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.6932471692578, 23.334871848217585

Images	
Description	<p>Educational Institution</p> <p>Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” is a public research university in Sofia, Bulgaria. It is the oldest institution of higher education in the country. The edifice of the university was constructed between 1924 and 1934 with the financial support of the brothers Evlogi Georgiev and Hristo Georgiev. Classes began modestly and without any noise on October 1, 1888. This is the birth date of the Bulgarian university – only 10 years after the Liberation. The university opened its gates with just eight professors, who, although few in number and almost all of them graduated abroad, still managed to bring to Sofia the spirit of higher education from different European countries. There were 43 students at first, only men. The first women were admitted after many years of petitions to the National Assembly, in 1901.</p>
Links	https://youtu.be/cO6pyL29JI4

Number	2
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	National Assembly of the Republic of Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69422398231894, 23.33264137696473

Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian government</p> <p>On January 15, 1938, Bulgarian women achieved the legal entitlement to cast their votes, marking the culmination of a protracted and intricate journey towards women’s suffrage within the nation. The initial step was taken in 1909 with the enactment of the Public Education Act, which afforded women the right to serve on school boards for the first time, although they were not allowed to participate in elections. This formal and limited concession failed to yield tangible results, as men predominantly continued to favor male candidates for trustee positions, barring women from the ballot box. In 1937, a partial victory was achieved when “women mothers of legal marriage” were granted the right to vote in local elections, although they remained ineligible for candidacy. Ultimately, on January 15, 1938, Bulgarian women gained the legal right to vote in parliamentary elections, albeit restricted to women over the age of 21 who were either married, divorced, or widowed. This restriction was overtly clear, excluding young, educated, single women, many of whom were pursuing studies abroad or established as intellectuals, from the electoral process. It wasn’t until 1944 that women in Bulgaria obtained equal suffrage, and in 1945, during the 26th National Assembly session, the first 16 women were elected as deputies.</p>
Links	https://viragoproject.eu/2021/12/06/885/

Number	3
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Elizaveta Karamihailova's Memorial plaque
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69337777307141, 23.337337950308346

Images	
Description	<p>Woman in science</p> <p>Elizaveta Karamihailova (1897-1968) was the first female nuclear physics in Bulgaria. She established the first practical courses of particle physics and became the first woman to hold a professorial title in the country. Elizaveta graduated as a PhD in Physics and Mathematics in Vienna and was appointed as a docent of Experimental Atomistics with Radioactivity at Sofia University in 1939. She founded the radioactivity laboratory at the Physics Institute of the Bulgarian Science Academy.</p>
Links	https://upb.phys.uni-sofia.bg/old/Karam.html

Number	4
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Konstantsa Lyapcheva's Home
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69217914742531, 23.336415270373237

Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian socialite Konstantsa Lyapcheva (1887-1944) was a socialite, involved in charity activities for unprivileged children (refugees, orphans, etc.). In the 1930s she was the first woman to actively engage with issues such as human trafficking, domestic violence, child protection. She was the chairwoman of the Union for the Protection of Children of Bulgaria until the very end. She was a member of almost all other charitable organizations of Sofia, in many of them as part of the management body. There is no area of social welfare in which she did not take part. Thanks to Konstanza, the activities of raising and educating children became the subject of law and received legislative protection, and motherhood was recognized as an extremely important social function. Upon her initiative, in 1927, June 1 was celebrated as Children's Day for the first time. She founded the first shelter homes for children in distress, for the training of social workers, summer camps and playgrounds.</p>
Links	n/a

Number	5
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Elena Markova-Bosilkova Home
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69085432371129, 23.329012373435987

Images		
Description	n/a	
Links	n/a	

Number	6	
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria	
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941	
Name of the point of interest	First Sofia State Girls High School (now, 7th Secondary School “Sveti Sedmochiselnitsi”) & Anastasia Golovina’s Workplace	
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69064928894992, 23.32836864324871	
Images		
Description	Woman in science 7 school “St. Sedmochiselnitsi” was founded in 1879 by a special decree of the Minister of Education, Marin Drinov, as the First Sofia State Girls’ High	

	<p>School. The history of girls' secondary education in Bulgaria began here. Girls, eager for knowledge, arrived from all over Bulgaria – Koprivshitsa, Kalofer, Stara Zagora, Prilep, Pirdop, Pleven, Varna, etc., which necessitated the opening of a boarding school. In 1882/1883, with the opening of a special pedagogical class, the high school reached its full development.</p> <p>Dr. Anastasia Golovina (1850 – 1933) worked in the First Girls' High School as a doctor. She was the first Bulgarian doctor who completed her education with a doctorate and the first Bulgarian female doctor. Hers were the innovations in Bulgaria related to the autopsy of the deceased to specify and confirm the cause of death. She is also the author of numerous scientific and popular science articles in the field of medicine, published in Bulgarian and foreign magazines. Throughout her life, Anastasia became the first Bulgarian psychiatrist and one of the founders of Bulgarian resort medicine and physiotherapy.</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>https://www.infinite-women.com/women/anastasia-golovina/</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>7</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Sofia, Bulgaria</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>42.698334, 23.319941</p>
<p>Name of the point of interest</p>	<p>Ekaterina Karavelova's Grave</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest</p>	<p>42.69014268422359, 23.326984834248545</p>
<p>Images</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>Bulgarian Feminist movement Ekaterina Karavelova (1860-1947) was a well-known educator, translator, writer, publicist, suffragist, and women's rights activist. She also had an active role in protecting Bulgaria's Jewish population from deportation to concentration camps in WWII. Ekaterina also became a long-term chairwoman of the Union of Bulgarian Women Writers, created on her</p>

	<p>initiative. She represented Bulgaria at the 4th Congress of the International Women’s League for Peace and Freedom in 1924 in Washington, USA. She was the founder of the cultural women’s organization Maika (Mother) and its chairperson in 1899-1929. Active as a teacher, Ekaterina was early on active in the debate of women’s education and status of female teachers.</p> <p><i>Continues at Ekaterina Karavelova’s Memorial Plaque</i></p>
Links	https://ekfwomen.org/en/about-us-en/about-ekaterina-karavelova/

Number	8
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Ekaterina Karavelova’s Memorial plaque
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.68988244467656, 23.32555789919287
Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian Feminist movement</p> <p><i>Continues from Ekaterina Karavelova’s Grave</i></p> <p>Furthermore, Ekaterina had a huge contribution to the development of the women’s movement in Bulgaria and the establishment of the role of women in society. She was one of the founders of the Bulgarian Women’s Union in 1901 and its chairwoman from 1915 to 1925. Convinced that women’s independence and equality require them to be able to earn a living, she strongly supported their vocational training. Karavelova led “Mother” to the establishment of the first business school for girls in Bulgaria “Maria Louisa”.</p>
Links	https://ekfwomen.org/en/about-us-en/about-ekaterina-karavelova/

Number	9
---------------	---

City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Elisaveta Bagryana's Memorial plaque
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.689819356155446, 23.32268257101826
Images	
Description	<p>Woman in arts</p> <p>Elisaveta Bagryana (1893–1991) was a prominent Bulgarian poet who lived in Sofia for much of her life. She is considered one of Bulgaria's most significant poets, often called "the first lady of Bulgarian women's literature". Elisaveta has been nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature three times and made substantial contributions to the country's literary heritage.</p>
Links	https://bnr.bg/en/post/100960112/125th-birth-anniversary-of-eternal-bulgarian-poetess-elisaveta-bagriana

Number	10
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Yana Yazova's Memorial plaque
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.690481782565946, 23.323648166299186

Images	
Description	<p>Woman in arts Yana Yazova (1912–1974) was a writer and intellectual from 20th century. Her poetry was translated into Esperanto, Czech, Serbian and Ukrainian. She travelled extensively in Europe and the Middle East and wrote about her travels as well. Her historical novel Alexander of Macedon, the trilogy Balkans and the anti-communist novel Salt Gulf were published after her death.</p>
Links	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yana_Yazova

Number	11
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Bulgarian Women’s Union building and Anna Karima’s workplace
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69102591326096, 23.324570846234295

Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian Feminist movement</p> <p>The Bulgarian Women’s Union was a women’s rights organisation active in Bulgaria from 1901 to 1944. In 1901, the organisation was founded by Vela Blagoeva, Ekaterina Karavelova, Anna Karima, Kina Konova, Julia Malinova, and Zheni Pateva. The organization was an umbrella organization of the 27 local women’s organisations that had been established in Bulgaria since 1878. It was founded as a reply to the limitations of women’s education and access to university studies in the 1890s.</p> <p>Anna Karima (1871-1949) was a writer, translator, editor and journalist, suffragist and women’s rights activist. In 1897 she founded the Women’s Educational Association called “Conscious” through which Anna, with her constant letters to the government, managed to convince them to allow women to study in university in 1901. Anna became the first Chairwoman of the Bulgarian Women’s Union and organized the first congress of feminist organizations. Throughout her life she’s constantly engaged in translating and writing own materials, all of them focused on feminine topics – from education of children, to opposing arranged marriages, to expressing freely one’s emotions – her works challenge the traditional understandings at the time, combat stereotypes and influence the attitudes of women.</p>
Links	https://kids.kiddle.co/Anna_Karima

Number	12
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Teodora Peykova's Workplace

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69314718885858, 23.323251199350366
Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian Feminist movement</p> <p>Teodora Peykova (1892-1972) was a writer, editor, and socialite, she founded the lady's magazine "Economy and household", which was published for 25 years. Through the magazine Teodora spread European taste and ideas throughout the country and used it to educate women about different social issues or inventions made by other women, to offer recipes and medical advice, weight-loss diets, press review, family advice, child-rearing advice, fashion, historical events, gymnastics, reports from Paris and other cities, advertisements, courses on sewing, embroideries, needlework, etc. She also became the first Bulgarian woman who taught herself how to drive her husband's car.</p>
Links	n/a

Number	13
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Mara Belcheva's Home
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69327335910196, 23.321191262751057

Images	
Description	<p>Woman in arts</p> <p>Mara Belcheva (1868-1937) was a poet, teacher, translator, and philologist. She published three collections of poetry: “Footsteps on the Threshold”, 1918, “Sonnets”, 1926, and “Selected Songs”, 1931. Mara published a biography of her late partner, poet Pencho Slaveykov, in 1925. She also translated Friedrich Nietzsche’s Thus Spoke Zarathustra and Gerhart Hauptmann’s Die versunkene Glocke into Bulgarian.</p>
Links	https://bibliophilia.eu/strihi-ot-portreta-na-mara-belcheva

Number	14
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Dimitrana Ivanova’s Home
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.68847163681135, 23.316939282276874

Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian Feminist movement</p> <p>Dimitrana Ivanova (1881–1960) was a Bulgarian educational reformer, suffragist and women’s rights activist. She chaired the Bulgarian Women’s Union from 1926 to 1944. From 1928, she published and edited the monthly magazine “The Woman” (1929 – 1931), in which she examined the legal aspects of the subordinate status of women. Dimitrana collaborated with many newspapers on issues of women’s life and future. Throughout her life she fights for gender equality in the field of education, as well as the right of women lawyers to exercise their profession as lawyers and judges. After a long struggle, she became one of the first Bulgarian women to have this right recognized.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/09612020400200384?needAccess=true</p> <p>https://v16-web-newkey.tiktokcdn.com/92a8c86e425af343be51b203aa90b530/672a5ec8/video/tos/maliva/tos-maliva-ve-0068c799-us/1e2ac8e166964eafbc031735f15e359d/?a=1988&bti=NDU3ZiAwOg%3D%3D&ch=0&cr=3&dr=0&lr=tiktok_m&cd=0%7C0%7C1%7C&cv=1&br=1568&bt=784&cs=0&ds=3&ft=piJEeMXj8Zmo0lgACb4jVO5ZrpWrKsd.&mime_type=video_mp4&qs=0&rc=ZWY5ODgzZjVmMzo4OTQ1ZEBpajk2amQ6ZmhwOzMzZzcNEBjYDVfXjZgNjlxYzZfYi9jYSNpZm5zciRnbmJgLS1kMS9zcv%3D%3D&vvpI=1&l=20241105120550CDEAD99AE5E22A170676&btag=e00090000</p>

Number	15
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Baba Nedelya street

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.684386429113246, 23.31719677419451
Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian Educator Nedelya Petkova (1826-1894) was a Bulgarian education pioneer. In 1859 she began teaching girls and developed this into a school system for girls across the Bulgarian part of the Ottoman Empire, with hundreds of girls attending classes.</p>
Links	https://www.infinite-women.com/women/nedelya-petkova/

Number	16
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Elisaveta Konsulova-Vazova's Workplace
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.686058399813305, 23.326745438299394

Images	
Description	<p>Woman in arts</p> <p>Elisaveta Konsulova-Vazova (1881-1965) – one of the first women professional artists in Bulgaria, the first Bulgarian woman to paint a nude figure at the State School of Painting and the first woman to host a solo exhibition. Elisaveta describes her revolutionary feminist ideas regarding child-rearing in a book about education – “Book for young mothers”. She is one of the founders of the Puppet Theater and the first editor-in-chief of the magazine “Home and World”.</p>
Links	<p>https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elisaveta_Konsulova-Vazova https://youtu.be/9jIYAGdfb9M</p>

Number	17
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Dora Gabe’s Memorial plaque
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.687320234715166, 23.328290390748876

Images	
Description	<p>Woman in arts</p> <p>Dora Petrova Gabe (1888 –1983) was a Bulgarian Jewish poet, writer and translator. She published poetry for adults and children as well as travel books, short stories and essays. In her later years, she also did extensive work in translation. Furthermore, she is remembered not only as a writer but was also an activist, fighting for peace and children’s rights. She was appointed as honorary diplomat for the Peace Council and received the Golden Cross for her work around Bulgarian-Polish relations. Furthermore, she became an ‘Honorary Citizen of Tolbukhin’, today Dobrich, a city in her home region.</p>
Links	https://www.europeana.eu/en/exhibitions/pioneers/dora-gabe

Number	18
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Kalina Malina’s Home
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69023812978044, 23.338847565439398

Images	
Description	Woman in arts Kalina Malina (1898–1979) was a Bulgarian children’s writer and translator, the author of about 50 children’s books, as well as the first Bulgarian children’s novel, Zlatno sartse (1930), and two more novels.
Links	n/a

Number	19
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Gallery “Vaska Emanuilova”
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.69826557706231, 23.3417443512561
Images	
Description	Woman in arts Gallery “Vaska Emanuilova” is one of the very few institutions, along with house-museum “V. Nedkova” and HG “El. Karamihailova” – Shumen, named after a woman and showing an exhibition related to the history of women.

Links	https://veg.sghg.bg/en/history/
Number	20
City name	Sofia, Bulgaria
Latitude & Longitude of the City	42.698334, 23.319941
Name of the point of interest	Rayna Knyaginya's Home
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	42.70783831462244, 23.316631296679372
Images	
Description	<p>Bulgarian Revolutionary</p> <p>Rayna Popgeorgieva Futekova, better known as Rayna Knyaginya, aka "Queen of the Bulgarians" (1856–1917) was a Bulgarian teacher, midwife, and revolutionary born in Panagyurishte who is famous for having sewn the flag of the April Uprising of 1876.</p>
Links	https://bnr.bg/en/post/101406093/bulgaria-marks-165-years-since-birth-of-bulgarian-revival-period-heroine-rayna-knyaginya

2.6. Velenje, Slovenia

In English

Number	1
City name	Ljubljana
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.049805245434015; 14.496852953102419
Name of the point of interest	Academy of Fine Arts

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.049805245434015; 14.496852953102419
Images	
Description	<p>(1926-2017): She is a Slovenian painter and illustrator, born in Ljubljana. She is best known for her illustrations for children's books, many of which have become classics of Slovenian children's literature. She graduated from the Academy of Fine Arts in Ljubljana, where she also completed a specialisation in graphic design. She has devoted her entire creative life to children's illustration.</p> <p>Her outstanding oeuvre includes over 200 book projects and more than 2,200,000 copies of individual books in various editions. Her picture books are produced and reprinted for new generations of readers in this country and all over the world. She has been working with Mladinska knjiga since 1964.</p> <p>Her artistic career began with the illustration of Dragotin Kette's fairy tale Šivilja in škarjice / The Seamstress and the Scissors. She has also illustrated books by Josip Ribičič (Miškolin, Nana, the Little Monkey), Kajetan Kovič (My Friend Piki Jakob, Muri the Cat, Pajacek and the Doll, Direndaj the Dragon, The Golden Ship), Svetlana Makarovič (The Terrible Wolf), Leopold Suhodolčan (The Little Cepecepetavček), Miha Mate (The Toy School), Srečko Kosovel (The Sweet Little Bears), Prežihov Voranec (Levi Devžej), Janez Bitenec (The Three Kittens), Polonce Kovač (The Little Mouse), the collection of fairy tales The Golden Bird and others. Her artwork also enriches the magazines Cicido and Ciciban. Part of her rich oeuvre is collected in the anthologies The Miracle Garden and Rasla je Jelka.</p>
Links	link link

Number	2
City name	Ljubljana
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.0569465; 14.5057515
Name of the point of interest	Memorial plaque Zofke Kveder
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.05558729086709; 14.509416258747628

Images	
Description	<p>(1878-1926): She was a writer and feminist, born in Ljubljana. She was a pioneer of Slovenian feminist literature, known for her novels, short stories and essays. She was born on 22 April 1878 in Ljubljana to her father Janez and her mother Neža, née Legat. Shortly after her daughter's birth, the family moved several times. In 1884 she began attending the folk school in Bloki. She continued her education at the Lichtenturn Institute in Ljubljana and finished it with good results in 1893 at the Ursuline School in Ljubljana. In December 1896, she got her first job as a clerk in Kočevje. In 1897 she moved to Ljubljana, where she copied various documents in the office of the lawyer Ivan Šušteršič. In her work and writing she focused on themes touching on women's lives. Her first articles on the position of women in society were published in the magazine Slovenka (Slovene newspaper), and later in Slovene Nation, Edinosta and Jugoslovanska Žena. Here she often published articles (For our wives, who take care of their own subsistence, Our hyperidealism, What we want, Woman in the family and society, About today's woman...) on women's rights to work, voting and education. She has advocated for an emancipated woman, a creator and an educated woman. She stressed that emancipated women are not the enemy of men and should not be feared by them. She wanted to prove that an emancipated woman could also be a wife and mother.</p>
Links	link link link

Number	3
City name	Čadram
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.389277; 15.4590732
Name of the point of interest	Primary school Anice Černejeve Makole
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.31807780085802; 15.66837887443098

Images	
Description	<p>Anica Černež was a Slovenian teacher, writer and poet, born on 3 April 1900 in Čadram. Anica Černež was born into a family of teachers. Her father, Ljudevit Černež, was first a teacher, later a school superintendent and also a poet and writer. Her mother was a teacher, Marija Hasenbüchl. Like her father, Anica was also a teacher and a speaker. She went to school at the age of five (1905) in Griže near Celje. After four years (1909) she went to Maribor to a private school for school sisters (today the Congregation of the School Sisters of St. Francis of Christ the King). She taught in Griže and then in Celje. In 1927 she qualified to teach mathematics, physics and chemistry by passing her diploma examination in Zagreb.</p>
Links	link

Number	4
City name	Velenje
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.36214834804165; 15.110638665269247
Name of the point of interest	Rod Jezerski zmaj
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.35707708725387; 15.116202826670017
Images	
Description	<p>(1940-2022) Herma has been very active in shaping the local community throughout her life. She was a teacher who loved to be involved in many activities, but she had a special love for scouting and her contribution in this field was really great. It is Herma Groznik who deserves most of the credit for</p>

	the final consolidation of the clan in Velenje, because with her pedagogical knowledge and the trust placed in her by her parents, the school managements, and also strong political support, she finally consolidated Scouting in Velenje. Organisationally, the model developed in her school became a model to such an extent that it was imitated in all other primary schools. In 2005, Hermina Groznik received a high municipal award the coat of arms of the Municipality of Velenje for her significant contribution to the local community.
Links	link

Number	5
City name	Šoštanj
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.3782836; 15.0461378
Name of the point of interest	Municipality Šoštanj
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.377297876286725; 15.045031331933407
Images	
Description	(1873-1950): Antonija Sternad, maiden name Acman, was born on 23 April 1873 to Gregor Acman and Lucia Acman. She was a famous midwife, the first in Šoštanj with a degree in midwifery. Antonija Sternad graduated from the midwifery school in Ljubljana on 29 July 1905, after completing a six-month course in midwifery organised by the Imperial-King's Foundation for the Education of Midwives. She helped 3000-4000 babies into the world in homes in Šoštanj and the surrounding area. Among others, Karel Destovnik Kajuh. Antonija Sternad is remembered as a very prominent citizen. According to stories, she was "half a doctor", as she also helped in the treatment of other illnesses. Antonija Sternad and her family lived in Šoštanj at house number 13, later at 1 Levstikova cesta.
Links	n/a

Number	6
City name	Velenje

Latitude & Longitude of the City	46362274; 15.110658
Name of the point of interest	Miners statue
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.35951226478748; 15.115427343522725
Images	
Description	<p>Fictional role: This fictional miner's wife represents the unwavering strength and resilience of the women who supported their families in the mining communities of Velenje. She symbolizes the backbone of these communities, standing as a testament to the enduring spirit of those who managed households and cared for their families while their husbands worked in the demanding and often perilous coal mines. This character embodies the sacrifices, hard work, and the vital role these women played in maintaining the well-being of their families and the cohesion of the mining community, making her a fitting symbol of dedication and fortitude.</p>
Links	n/a

Number	7
City name	Celje
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.23092; 15.26044
Name of the point of interest	Alma Karlin statue
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.22855811819493; 15.266471184355392
Images	

Description	<p>(1889-1950): She was a Slovenian writer, traveller and polyglot, born in Celje. She travelled extensively around the world and wrote several books about her experiences, including "Globetrotting Through Siberia and Central Asia" and "In the Land of Silent". She finished high school in Graz, from where she went to London in 1909 to study languages. She studied English, French, Latin, Italian, Norwegian, Danish, Russian and Spanish. At the beginning of the First World War, in 1914, she had to flee to Sweden and Norway because, as an Austro-Hungarian citizen, she was unwelcome in London. In 1918, she returned to Celje, where she founded a school for foreign languages, and her decision to travel around the world was ripe. She used her savings to buy her first typewriter, the famous Erika, which followed her for the rest of her life. She prepared for her journey by practising her painting skills and taking additional lessons in geography, history, natural history, botany and zoology.</p>
Links	<p>link link</p>

Number	8	
City name	Ribnica	
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.73072079669432; 14.71866261600676	
Name of the point of interest	Birth house of Franja Bojc Bidovec	
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.721893946343215; 14.741965093830284	
Images		
Description	<p>(1913-1944): She was a Slovenian nurse, born in Nemški vas near Ribnica. She attended primary school in Ribnica 1920-25, also one grade of bourgeois school 1925-26, then enrolled at the Municipal Women's Real Gymnasium in Ljubljana, from which she graduated in 1933. In Ljubljana, she lived in modest conditions in the boarding house of the Society of the Sisters of Mercy in the St. Joseph's Shelter, where she also supported herself by giving lessons. She attended the incomplete Faculty of Medicine in Ljubljana from 1933-39, then continued her studies in Belgrade and Zagreb, where she was graduated in</p>	

	1939. During the Second World War she worked in a secret hospital in the mountains near Celje. She helped to treat wounded partisan fighters and saved many lives, despite the constant danger of being discovered and captured by the occupiers. From January 1944 to May 1945, she was the administrator, doctor and surgeon of the Slovenian Partisan War Hospital, already named after her during the war, in the inaccessible Pasice gorge near Cerknjo.
Links	link

Number	9
City name	Ljubljana
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46°18'14.3"N 14°16'29.5"E
Name of the point of interest	Ivana Kobilca statue in front of St. James Parish Church
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.30395717447477; 14.274867985556378

Images	
Description	Ivana Kobilca is the most important Slovenian painter and was born on 20 December 1861 in Ljubljana. She studied drawing with Ida Künl in Ljubljana, and privately she also studied French and Italian. At the age of 16, she visited Vienna with her father, who was so taken with her that she decided to become a painter. After a few years (1879), she actually returned to Vienna, where she copied paintings by the old masters in the gallery of the Vienna Academy. From 1881 to 1891, she honed her skills in Munich, where she entered the School of Arts and Crafts. Her works were first exhibited in Vienna in 1888. A year later, she exhibited 30 of her paintings at a large retrospective exhibition on Vega Street in Ljubljana. The exhibition was seen by 695 people, a

	<p>remarkable number for those times, while none of her paintings were sold. A great success for Kobilka was when two of her paintings, <i>Liquorice</i> and <i>Summer</i>, were shown at an international exhibition in Paris. 2800 paintings by various artists were submitted for selection, but only 200 were chosen, including these two works by Kobilka. This feat paved the way for Kobilka to enter the international market. <i>Summer</i>, her most popular work, was painted in 1889 and 1890. In the painting, we can see a girl and her children weeding a flower tendril in the garden in summer. In this painting, Kobilka is actually depicting her younger sister Fani, while the children next to her are her cousin Johnny the Lightning and her cousin Katrica the Lightning.</p>
Links	link

Number	10
City name	Celje
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.23092; 15.26044
Name of the point of interest	Celje castle
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.21964598251005; 15.272040170341016
Images	
Description	<p>Barbara of Celje was born around 1392, presumably in Celje. Barbara was the youngest of six children of Count Herman II of Celje and Countess Anna of Schaunberg (d. 1396). She was brought up at the court in Celje together with her (little) cousin Anna, who married King Władysław II of Poland in 1402. Jagiel. Barbara was given an important role in her father's dynastic plans at an early age when, after the Battle of Nikopol (1396), opportunities opened up for the Celje family within the Hungarian kingdom. Herman betrothed her to the twenty-four years older King Sigismund of Hungary in 1401, they married in Krapina in November 1405, and she was crowned Queen of Hungary in Székesfehérvár on 6 December.</p>
Links	link link

Number	11
City name	Trebnje
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.9081708; 15.0125985
Name of the point of interest	Municipality Trebnje
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.9081708; 15.0125985
Images	
Description	<p>Minka Govekar (born Minka Vasič) was a Slovenian translator, activist and publicist, born on 28 October 1874 in Trebnje. She got on well with her parents. She was educated in Ljubljana, in a bourgeois school run by the Ursulines. There, she gained most of her knowledge through reading, and her writings were brilliant. She decided to become a teacher, as this was almost the only way for women to get an education at that time. In 1901 she was among the founders of the first Slovenian women's association, called the General Slovenian Women's Association. She served as secretary of the society for 27 years. The Society's main task was to strive for women's equality in all areas (access to education, the right to vote). To this end, they organised rallies and wrote petitions. It supported the "modernisation of motherhood", where a woman would be an educated mother and equal to her husband. She also travelled extensively as part of her activist efforts, mainly to Austrian, Croatian and Serbian countries, but she was most fond of working with Czech women.</p>
Links	link

Number	12
City name	Divača
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.68472; 13.97028
Name of the point of interest	Ida Kravanja (Ita Rina) statue in front of the Museum of Slovenian Film Actors
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.68414098267163; 13.971187996386641

Images	
Description	<p>Ida Kravanja was one of the few Slovenian actresses who managed to make a name for themselves abroad. Under the artistic name Ita Rina, she succeeded in the European and world film world. She was born on 7 July 1907 in Divača in the Karst region. Her father Jožef Kravanja was from Bovec, and her mother Marija née Marka was from Log pod Mangrtom. His father worked on the railway, as did many inhabitants of Divača, which was an important railway crossing on the route of the Southern Railway. At the outbreak of the First World War, the family moved to Ljubljana. Knowing how passionate she was about dance and acting, her father gave her the book Children's Stage for her eighth birthday, and she was completely taken by it. Reading it gave her the idea to have her own theatre and she invited her peers, who were her playmates, to join her.</p> <p>In Berlin, she got a part in a youth film with the - ironically for her situation - ironic title What Children Tell Their Parents. Soon after entering the film industry, she was suggested to change her name, as Ida Kravanja was a difficult name to pronounce abroad. She settled for the name Ita Rina. Her first film was a great stepping stone for her. Film critics wrote glowing things about her, and she was nicknamed the Yugoslav Queen of Beauty.</p> <p>She also starred in the film Erotikon, which brought her worldwide fame. Suddenly, everyone was talking about her. She became a star and offers for film roles came in like wildfire. The good word about her even spread to America. Among other things, she received an offer from Hollywood, but turned it down.</p>
Links	link

Number	13
City name	Velenje
Latitude & Longitude of the City	46.36214834804165; 15.110638665269247
Name of the point of interest	Health Center Velenje
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	46.36157781086836; 15.116761203998442

Images	
Description	<p>Urša Stropnik Šonc was born in Slovenj Gradec in 1973. She graduated from secondary school (natural sciences and mathematics) in Velenje and graduated in fine arts (book illustration) at the Faculty of Arts in Maribor. Since 1998 she has been working as an independent cultural artist. Her first book illustration (a picture book by Rok Poles, About Three Bats) was published in 1997. In her twenty-year career, she has illustrated more than 80 books, participated in 20 solo and 10 group exhibitions, and has taken part in the Slovenian Biennial of Illustration three times.</p> <p>She collaborates with many publishing houses, e.g. Obzorja, Pivec, DZS, Didakta, Izolit, Aristej, Hieroglif, etc., and magazines such as Zmajček, Cicizabavnik, Trobentica, Dodo, BIM-BAM and others. Her contribution enriched the children's colouring books by Kristina Stropnik, which are among the best quality examples of this genre. In the framework of cooperation with museum institutions, she illustrated a guide to the museum collection of the Maribor Regional Museum for children (Tigi the Castle Kitten: A Walk Through the Maribor Regional Museum for Young Visitors, 2001) and illustrated thematic sections of the permanent installation at the Faces of Ljubljana exhibition at the Ljubljana City Museum (2003-2004).</p> <p>Her paintings adorn the paediatric wards of the Velenje Health Centre and the General Hospital of Franca Derganec in Šempeter pri Novi Gorici. She has designed wooden puzzles and toys (e.g. Animal Garden, 2010), she is the author of the art templates for the puppet show Dr. Eko performed by the FRU-FRU theatre (2010). She also works as an art pedagogue, she taught at the Nazarje Primary School in 1998, and now she teaches subjects in the field of art and design at the People's University in Velenje.</p>
Links	n/a

2.7. Vilnius, Lithuania

In English	
Number	1
City name	Vilnius

Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Adelė Dirsyte (1909-1955)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.688055, 25.270555
Images	<p>Photo Source: Wikipedia</p>
Description	<p>Adele was much like many other women who helped to shape Lithuania's first Republic. She worked in various youth and women's organizations, wrote articles, poetry, and organized seminars. Adele also taught German at a girls' school until her arrest by KGB in 1946 for "contra-revolutionary" activities. Despite enduring eight months of torture in a secret KGB prison, her spirit remained unbroken. Even in Siberian gulags she continued teaching and supporting other women, emphasizing forgiveness over revenge. This message was captured in a small prayer book called "Mary, Save Us,". Translated into more than nine languages and distributed in hundreds of thousands of copies, it remains one of the most widely published Lithuanian books to this day.</p>
Links	<p>https://youtu.be/eE7tfcnejGc?t=368</p> <p>06:08-07:48 watch video in this time frame</p>

Number	2
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E

Name of the point of interest	Memorial plates to remember Chaya and Leya Schemiavitz (1931-1943)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.690200, 25.273032
Images	<p>Photo Author: Ieva B.</p>
Description	Lea Schemiavitz, known as Lili to her family, was just 10 years old when she was imprisoned in the Vilnius ghetto. What might she have grown up to be? Perhaps a teacher, a businesswoman, an artist, or a prime minister? Sadly, we will never know, as she perished near Bezdonys. All that's left are this stone and her brother's memories.
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rH3U1U8wwd8&ab_channel=WorldJewishCongress

Number	3
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Žemaitė Julija Beniuševičiūtė-Žymantienė (1845-1921)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.688395, 25.274139

Images	<p>Photo source: National Museum of Lithuania, Epaveldas.lt</p>
Description	<p>Don't judge her by her serious look. Julija, also known as Žemaitė, was a free spirit who didn't care about societal norms and loved to dance. She started writing stories at 50, becoming a key figure in Lithuania's culture and politics, particularly advocating for the rights of peasant women. Julija also participated in the first Lithuanian Women's Congress in 1907, where she addressed the challenges faced by underprivileged women. Fun fact: Žemaitė is the only woman ever featured on Litas banknotes, though they were replaced by coins just four years later.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zEYhb0rMY04&ab_channel=GRA%C5%BDIIRTAGALINGA</p>

Number	4
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Marija and Meilė
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.685360, 25.277968

<p>Images</p>	<p style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">20. Vilnius. Su Meile Lukšiene</p> <p>Photo Source: Algirdas Tarvydas XX a. Palanga resort museum</p>
<p>Description</p>	<p>Two little girls used to live in this building. One of them is mentioned on this memorial plaque. Despite the turmoil of World War II, Marija Gimbutienė managed to become a world-famous archaeologist and anthropologist. She made a groundbreaking discovery, revealing that 5000 years ago, Old European communities were woman-centered, practicing peace and equality. This new view of European history inspired countless scientists and feminist artists. Her cousin Meilė Lukšienė (1913-2009) on the other hand shaped your life - she played an important role in changing the school education system in Lithuania just after independence!</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>https://youtu.be/BjE2-H1R9Zs?t=1905</p> <p>00:31:45-00:32:28 watch video in this time frame</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>5</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Vilnius</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>54.6872° N, 25.2797° E</p>
<p>Name of the point of interest</p>	<p>Beatričė Grincevičiūtė (1911-1988)</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest</p>	<p>54.689745466430296, 25.27751401690186</p>

Images	<p>Photo source: B. Grincevičiūtė memorial apartment-museum Beatričės House</p>
Description	<p>In the early 20th century in Lithuania, people with disabilities were often seen as a burden or as dependent on society. It didn't matter if they had talent, worked hard or wanted to contribute. This is why Beatričė didn't like being called a "blind singer." However, that's exactly how she was introduced before her first concert. Still, her talent shone brightly - she became one of the most famous sopranos in Lithuanian opera and recorded over 1300 songs. Now, you're in front of her apartment turned museum. Here, you can discover not just her music but also the Braille language.</p>
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ko13T98-6iM

Number	6
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Felicija Bortkevičienė
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.687399, 25.279125

Images	
Description	<p>Photo source: Maironis Lithuanian Literature Museum</p> <p>This plaque tells us that the Lithuanian council used to operate in this building. Felicija Bortkevičienė served here as a senior secretary, but her role extended far beyond that. If we had to list all the political, cultural, and charitable organizations where she energetically organized or managed, we'd be here for quite a while. Surprisingly, she never held any official political positions. Once, there was a consideration for her to become the Minister of Provision and Public Work, but some government members had reservations about a woman holding this position, so she wasn't chosen. Later, Felicija was nominated for the presidency of Lithuania but received only one vote.</p>
Links	<p>https://youtu.be/hEOnvmvmDm0?t=727</p> <p>00:12:06-00:13:41 watch video in this time frame</p>

Number	7
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Elzė Ožeškienė (1841-1910)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.687370, 25.280512

<p>Images</p>	<p>Photo source: National Library of Poland</p>
<p>Description</p>	<p>Back when Vilnius was called Wilno, this square was named after a famous Polish writer, Eliza Orzeszkowa. She lived in the city for a while and ran a successful publishing business until the Russian authorities shut it down. In her writing, you can find many topics related to feminism, like women's education, independence, marriage, work, and the struggles of illegitimate children. In 1905, she was nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature but was later overlooked in favor of another male writer.</p>
<p>Links</p>	<p>https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/lt/maps/compare/review/24a805fe-528c-4165-9d6a-d0dfd54adab9?x=582437.7283417915&y=6062246.456419289&zoom=15&fbclid=IwAR1JrN4550e-rdlbnPuQ2rvrr69k0emmgHQG4e_66EqZiMGknlXb2AC6tUY</p> <p>An interactive map link</p>

<p>Number</p>	<p>8</p>
<p>City name</p>	<p>Vilnius</p>
<p>Latitude & Longitude of the City</p>	<p>54.6872° N, 25.2797° E</p>

Name of the point of interest	Veronika and Julija
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.685163, 25.279235
Images	<p>Photo by Ieva B.</p>
Description	<p>This building used to be a hospital founded by one of Lithuania's first female doctors, Veronika Janulaitytė - Alseikiene (1883–1971). Her sister, Dr. Julija Janulaitytė - Matjošaitiene (1880–1978), also worked here. Despite coming from a poor family, both sisters became doctors and did a lot of charity and cultural work outside their medical practice. They also raised their daughters, Marija and Meilė, who became influential scholars.</p>
Links	<p>https://youtu.be/BjE2-H1R9Zs?t=1949</p> <p>00:32:28-00:33:55 watch video in this time frame</p>

Number	9
City name	Vilnius

Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Marcelė Kubiliūtė
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.685003, 25.279964
Images	<p>Photo source: National Museum of Lithuania</p>
Description	<p>Did you know that the first secret service squad in Lithuania was composed entirely of women? The most courageous and determined among them was Marcelė. Some say that she held the entire safety of the young Lithuanian nation in her hands! In 1919, she played a crucial role in uncovering a secret plot to overthrow the Lithuanian government based in Kaunas at that time. The Polish secret service, annoyed by her interference, even put a 5000 zloty bounty on her, and she became known as the "woman with a fox." Can you guess why? Till this day she is the only Lithuanian woman awarded all major Lithuanian orders.</p>
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ProKlZ8hzQA&ab_channel=Lietuvosnacionalinisradijasirtelevizija

Number	10
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Aleksandra Jurašaitytė - Vailokaitienė (1895-1957)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.6866789161342, 25.282033865153302

Images	<p>Photo source: photo by Aleksandra Jurašaitytė-Vailokaitienė, Lithuanian National Museum</p>
Description	<p>Look up, can you see those huge windows on the top floor of Gedimino Avenue 12? There used to be a photo studio there. And you know the most famous photo taken there. You've seen it hundreds of times by now. But have you ever wondered who was behind the camera? Her name was Aleksandra, and she, along with her mother, took over her father's photo studio after his passing in 1915. She also traveled extensively, documenting the lives of Lithuanian peasants, orphans, famous politicians, and more.</p>
Links	<p>https://youtu.be/l8257Rdwo-w?t=562</p> <p>00:09:22-00:11:33 watch video in this time frame</p>

Number	11
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	Jadvyga Chodakauskaitė - Tūbelienė (1891 - 1988)
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.68658437335695, 25.28588552790082

Images	<p>Photo source: archive photo of the Historical Presidential Palace in Kaunas</p>
Description	<p>For a while a young woman lived in this house. She became one of the most influential women in Lithuania between the two World Wars, and not just because she was married to the longest-serving Prime Minister. Jadvyga played a key role in founding the Lithuanian Women's Council. She was also a writer, journalist, and diplomat. Did you know she's the reason the Act of Independence of Lithuania became known worldwide? Jadvyga translated the Act into German and discreetly handed it to her friend, the editor of a significant newspaper. He took it to Berlin the next day and published it for the world to see!</p>
Links	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y7u7Jtjy1C4&ab_channel=LietuvosRespublika</p>

Number	12
City name	Vilnius
Latitude & Longitude of the City	54.6872° N, 25.2797° E
Name of the point of interest	The House of Signatories
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	54.682333090520515, 25.28929911457452

Images	
Description	<p>Photo source: National Museum of Lithuania</p> <p>Every year on February 16, we hold annual ceremonies to commemorate our independence at the House of the Signatories. Leaders of the country give speeches from the balcony, and hundreds of people fill the streets with flags, braving the cold February weather to celebrate freedom and independence. But who was this freedom for? At that time, hardly any country in the world recognized women as equal members of society with the right to vote or run for office. Lithuanian women were not satisfied with this. They raised their voices and won these rights. Today, they continue to raise their voices to gain more recognition for their historical contributions, one exhibition at a time...</p>
Links	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5x7CyH8Nexo&t=144s&ab_channel=Lietuvosnacionalinisradijasirtelevizija</p>

2.8. Lecco, Italy

In English

Number	1
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	PAOLA COLOMBO. COMUNE DI MONTE MARENZO; Piazza Municipale, 5, 23804 Monte Marenzo LC;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.77117277647121, 9.454672606595363

Images	
Description	<p>PAOLA COLOMBO. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Paola is mayor of the town where she lives, Monte Marengo, where she has been serving the community for about 9 years. She enjoys gaining new experiences; at the age of 16 she spent some time studying abroad, in the United States. She likes dealing with people, building something new, she gets excited about ideas where she counts. She believes in the importance of travel, experiences and studies. She has many ideas, but she also likes to observe the ideas of others and see what can be useful in her own area. It is important for her to have people she trusts to advise her, but when she is convinced of what she believes in, she goes all the way. What does she suggest to young women? To be determined, to never stop but, at the same time, not to be in a hurry; to know how to seize opportunities, to try because you can go back and, if you don't succeed, it's not a failure, but "you can always start again from there".</p>
Links	

Number	2
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	STUDENTS ISTITUTO D'ISTRUZIONE SUPERIORE LORENZO ROTA; Via Lavello, 17, 23801 Calolziocorte LC;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.79360578710849, 9.432719593829129

Images	
Description	<p>BOYS and GIRLS from the Lorenzo Rota Higher Education Institute. Active protagonists of HerStory, they shared reflections, ideas, knowledge, desires, aspirations with respect to the topic of gender. They recognise the value of practical example, of their adult role models, of a story that looks not only to the past but also and above all to the present; a story that is capable of leaving imprints today for the future. Directly involved in project activities, they will be the drivers of a new focus on the topic.</p>
Links	

Number	3
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	ALESSANDRA MAGGI L'ISOLA DELLA STUPIDERA: Via Ca' Romano, 23854 Olginate LC;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.780432166469474, 9.426251366845603
Images	
Description	<p>ALESSANDRA MAGGI. Stakeholder of HerStory, woman of Lecco present. Alessandra describes herself as a teacher by choice. After graduating in Primary Education, she obtained a Master's degree in Clinical Pedagogy. She is the president of "L'isola della Stupidera", a social promotion association that takes care of meeting and entertainment spaces for families. It is a reality born</p>

	<p>from her desire to create a “time within my happy everyday life” that was always thought out and made to measure. She likes to be inside contexts, to observe and understand what is needed without too many methods and structures. She believes in the importance of having more male figures at school, to give children the opportunity to recognise their own gender and the opposite. What does she suggest to young women? To do what they like and involve others; generate something that makes them feel good; recognise their need and make it everyone's need.</p>
Links	

Number	4
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	MARINA CALEGARI. COMUNE DI OLGINATE; Piazza Volontari del Sangue, 1, 23854 Olginate LC;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.79928734702603, 9.412264871605338
Images	
Description	<p>MARINA CALEGARI. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Marina is an architect, interested in the world of construction since she was a child. She is also a sports enthusiast and has practised skiing and water skiing at a competitive level, travelling extensively. She studied architecture at the Milan Polytechnic. In recent years, she has also dedicated herself to the political life of her town, Olginate, as municipal councillor, and as vice-mayor. She is currently councillor for social, sport and youth policies and councillor in the “Comunità Montana”. She has worked as a volunteer in the Lions Club and is currently on the board of “Impresa sociale Girasole”. She is very passionate about working as a public administrator: it is for her the way to give back to the community what she has received. She believes in the importance of equal opportunities, respect and the value of individuality. What does she suggest to young women? To believe, to be reliable and tenacious; to be responsible, empathetic and listening. Try to involve, work as a team, be a team player.</p>

Links	
Number	5
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	MARINA BALOSSI. LIONS LECCO: Via Maggiore, 19, 23900 Lecco LC;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.844912114864435, 9.398766311031418
Images	
Description	MARINA BALOSSI. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Marina is an entrepreneur and coordinator of the “Lions New Voices Committee”. Her daughters help define who she is today; having walked with them "determines me". She has an optimistic approach to the future: her family taught her that you don't give up, you don't give in, and that you always need courage; she also looks ahead with a sense of humour and her self-deprecation helps her in this. She believes in the importance of taking space and making an impact in practice, focusing less on big laws or impositions, but making an impact in the here and now. What does she suggest to young women? Not to live subject to the judgement of others, not to always conform, to be listening, to value the encounters they make in their own story, because every encounter is capable of leaving a mark and allows you to leave your own mark.
Links	

Number	6
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	FULVIA GREPPI. SEDE SOCIALE "HOTEL NH PONTEVECCHIO"di Lecco. Via Azzone Visconti, 84, 23900 Lecco LC.

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.848797445469074, 9.392827710482996
Images	
Description	<p>FULVIA GREPPI. Stakeholder of HerStory, woman of Lecco present. Fulvia is an entrepreneur. For the past three years she has been working in the association “Compagnia delle Opere”, which aims to support entrepreneurs, non-profit organisations, managers and professionals in the development of businesses and professional activities in an orientation for the good of all. She also likes to contribute to the social, national and international dimension; that is why she is a member of 'Soroptimist', an organisation that promotes actions and creates opportunities through the global network of members and international cooperation, so that all women can realise their individual and collective potential, realise their aspirations and create strong peaceful communities in the world. As an entrepreneur, she believes in work as a passion, as a relational life experience. Travelling opened her mind to the condition of women, which she then found in some realities in her area. What does she suggest to young women? To be consistent with themselves, to value independence and curiosity; to be flexible and resilient with respect to the physiological criticalities they will encounter. Travelling and learning are useful tools to confront and better understand that rights are not taken for granted, that what we have needs constant affirmation; to know how to oppose and not accept the first signs of discrimination.</p>
Links	

Number	7
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	LUISA BONO. LECCO POLICE HEADQUARTERS. Corso Promessi Sposi, 40, 23900 Lecco LC.
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.85531353440556, 9.403488536978456

Images	
Description	<p>LUISA BONO. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Luisa is a psychologist and psychotherapist. She graduated in Developmental Psychology and Educational Processes at Milano-Bicocca University and specialised in cognitive-behavioural-oriented psychotherapy at the Studi Cognitivi school in Milan. For several years she has been working in the field of primary prevention of child sexual abuse; she is an auxiliary of the Judicial Police and she works in the assessment and care of minors in situations of abuse and maltreatment. She believes in the importance of education and prevention from an early age; developing critical thinking, good examples, good role models. What does she suggest to young women? To be determined, despite hardships, to be tenacious, to be committed; to create a good synergy together, to stick together. Find the right way to manage one's time, give everything its due, give everything its weight, including taking personal space.</p>
Links	

Number	8
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	LEA GAROFALO. Via Cadorna, Lecco, LC, 23900;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.858920055345244, 9.385407411032437
Images	

Description	<p>LEA GAROFALO. In 2020, an associative reality in Lecco promoted an innovative action: symbolically changing the names of three city streets, naming them after great women of Italian history. Through a poll, citizens chose three women: among them, LEA GAROFALO. Lea was born in 1974 in Petilia Policastro (Crotona) where she grew up in a “Ndrangheta’s” family. She soon developed a spontaneous and genuine opposition to crime, trafficking and the logic that also belonged to her family, and so in 2002 she testified about the internal feuds between her family and that of her former partner Carlo Cosco. Initially subjected to protection, she was then excluded from the programme and, once readmitted, continued to be considered a collaborator of justice and not a witness; a condition that Lea did not accept. Threatened several times, in 2009 she was killed by her former partner and her body was set on fire.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YtzArWI-Fcg</p>

Number	<p>9</p>
City name	<p>Lecco</p>
Latitude & Longitude of the City	<p>45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376</p>
Name of the point of interest	<p>AURORA SPREAFICO. TEATRO SOCIALE DI LECCO. Piazza Giuseppe Garibaldi, 10, 23900 Lecco LC.</p>
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	<p>45.85292897869079, 9.389269938014593</p>
Images	
Description	<p>AURORA SPREAFICO. Stakeholder of HerStory, woman of Lecco present. Aurora is an actress and writer. She graduated from the Luca Ronconi School of “Piccolo Teatro di Milano” where she trained and worked with various actors and directors. In 2021, she published “Cavallucci”, her first collection of poems. Theatre is her passion and her dream; commitment and passion guide her in the pursuit of her professional and personal path. She enjoys engaging with young people who are choosing their future, offering them concrete spaces for dialogue and helping them to identify their interests and aspirations.</p>
Links	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I5rvrB3bB_I</p>

Number	10
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	FRANCESCA CICERI. via del Roccolo, Lecco, LC, 23900;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.850424123328374, 9.411676295686902
Images	
Description	FRANCESCA CICERI .In 2020, an associative reality in Lecco promoted an innovative action: symbolically changing the names of three city streets, naming them after great women of Italian history. Through a poll, citizens chose three women: among them, FRANCESCA CICERI. Francesca was born in Lecco in 1904; a member of the Communist Party of Italy, she was particularly active in organising and leading Italian women's groups in Paris and Lyon. She then returned to Italy to carry out anti-fascist activities among the textile workers and to direct the struggle of the "mondine" (rice weeders); having escaped and returned to Italy clandestinely from the Leninist school in Mosca, she and her husband were arrested and sentenced to eight years imprisonment. In 1943, she and her husband went to the Piani d'Erna and formed one of the first partisan formations. After the Liberation, she became leader of the PCI women's federation and a member of the Women's Consultative Commission of the Milan Chamber of Labour. In the last years of her life, she was president of the Lecco ANPI. In 1977, the municipal administration awarded her the gold medal for the Resistance. She died in Lecco in 1988.
Links	

Number	11
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	MARIA CALVETTI. CENTRO CIVICO SANDRO PERTINI; 23900 Lecco LC;

Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.852224154222895, 9.413542911031952
Images	
Description	<p>MARIA CALVETTI. On International Women's Day (2023), the Sandro Pertini Civic Centre (Lecco) was named after her. Maria was born in Lecco in 1950. Together with her husband, she set up the "Open Families" group of the "Centro Orientamento Educativo" (COE). She was president of the "Associazione Lecchese Famiglie Affidatarie" (Lecco Association of Foster Families) until obtaining, in 2011, together with her husband, the civic merit of the Municipality of Lecco for their testimony of a lifestyle marked by the values of concrete solidarity and openness to the world. She passed away in 2018.</p>
Links	

Number	12
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	ROMINA PAPINI. AMBITO DISTRETTUALE DI LECCO. Via Graziano Tubi, 43, 23900 Lecco LC.
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.85530887384826, 9.401667630961006

Images	
Description	<p>ROMINA PAPINI. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Romina is a pedagogist, a professional educator and a doula. She provides “gentle” support to new parents, supporting them both in the practical management of the tasks related to pregnancy and the newborn child and in the psychological dimension; it is therefore an accompaniment at different levels, in which “being gentle” is, for her, the key. She likes working in a network with municipalities, families, and health institutions, and she is now a point of reference at provincial level for the maternal-infant sphere, in pre-natal care. Today she is happy to have realised her dream: to work within the public service, therefore dedicated to everyone. Being a mother has helped her to understand how much you must be light when working with mothers and fathers; sometimes you just have to be. Her mantra is “walk light because you walk on my dreams”. What does she suggest to young women? To be tenacious, to try hard when they believe in something; to talk, discuss and share.</p>
Links	

Number	13
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	CARLA FERRACINI. SALA CIVICA A SAN GIOVANNI; Via Don Luigi Orione, 8, 23900 Lecco LC;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.86670185833263, 9.407538309179346

Images	
Description	<p>CARLA FERRACINI. On International Women's Day (2023), the civic hall in San Giovanni (Lecco) was named after her. Carla was born in Lecco in 1932. She attended the Brera Academy of Fine Arts in Brera and Milan and courses in Xylography and Lithography in Urbino. On returning to her hometown, she devoted herself to teaching, without however abandoning her artistic career. Two exhibitions were dedicated to her in Lecco: the first in 1998 at the Torre Viscontea and the second in 2012, again in the Torre Viscontea, entitled "Vie d'uscita". She donated one of her works to the "Sistema Museale Urbano Lecchese": "Il vascello fantasma". In 2001, Carla created the monument for Aido installed at Castello Cemetery. She passed away in February 2022.</p>
Links	

Number	14
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	GABRIELLA MALGARINI ZANINI. SALA CIVICA DI CASTELLO; Via Seminario, 39, 23900 Lecco LC;
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.864297092066586, 9.394507353360378

Images	
Description	<p>GABRIELLA MALGARINI ZANINI. On International Women's Day (2023), the civic hall in Castello (Lecco) was named after her. Gabriella was born in Mantova in 1921 and later moved to Lecco together with her husband, who like her was a paediatrician. Scarred by her father's death, she was interested from the outset in the study of palliative care, which began to be discussed in Lecco in 1995, when she proposed a service to the Soroptimist Club aimed at terminally ill oncological patients. In October 1996, the ACMT, "Associazione per la Cura dei Malati Terminali" (Association for the Care of the Terminally Ill) was established, of which she was president and with which she signed an agreement in 1999 to collaborate with the Asl home care service. Appointed honorary president in 2007, she passed away in 2010.</p>
Links	

Number	15
City name	Lecco
Latitude & Longitude of the City	45.857256560085844, 9.395715941783376
Name of the point of interest	NILDE IOTTI. via Bersaglio, Lecco, LC, 23900
Latitude & Longitude of the point of interest	45.86441445137566, 9.392062226377785
Images	

Description	NILDE IOTTI. In 2020, an associative reality in Lecco promoted an innovative action: symbolically changing the names of three city streets, naming them after great women of Italian history. Through a poll, citizens chose three women: among them, NILDE LIOTTI. Nilde was born in 1920 in Reggio Emilia, graduated in literature from the Catholic University of Milan; she directed the Women's Defence Group, a structure that was very active in the war of Liberation. She was the promoter of the family law (1975), the battle on the divorce referendum (1974) and the abortion law (1978). She was the first woman in the history of republican Italy to hold the office of President of the Chamber of Deputies; she went on to chair the Parliamentary Commission for Institutional Reforms and was elected Vice-President of the Council of Europe. The 'Lady of the Republic' passed away in 1999.
Links	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=okiugC3fvlk https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34rbBJT6Y_8 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eQDVLYXL4p0

3. Treasure Hunt Paths

3.1. Salamanca, Spain

In English		
City, Country: Salamanca, España		
Start point: Plaza de los Bandos		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	House of Santa Teresa de Jesús. Calle Condes de Crespo Rascón, 25	Would you like to find a place representative of Saint Teresa of Jesus in the city? She was a writer and religious woman. To give you a little clue, you have to go to a well-known square in the city of Salamanca. Woman: Santa Teresa de Jesús
Next challenge! This has only just begun.		
2	Plaza de los Bandos, 3	Find the location of the monument to Carmen Martín Gaité. It was erected in 2000 to commemorate this historic woman from Salamanca. She was a writer, linked to the theatre and won several prizes. Woman: Carmen Martín Gaité
Now, go to the heart of Salamanca! One of its emblematic places, let's go for the next clue!		
3	Plaza Mayor, 1	You can find several medallions in one of Salamanca's most emblematic squares. Some of them are of women who have ruled the city. Look for the square and find a medallion of one of these women, for example, Queen Juana Manuel de Villena. She was governor of Salamanca from 1369 to 1381 due to her marriage to Enrique de Trastámara. Woman: Queen Juana Manuel de Villena
Once you have arrived at the Plaza Mayor of Salamanca, dare to move on to the next step!		
4	Central Food Market of Salamanca. Plaza del Mercado, 0	Did you know that for a while in Salamanca people lived among the chants and aromas of "¡Merengues, rosquillas, a cuaaaaaarto!"? Come down a little from where you are right now and find the place where the Merenguera sold her sweets.

		Woman: Romana González La Merenguera
You've already sweetened up a bit! Now, keep walking between the theatre and the stage.		
5	Faculty of Philology of the University of Salamanca. Plaza de Anaya, s/n	Which faculty in Salamanca would you go to if you wanted to know more about Helena Pimenta? She was director of the Compañía Nacional de Teatro Clásico from 2011 to 2019. In 1993 she was awarded the Premio Nacional de Teatro. She is the first woman to head the Compañía Nacional de Teatro Clásico (CNTC) since its foundation. Woman: Helena Pimenta
Continue along the streets that are marked by the University of Salamanca. With the following clue you will arrive at one of its Centres.		
6	CEMUSA, Aulario de San Isidro. Plaza de San Isidro, 1	Did you know that Ana Díaz Medina has been a professor and director of a Centre at the University of Salamanca? This Centre carries out research and numerous activities on women. Find out more! Woman: Ana Díaz Medina
Now that you have discovered CEMUSA, now CIGESAL, let's take a walk through another of the Faculties of the University of Salamanca!		
7	Faculty of Geography and History of the University of Salamanca. Calle Cervantes, s/n	Teresa Vicente Mosquet was part of the Interdisciplinary Gender Studies Programme and was a Professor of Geography. Where do you think she taught her classes? Woman: Teresa Vicente Mosquet
You've already walked between Geography and History. Where would you go if you were looking for international training?		
8	International Courses of the University of Salamanca. Plaza Fray Luis de León, 1	Did you know that Dolores Cebrián Fernández Villegas was born in Salamanca? She was a Spanish educator and scientist, also noted for her valuable contribution to teaching and science. Look for her where you would want to find her internationally. The Antiguo Colegio Mayor de San Bartolomé was located there and was the Antiguo Colegio de Maestras. Woman: Dolores Cebrián Fernández Villegas
Now you'll have to search the street itself! Keep an eye out for the next clue.		
9	Calle La Latina, 7	Where could you find evidence of Beatriz Galindo's legacy in Salamanca? Look for a monument, commemorative plaque or statue that honours her

		<p>contribution to the city's history by walking along Calle La Latina.</p> <p>Woman: Beatriz de Galindo</p>
<p>Only two more places left. Run, go to your next clue!</p>		
10	<p>Tower of the Cathedral of Salamanca. Plaza Juan XXIII, s/n</p>	<p>Where do you think you can find the grave of Doña Urraca? It is a sculptural work of great historical and artistic value. If you can't go inside, you can take a photo from outside.</p> <p>Woman: Doña Urraca</p>
<p>Last steps! One more clue and you've got it.</p>		
11	<p>Old Cathedral of Santa María de la Sede. Calle Doyagüe</p>	<p>Where do you think Doña Mafalda was buried? It is next to the main altarpiece presided over by the patron saint, Virgen de la Vega.</p> <p>Woman: Doña Mafalda</p>
<p>Fantastic! You've done it! Now you know something more about the historical women of your city, congratulations!</p>		

In the National language

<p>City, Country: Salamanca, España</p>		
<p>Start point: Plaza de los Bandos</p>		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	<p>House of Santa Teresa de Jesús. Calle Condes de Crespo Rascón, 25</p>	<p>¿Te animas a encontrar un lugar representativo de Santa Teresa de Jesús en la ciudad? Fue una mujer escritora y religiosa. Para darte una pequeña pista, tienes que ir a una plaza conocida en la ciudad de Salamanca.</p> <p>Woman: Santa Teresa de Jesús</p>
<p>¡Siguiente reto! Esto solo acaba de empezar.</p>		
2	<p>Plaza de los Bandos, 3</p>	<p>Encuentra el lugar donde está el monumento a Carmen Martín Gaité. Este se erigió en el año 2000 para conmemorar a esta mujer histórica de Salamanca. Fue escritora, vinculada al teatro y ganó diferentes premios.</p> <p>Woman: Carmen Martín Gaité</p>

¡Ahora, ve al corazón de Salamanca! Uno de sus lugares emblemáticos. ¡A por la siguiente pista!		
3	Plaza Mayor, 1	<p>Puedes encontrar varios medallones en una de las plazas más emblemáticas de Salamanca. Algunos de ellos son de mujeres que han gobernado en la ciudad. Busca la plaza y encuentra algún medallón de estas mujeres, por ejemplo, de la Reina Juana Manuel de Villena. She was governor of Salamanca from 1369 to 1381 due to her marriage to Enrique de Trastámara.</p> <p>Woman: Queen Juana Manuel de Villena</p>
Una vez que ya has llegado a la Plaza Mayor de Salamanca, ¡atrévete a pasar al siguiente paso!		
4	Central Food Market of Salamanca. Plaza del Mercado, 0	<p>¿Sabías que durante un tiempo en Salamanca se vivió entre los cantos y los aromas de “¡Merengues, rosquillas, a cuaaaaarto!”? Baja un poco del sitio donde estás ahora mismo y encuentra el lugar donde la Merenguera vendió sus dulces.</p> <p>Woman: Romana González La Merenguera</p>
¡Ya te has endulzado un poco! Ahora, sigue caminando entre el teatro y la escena.		
5	Faculty of Philology of the University of Salamanca. Plaza de Anaya, s/n	<p>¿A qué Facultad de Salamanca irías si quisieras conocer algo más sobre Helena Pimenta? She was director of the Compañía Nacional de Teatro Clásico from 2011 to 2019. In 1993 she was awarded the Premio Nacional de Teatro. She is the first woman to head the Compañía Nacional de Teatro Clásico (CNTC) since its foundation.</p> <p>Woman: Helena Pimenta</p>
Sigue recorriendo las calles que están marcadas por la Universidad de Salamanca. Con la siguiente pista llegarás a uno de sus Centros.		
6	CEMUSA, Aulario de San Isidro. Plaza de San Isidro, 1	<p>¿Sabías que Ana Díaz Medina ha sido profesora y directora de un Centro de la Universidad de Salamanca? En este Centro se investiga y realizan numerosas actividades sobre la mujer. ¡Encuétralo!</p> <p>Woman: Ana Díaz Medina</p>
Ahora que ya has descubierto el CEMUSA, actual CIGESAL, ¡vamos a pasear por otra de las Facultades de la Universidad de Salamanca!		
7	Faculty of Geography and History of the University of Salamanca. Calle Cervantes, s/n	<p>Teresa Vicente Mosquet formó parte del Programa de Estudios Interdisciplinarios de Género y fue profesora Catedrática en Geografía. ¿En qué lugar crees que impartió sus clases?</p> <p>Woman: Teresa Vicente Mosquet</p>

Ya has paseado entre la Geografía y la Historia. ¿Dónde irías si buscaras formación internacional?		
8	International Courses of the University of Salamanca. Plaza Fray Luis de León, 1	¿Sabías que Dolores Cebrián Fernández Villegas nació en Salamanca? Fue educadora y científica española, también destacó por su valiosa contribución en la enseñanza y la ciencia. Búscala en donde lo internacional querrías encontrar. Allí se ubicaba el Antiguo Colegio Mayor de San Bartolomé y fue el Antiguo Colegio de Maestras. Woman: Dolores Cebrián Fernández Villegas
¡Ahora tendrás que buscar en la propia calle! Estate muy pendiente de la siguiente pista.		
9	Calle La Latina, 7	¿Dónde podrías encontrar evidencia del legado de Beatriz Galindo en Salamanca? Busca un monumento, placa conmemorativa o estatua que honre su contribución a la historia de la ciudad, descúbrelo caminando por la Calle La Latina. Woman: Beatriz de Galindo
Solo quedan dos lugares más. ¡Corre, ve a tu siguiente pista!		
10	Tower of the Cathedral of Salamanca. Plaza Juan XXIII, s/n	¿En qué lugar crees que puedes encontrar el sepulcro de Doña Urraca? Es una obra escultórica de gran valor histórico y artístico. Si no puedes entrar, puedes hacer una foto desde fuera. Woman: Doña Urraca
¡Últimos pasos! Una pista más y ya lo tienes.		
11	Old Cathedral of Santa María de la Sede. Calle Doyagüe	¿Dónde piensas que fue enterrada Doña Mafalda? Está junto al retablo mayor presidido por la patrona, Virgen de la Vega. Woman: Doña Mafalda
¡Fantástico! ¡Lo has hecho! Ahora sabes algo más sobre las mujeres históricas de tu ciudad, ¡enhorabuena!		

3.2. Fort-de-France, France

In English

City, Country: Fort-de-France, Martinique, France

Start point: Le Carénage

Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	Le Carénage	<p>What was the work of the charcoal burners (“les charbonnières”)?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prepare coal for sale and distribution 2. Supply coal to factory furnaces 3. Mine coal in the mines 4. Supply coal to steamships [Correct] <p>How many kilograms did the baskets that the charcoal burners put on their heads to transport coal weigh?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 5 kg 2. 10 kg 3. 40 kg [Correct] 4. 60 kg
2	Place Paulette Nardal	<p>What was Paulette Nardal's field of study at La Sorbonne?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mathematics 2. Literature 3. History 4. English [Correct] <p>Which literary movement was influenced by Paulette Nardal?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Symbolism 2. Dadaism 3. Negritude [Correct] 4. Impressionism
3	UFM (Espace Jane Léro)	<p>When did Jane Léro found the Union des Femmes de Martinique?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. in June 1920 2. in June 1944 [Correct] 3. in June 1945 4. in June 1968 <p>When did women in France first gain the right to vote in elections?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. February 21, 1848 2. March 15, 1944

		<p>3. April 21, 1944 [Correct]</p> <p>4. August 28, 1962</p>
4	Loge d'émancipation féminine	<p>What is Claude Carbet's birth name?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Claudia Tricot 2. Marie-Magdeleine Tricot 3. Olympe Tricot [Correct] 4. Daphné Tricot <p>Which themes did Claude Carbet often explore in her writings?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Romance and adventure 2. Political satire 3. Colonial oppression and women's rights [Correct] 4. Scientific exploration
5	La Maison de Solange	<p>How long did Solange Fitte Duval serve as president of the UFM?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 10 years 2. 15 years 3. 20 years [Correct] 4. 25 years <p>Who is the target audience of La Maison de Solange?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Illiterate women 2. Women victims of violence [Correct] 3. Undocumented women 4. Homeless women

In French

City, Country: Fort-de-France, Martinique, France		
Start point: Le Carénage		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	Le Carénage	<p>Quel était le travail des charbonnières?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Préparer du charbon pour la vente et la distribution 2. Fournir du charbon aux fours des usines 3. Extraire du charbon dans les mines

		<p>4. Fournir du charbon aux bateaux à vapeur [Correct]</p> <p>Combien de kilogrammes pesaient les paniers que les charbonnières mettaient sur leur tête pour transporter du charbon ?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5 kg 10 kg 40 kg [Correct] 60 kg
2	Place Paulette Nardal	<p>Quel était le domaine d'études de Paulette Nardal à La Sorbonne?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Mathématiques Littérature Histoire Anglais [Correct] <p>Quel mouvement littéraire a été influencé par Paulette Nardal?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Symbolisme Dadaïsme Négritude [Correct] Impressionnisme
3	UFM (Espace Jane Léro)	<p>Quand Jane Léro a-t-elle fondé l'Union des Femmes de Martinique?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> en juin 1920 en juin 1944 [Correct] en juin 1945 en juin 1968 <p>Quand les femmes en France ont-elles obtenu pour la première fois le droit de vote aux élections ?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> le 21 février 1848 le 15 mars 1944 le 21 avril 1944 [Correct] le 28 août 1962
4	Loge d'émancipation féminine	<p>Quel est le nom de naissance de Claude Carbet?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Claudia Tricot Marie-Magdeleine Tricot Olympe Tricot [Correct]

		<p>4. Daphné Tricot</p> <p>Quels thèmes Claude Carbet explorait-elle souvent dans ses écrits?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Romance et aventure 2. Satire politique 3. Oppression coloniale et droits des femmes [Correct] 4. Exploration scientifique
5	La Maison de Solange	<p>Combien de temps Solange Fitte Duval a-t-elle été présidente de l'UFM?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 10 ans 2. 15 ans 3. 20 ans [Correct] 4. 25 ans <p>À qui La Maison de Solange s'adresse-t-elle?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Des femmes analphabètes 2. Des femmes victimes de violence [Correct] 3. Des femmes sans papiers 4. Des femmes sans domicile fixe

3.3. Nicosia, Cyprus

In English

City, Country: Nicosia, Cyprus		
Start point: Faneromeni School		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	Faneromeni School	<p>What was Faneromeni School when it was created?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first primary school for girls in Cyprus. [Correct] 2. The first school in Cyprus. [False] 3. The first university for architects in Cyprus. [False]

2	Anna Tigiridou	<p>Who was Anna Tigiridou?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first teacher in Cyprus. [False] 2. The first dentist in Cyprus. [Correct] 3. The first architect in Cyprus. [False]
3	The Royal Hall	<p>1905 was the year women voted for the first time in elections, however...:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Someone neglected to write into the law that of those who paid taxes, only men were entitled to vote. [Correct] 2. Only women who did not work were allowed to vote. [False] 3. Only women who were married had the right to vote. [False]
4	Diamantou Charalambous	<p>Who was Diamantou Charalambous?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Diamantou Charalambous was the daughter of Makarios during the British colonial period. [False] 2. Diamantou Charalambous was a construction worker during the British colonial period. [Correct] 3. Diamantou Charalambous was a famous teacher during the British colonial period. [False]
5	Arsinoes Street	<p>Where did Arsinoes Street in Cyprus get its name from?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. From Arsinoe, daughter of Lefkippos from Ancient Greek Mythology. [False] 2. Arsinoes Street was named after the wife of King Leontocrates of Cyprus during the Ptolemaic dynasty. [Correct] 3. Arsinoes Street took its name from the president of the Republic of Cyprus, Arsinoe. [False]
6	Ledras Street -Loukia Nikolaidou	<p>Loukia Nicolaidou was the first female painter in Cyprus. Where did she study?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nicosia. [False] 2. Paris. [Correct] 3. England. [False]

Πόλη, Χώρα: Λευκωσία, Κύπρος		
Σημείο Εκκίνησης: Παρθεναγωγείο Φανερωμένης		
Αριθμός	Σημείο κυνήγι θησαυρού	Κουίζ
1	Παρθεναγωγείο Φανερωμένης	<p>Τι ήταν το Παρθεναγωγείο Φανερωμένης όταν δημιουργήθηκε;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Η πρώτη πρωτοβάθμια σχολή για κορίτσια στην Κύπρο. [Σωστό] 2. Το πρώτο σχολείο στην Κύπρο. [Λάθος] 3. Το πρώτο πανεπιστήμιο για αρχιτέκτονες στην Κύπρο. [Λάθος]
2	Άννα Τιγγιρίδου	<p>Ποια ήταν η Άννα Τιγγιρίδου;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Η πρώτη δασκάλα στην Κύπρο. [Λάθος] 2. Η πρώτη οδοντίατρος στην Κύπρο. [Σωστό] 3. Η πρώτη αρχιτέκτονας στην Κύπρο. [Λάθος]
3	Ρογιαλ Χολ	<p>Το 1905 ήταν η χρονιά που για πρώτη φορά ψήφισαν γυναίκες σε εκλογές, όμως...:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Κάποιος αμέλησε να γράψει μέσα στο νόμο ότι από όσους πλήρωναν φόρους μόνο οι άντρες δικαιούνταν να ψηφίσουν. [Σωστό] 2. Ψήφιζαν γυναίκες που δεν δούλευαν. [Λάθος] 3. Ψήφιζαν γυναίκες που ήταν παντρεμένες. [Λάθος]
4	Διαμαντού Χαραλάμπους	<p>Ποια ήταν η Διαμαντού Χαραλάμπους;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Η Διαμαντού Χαραλάμπους ήταν κόρη του Μακάριου κατά την Βρετανική αποικιοκρατία. [Λάθος] 2. Η Διαμαντού Χαραλάμπους ήταν εργάτρια στην κατασκευαστική βιομηχανία κατά την Βρετανική αποικιοκρατία. [Σωστό] 3. Η Διαμαντού Χαραλάμπους ήταν φημισμένη δασκάλα κατά τη Βρετανική αποικιοκρατία. [Λάθος]
5	Οδός Αρσινόης	<p>Από που πήρε το όνομα της η Οδός Αρσινόης στην Κύπρο;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Από την Αρσινόη, κόρη του Λευκίππου από την Αρχαία Ελληνική Μυθολογία. [Λάθος]

		<p>2. Η Οδός Αρσινόης πήρε το όνομα της από την σύζυγο του Βασιλιά Λεοντόκρατου της Κύπρου κατά τη διάρκεια της Πτολεμαϊκής δυναστείας. [Σωστό]</p> <p>3. Η Οδός Αρσινόης πήρε το όνομα της από την πρόεδρο της ΚΔ την Αρσινόη. [Λάθος]</p>
6	Οδός Λήδρας - Λουκία Νικολαΐδου	<p>Η Λουκία Νικολαΐδου ήταν η πρώτη γυναίκα ζωγράφος στην Κύπρο. Που σπούδασε;</p> <p>1. Σπούδασε στη Λευκωσία. [Λάθος]</p> <p>2. Σπούδασε τέχνη στο Παρίσι. [Σωστό]</p> <p>3. Σπούδασε τέχνη στην Αγγλία. [Λάθος]</p>

3.4. Athens, Greece

In English

City, Country: Athens, Greece		
Start point: Melina Merkouri's bust		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	Melina Merkouri's bust	<p>I am known as the last Greek goddess, thanks to my fight against dictatorship and my involvement as Minister of Culture. I am widely known as the person who initiated the fight for the return of Parthenon Marbles back in Greece, a fight that still continues and I am a well-known actress.</p> <p>1. Aliko Vougiouklaki 2. Melina Merkouri [Correct] 3. Tzeni Karezi</p>
2	Tzeni Karezi's Theatre	<p>Tzeni Karezi had rich social and political activity while she managed to be a protagonist in important plays in cinema and theatre and the plays in cinema are still played on TV.</p> <p>1. Wrong 2. Right [Correct]</p>
3	Sappho's Statue-Onassis Cultural Foundation	<p>Identify the Greek lyric poet, that hailed from Lesbos and is known for their poetry, which vibrated with</p>

		<p>spontaneity and intense emotions. The term "Lesbian love" has also been associated with their name.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Erinna 2. Sappho [Correct] 3. Corinna
4	Manto Mavrogenous' Bust - Pedion tou Areos	<p>Select the correct story:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manto Mavrogenous was a heroine who contributed her fortune to the Hellenic cause, was born in Trieste, and led the rebellion on Mykonos. Her financial support made her legendary in European philhellenic circles. She was honored with the rank of Lieutenant General but later died penniless in Paro. [Correct] 2. Manto Mavrogenous was a Greek poet whose works inspired the Greek War of Independence. Born in Athens, she financed the rebellion of the island's inhabitants against the Turks and her literary contributions, she was honored by Ioannis Kapodistrias with the title of Chief Poetess but died in wealth in Mykonos. 3. Manto Mavrogenous was a French noblewoman who supported the Greek War of Independence. She was instrumental in providing strategic advice and military training to Greek soldiers. Born in Paris, she moved to Greece and played a key role in the naval battles.
5	Domnas Visvizi's' Bust - Pedion tou Areos	<p>Domna Visvizi was a Greek maritime captain who took command of her ship after her husband's death in July 1822 and continued to fight in the war. Despite running low on funds and being rejected additional funding by the Greek leadership, she gave her boat, the Kalomoira, to the Greek navy in 1824.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wrong 2. Right [Correct]
6	Laskarina Bouboulinas' Bust - Pedion tou Areos	<p>Apart from Domna Visvizi and Manto Mavrogenous, which was another famous heroine of Greek Independence war also part of the Filiki Etaireia secret society. Following the defeat of my faction in the Greek civil war:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Laskarina Bouboulina [Correct] 2. Athena Goddess 3. Queen Amalia

7	Paxinos-Minotis Museum	<p>Who was the first Greek actress who managed to make it in Hollywood and even on her own terms, and the first non-American actress that won an Academy Award for Best Actress for her performance in the film "For Whom the Bell Tolls"?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tzeni Karezi 2. Katina Paxinou [Correct] 3. Greta Garbo
8	Marble Plaque of Antigoni Krontira-Metaxa	<p>Antigoni Metaxa-Krontira was an important Greek educator who studied Educational Science in Paris, and in 1933 she founded the first children's theatre for children in Greece. She produced vinyl records of fairy tales and songs and the first children's television show. Her goal was to educate children by entertaining them. She was awarded by the Academy of Athens for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Combining children's education with theatre 2. Creating first television show. 3. Creating the first children's theatre for children. 4. All the above [Correct]
9	National Gallery-Opi Zouni	<p>Opi Zoumi (1941-2008) had more of 70 solo exhibitions in Europe and 450 participations in group exhibitions and she was an important representative of geometric art in Greece. Where was her work was not initially recognized at her time?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Greece [Correct] 2. Europe 3. Internationally
10	Experimental Special Primary School "Rosa Imvrioti"	<p>Who was a pioneer of special education, with a rich social and political activity, worked as a teacher of literature in middle schools and in 1934 and became the first female middle school principal? Also, she was an elected member of the Council of the International Women's Union but was exiled and suffered tortures due to her political activity.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Marika Kotopouli 2. Rosa Imvrioti [Correct] 3. Melina Merkouri
11	Lela Karagianni's Bust-Exarxeia Square	<p>She was a legendary fighter of the National Resistance against the German troops in the period 1941- 1944. A protagonist of the «Secret War», although a mother of seven children, and the first Greek citizen to offer organized resistance against the German enemy. She became a renowned symbol of resistance worldwide. Who is she?</p>

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Melina Merkouri 2. Lela Karagianni [Correct] 3. Tzeni Karezi
12	Kalliroi Parren's Bust-1st Cemetery of Athens	<p>Kalliroi Parren is considered to be one of the first Greek feminists, and the first Greek woman journalist, editor and director of the feminist newspaper that was written exclusively by women and addressed mainly to women in Athens and Piraeus named "Efimeris ton Kirion".</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Right [Correct] 2. Wrong
13	Marina Galanou	<p>Marina Galanou has been the President of the Greek Transgender Support Association, a publisher of the publishing house and bookstore "Colourful Planet" and was with civil society organizations for more than 20 years. Based on her activism, the LGBTQ+ community in Greece received more equal rights and a safe space network.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Right [Correct] 2. Wrong
14	Efi Vembou	<p>She was a leading Greek singer and actress active from the interwar period to the early postwar years and the 1950s. She became best known for her performance of patriotic songs during the Greco-Italian War, when she was dubbed the "Songstress of Victory". What is her known name?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sofia Vembo [Correct] 2. Maria Vembo 3. Eleni Vembo

In Greek

Πόλη, Χώρα: Αθήνα, Ελλάδα		
Σημείο εκκίνησης: Προτομή Μελίνας Μερκούρη		
Αριθμός	Σημείο ενδιαφέροντος	Κουίζ
1	Η προτομή της Μελίνας Μερκούρη	Είμαι γνωστή ως η τελευταία Ελληνίδα θεά, χάρη στον αγώνα μου κατά της δικτατορίας και τη συμμετοχή μου στην πολιτική ως Υπουργός Πολιτισμού. Είμαι ευρέως γνωστή ως το άτομο που ξεκίνησε τον αγώνα για την επιστροφή των Γλυπτών του Παρθενώνα πίσω στην

		<p>Ελλάδα, έναν αγώνα που συνεχίζεται ακόμα και σήμερα και είμαι γνωστή ηθοποιός.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Αλίκη Βουγιουκλάκη 2. Μελίνα Μερκούρη [Σωστό] 3. Τζένη Καρέζη
2	Θέατρο Τζένη Καρέζη	<p>Η Τζένη Καρέζη είχε πλούσια κοινωνική και πολιτική δραστηριότητα ενώ κατάφερε να πρωταγωνιστήσει σε σημαντικά έργα του κινηματογράφου και του θεάτρου και τα έργα στον κινηματογράφο παίζονται ακόμα στην τηλεόραση.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Λάθος 2. Σωστό [Σωστό]
3	Άγαμα Σαπφούς-Στέγη Γραμμάτων και Τεχνών Ίδρυμα Ωνάση	<p>Προσδιορίστε την Ελληνίδα στην αρχαία Ελλάδα που δημιούργησε λυρικά ποιήματα, με καταγωγή από τη Λέσβο. Είναι γνωστή για την ποίησή της, η οποία δονούνταν από αυθορμητισμό και έντονα συναισθήματα. Ο όρος "λεσβιακή αγάπη" έχει επίσης συνδεθεί με το όνομά της. Ποια είναι;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Έρινα 2. Σαπφώ [Σωστό] 3. Κορίνα
4	Προτομή Μαντώ Μαυρογένους - Πεδίον του Άρεως	<p>Επιλέξτε τη σωστή ιστορία:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Η Μαντώ Μαυρογένους ήταν ηρωίδα που συνεισέφερε την περιουσία της στην Ελληνική Επανάσταση, γεννήθηκε στην Τεργέστη και ηγήθηκε της εξέγερσης στη Μύκονο. Η οικονομική της στήριξη την έκανε θρυλική στους ευρωπαϊκούς φιλελληνικούς κύκλους. Τιμήθηκε με το βαθμό του αντιστράτηγου, αλλά αργότερα όμως πέθανε απένταρη, στην Πάρο. [Σωστό] 2. Η Μαντώ Μαυρογένους ήταν Ελληνίδα ποιήτρια της οποίας τα έργα ενέπνευσαν την Ελληνική Επανάσταση. Γεννημένη στην Αθήνα, χρηματοδότησε την εξέγερση των κατοίκων του νησιού κατά των Τούρκων και τη λογοτεχνική της προσφορά, τιμήθηκε από τον Ιωάννη Καποδίστρια με τον τίτλο της Πρωτοποικήτριας αλλά πέθανε πλούσια στη Μύκονο. 3. Η Μαντώ Μαυρογένους ήταν Γαλλίδα ευγενής που υποστήριξε την Ελληνική Επανάσταση. Διαδραμάτισε καθοριστικό ρόλο στην παροχή συμβουλών και στρατιωτικής εκπαίδευσης στους Έλληνες στρατιώτες. Γεννημένη στο

		Παρίσι, εγκαταστάθηκε στην Ελλάδα και έπαιξε καθοριστικό ρόλο στις ναυμαχίες.
5	Προτομή Δόμνας Βισβίζη - Πεδίων επίσης Άρεως	<p>Η Δόμνα Βισβίζη ήταν Ελληνίδα καπετάνισσα που ανέλαβε τη διοίκηση του πλοίου της μετά το θάνατο του συζύγου της τον Ιούλιο του 1822 και συνέχισε να πολεμά στον πόλεμο. Παρά το γεγονός ότι εξαντλήθηκαν τα κονδύλια και απορρίφθηκε η πρόσθετη χρηματοδότηση της από την ελληνική ηγεσία, έδωσε το πλοίο της, το Καλομοίρα, στο ελληνικό ναυτικό το 1824.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Λάθος 2. Σωστό [Σωστό]
6	Προτομή Λασκαρίνας Μπουμπουλίνας - Πεδίων του Άρεως	<p>Εκτός από τη Δόμνα Βισβίζη και τη Μαντώ Μαυρογένους, ποια ήταν μια άλλη μια διάσημη ηρωίδα του αγώνα της Ελληνικής Ανεξαρτησίας, επίσης μέλος της μυστικής εταιρείας της Φιλικής Εταιρείας; Ήταν η πρώτη γυναίκα ναύαρχος στην Ιστορία και είχε σχηματίσει δικό της εκστρατευτικό σώμα από Σπετσιώτες, τους οποίους αποκαλούσε «γενναία μου παλικάρια». Είχε αναλάβει να αρματώνει, να συντηρεί και να πληρώνει τον στρατό αυτό με τη περιουσία της.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Λασκαρίνα Μπουμπουλίνα [Σωστό] 2. Θεά Αθηνά 3. Βασίλισσα Αμαλία
7	Μουσείο Παξινού-Μινωτή	<p>Ποια ήταν η πρώτη Ελληνίδα ηθοποιός που κατάφερε να μπει στο Χόλιγουντ και μάλιστα με τους δικούς της όρους, και η πρώτη μη Αμερικανίδα ηθοποιός που κέρδισε Όσκαρ Καλύτερης Ηθοποιού για την ερμηνεία της στην ταινία " Για Ποιον Χτυπά η Καμπάνα".</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Τζένη Καρέζη 2. Κατίνα Παξινού [Σωστό] 3. Γκρέτα Γκάρμπο
8	Μαρμάρινη Πλάκα Αντιγόνης Κροντήρα-Μεταξά	<p>Η Αντιγόνη Μεταξά-Κροντηρά ήταν σημαντική Ελληνίδα παιδαγωγός που σπούδασε Παιδαγωγικές Επιστήμες στο Παρίσι και το 1933 ίδρυσε το πρώτο παιδικό θέατρο για παιδιά στην Ελλάδα. Παρήγαγε δίσκους βινυλίου με παραμύθια και τραγούδια και την πρώτη παιδική τηλεοπτική εκπομπή. Στόχος της ήταν να εκπαιδεύσει τα παιδιά διασκεδάζοντάς τα. Βραβεύτηκε από την Ακαδημία Αθηνών για:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Τον συνδυασμό της εκπαίδευσης των παιδιών με το θέατρο. 2. Δημιουργία πρώτης τηλεοπτικής εκπομπής.

		<p>3. Δημιουργία του πρώτου παιδικού θεάτρου για παιδιά.</p> <p>4. Όλα τα παραπάνω. [Σωστό]</p>
9	Εθνική Πινακοθήκη-Όπι Ζούνη	<p>Η Όπη Ζούμη (1941-2008) είχε περισσότερες από 70 ατομικές εκθέσεις στην Ευρώπη και 450 συμμετοχές σε ομαδικές εκθέσεις και υπήρξε σημαντική εκπρόσωπος της γεωμετρικής τέχνης στην Ελλάδα. Σε ποια περιοχή το έργο της δεν αναγνωρίστηκε αρχικά στην εποχή της;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ελλάδα [Σωστό] 2. Ευρώπη 3. Διεθνώς
10	Πειραματικό Ειδικό Δημοτικό Σχολείο «Ρόζα Ιμβρυώτη»	<p>Η πρωτοπόρος της ειδικής αγωγής, με πλούσια κοινωνική και πολιτική δραστηριότητα, εργάστηκε ως καθηγήτρια λογοτεχνίας σε γυμνάσια και το 1934 έγινε η πρώτη γυναίκα διευθύντρια γυμνασίου. Επίσης, ήταν εκλεγμένο μέλος του Συμβουλίου της Διεθνούς Ένωσης Γυναικών, αλλά εξορίστηκε και υπέστη βασανιστήρια λόγω της πολιτικής της δραστηριότητας. Ποια ήταν;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Μαρίκα Κοτοπούλη 2. Ρόζα Ιμβρυώτη [Σωστό] 3. Μελίνα Μερκούρη
11	Προτομή Λέλας Καραγιάννη-Εξάρχεια	<p>Υπήρξε θρυλική αγωνίστρια της Εθνικής Αντίστασης κατά των γερμανικών στρατευμάτων την περίοδο 1941-1944. Πρωταγωνίστρια του «Μυστικού Πολέμου», αν και μητέρα επτά παιδιών, και η πρώτη Ελληνίδα πολίτης που προέβαλε οργανωμένη αντίσταση κατά του γερμανικού εχθρού. Έγινε ένα διάσημο σύμβολο αντίστασης παγκοσμίως. Ποια είναι;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Μελίνα Μερκούρη 2. Λέλα Καραγιάννη [Σωστό] 3. Τζένη Καρέζη
12	Προτομή Καλλιρόης Παρρέν-1ο Νεκροταφείο Αθηνών	<p>Η παρακάτω περιγραφή είναι σωστή ή λάθος: Η Καλλιρόη Παρρέν θεωρείται μία από τις πρώτες Ελληνίδες φεμινίστριες και η πρώτη Ελληνίδα δημοσιογράφος, εκδότρια και διευθύντρια της φεμινιστικής εφημερίδας που γράφτηκε αποκλειστικά από γυναίκες και απευθυνόταν κυρίως σε γυναίκες στην Αθήνα και τον Πειραιά με την επωνυμία «Εφημερίδα των Κυριών».</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Σωστό [Σωστό] 2. Λάθος

13	Μαρίνα Γαλανού	<p>Η παρακάτω περιγραφή είναι σωστή ή λάθος: Η Μαρίνα Γαλανού έχει διατελέσει Πρόεδρος του Σωματίου Υποστήριξης Διεμφυλικών, δημιουργός του εκδοτικού οίκου και βιβλιοπωλείου «Πολύχρωμος Πλανήτης» και ήταν ηγέτιδα οργανώσεων της κοινωνίας των πολιτών για περισσότερα από 20 χρόνια. Με βάση τον ακτιβισμό της, η ΛΟΑΤΚΙ+ κοινότητα στην Ελλάδα έλαβε περισσότερα ίσα δικαιώματα και ένα δίκτυο ασφαλούς χώρου.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Σωστό [Σωστό] 2. Λάθος
14	Σοφία Βέμπο	<p>Υπήρξε κορυφαία Ελληνίδα τραγουδίστρια και ηθοποιός που δραστηριοποιήθηκε από τον μεσοπόλεμο έως τα πρώτα μεταπολεμικά χρόνια και τη δεκαετία του 1950. Έγινε περισσότερο γνωστή για την ερμηνεία πατριωτικών τραγουδιών κατά τη διάρκεια του ελληνοϊταλικού πολέμου, όταν ονομάστηκε «τραγουδίστρια της νίκης». Ποιο είναι το γνωστό της όνομα;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Σοφία Βέμπο [Σωστό] 2. Μαρία Βέμπο 3. Ελένη Βέμπο

3.5. Sofia, Bulgaria

In English

City, Country: Sofia, Bulgaria		
Start point: Sofia university "St.Kliment Ohridski"		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski"	<p>Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski" is a state research university in Sofia, Bulgaria. It is the oldest higher education institution in the country. This is the birth date of the Bulgarian university education - only 10 years after the country's liberation.</p> <p>At the beginning, there were 43 students, only men. The first women were admitted in 1901, after many years of petitioning at the National Assembly. Thus, the nation's potential for scientific innovation and the</p>

		<p>development of Bulgarian science in general were significantly increased.</p> <p>In which year did women begin to attend University in Bulgaria?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1901 [Correct] 2. 1888 3. 1903 <p>Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski" is the:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Biggest higher education institution in Bulgaria 2. Oldest higher education institution in Bulgaria [Correct] 3. Most modern higher education institution in Bulgaria 4. D. All the above
2	<p>Elizaveta Karamihailova's Memorial plaque</p>	<p>Elizaveta Karamihailova (1897-1968) was the first woman nuclear physicist in Bulgaria. She created the first practical courses in elementary particle physics and became the first woman professor in the country.</p> <p>In 1917 she began studying electrical and radio engineering at the University of Vienna. Her research on gamma rays and polonium is still relevant today and is considered a significant advance in modern physics.</p> <p>Elizaveta graduated with a PhD in physics and mathematics in Vienna. In 1939, after many years of efforts, she was finally appointed full associate professor of experimental atomic physics at Sofia University. She even converted her office into a laboratory to provide her students with hands-on training in modern scientific methods.</p> <p>In 1945, Elizaveta became head of the newly established Department of Atomic Physics at the university, marking another milestone in her remarkable career. Although she held the post of head of the department until 1955, after 1944 her status as a "credible" scientist was called into question because of her "bourgeois background" and her links with scientists behind the Iron Curtain.</p> <p>Elizaveta Karamihailova was:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first woman nuclear physicist in Bulgaria 2. The head of the Department of Atomic Physics at the Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski" 3. An associate professor of experimental atomic physics at Sofia University

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The first woman professor in the country 5. All the above [Correct] <p>While studying at the University of Vienna, Elizaveta Karamihailova researched:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. uranium 2. radio signals transmission 3. gamma rays and polonium [Correct] <p>The Bulgarian Academy of Sciences treated Elizaveta as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A non-credible scientist [Correct] 2. A renowned scientist in her field 3. A bourgeois
3	Konstantsa Lyapcheva's Home	<p>Konstantsa Lyapcheva (1887-1944) was a socialite who engaged in charity work for underprivileged children (refugees, orphans, etc.).</p> <p>During the Balkan Wars (1912-1913), as a Sister of Charity, she helped wounded soldiers and refugees, and in peacetime she became a protector of the Bulgarian children. For her humanitarian deeds she was awarded the Grand Cross of the Bulgarian Red Cross and the Ladies' Order of Civil Merit of Tsar Boris III.</p> <p>In the 1930s, Konstantsa became the first woman to actively engage in issues such as human trafficking, domestic violence, and child protection. Until the very end, she was president of the Union for the Protection of Children in Bulgaria. She was a member of almost all other charities in Sofia, in many of them as part of the governing body. There was no area of social welfare in which she was not involved. Thanks to Konstantsa, the activities of raising and educating children received legislative protection, and motherhood was recognized as an extremely important social function. It was her own initiative that 1 June was celebrated as Children's Day for the first time in 1927. She founded the country's first shelters for children in distress, training centers for social workers, summer camps and playgrounds.</p> <p>Konstantsa Lyapcheva was actively engaged with the following topic:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Human trafficking 2. Domestic violence 3. Child protection 4. All the above [Correct]

		<p>Which awards did Konstantsa Lyapcheva receive throughout her lifetime?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Grand Cross of the Bulgarian Red Cross [Correct] 2. Nobel Peace Prize 3. Ladies' Order of Civil Merit of Tsar Boris III [Correct] 4. All the above
4	National Assembly of the Republic of Bulgaria	<p>On January 15, 1938, Bulgarian women were granted the legal right to vote, the culmination of a long and complex journey towards women's suffrage in the country. The first step was taken in 1909 with the passing of the National Education Act, which for the first time granted women the right to serve on school boards, although they were not allowed to participate in elections. This formal and limited concession failed to produce tangible results, as men continued to favor predominantly male candidates for positions on the boards, keeping women away from the polls.</p> <p>In 1937, a partial victory was achieved when "women mothers by lawful marriage" were allowed to vote in local elections, although they remained ineligible to run. Eventually, on 15 January 1938, Bulgarian women gained the legal right to vote in parliamentary elections, albeit limited to women over 21 who were married, divorced or widowed. This restriction was open and clear - it excluded young, educated and free women, many of whom were studying abroad or had established themselves as intellectuals, from the electoral process. It was not until 1944 that women in Bulgaria received equal voting rights, and in 1945, during the 26th session of the National Assembly, the first 16 women were elected as deputies. After the elections to the 49th National Assembly, the 57 women included in it accounted for only 23.8% representation. According to the Inter-Parliamentary Union, the average percentage of women's representation in parliament worldwide is 26.5%, and in the same ranking, Bulgaria ranks 97th for women's participation in parliament.</p> <p>When were Bulgarian women granted equal voting rights?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1944 [Correct] 2. 1945 3. 1937

		<p>From 15 January 1938 onwards which Bulgarian women gained the legal right to vote in parliamentary elections?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Women over 21 who were married, divorced or widowed [Correct] 2. Women over 18 who were mothers 3. Women with a University degree <p>How many women were elected as deputies during the 26th session of the National Assembly?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 3 2. 16 [Correct] 3. 38
5	<p>First Sofia State Girls High School (now, 7th Secondary School "Sveti Sedmochiselnitsi") & Anastasia Golovina's Workplace</p>	<p>7 Secondary School "St. Sedmochislenitsi" was originally founded in 1879 by a special decree of the Minister of Education Marin Drinov as the First Sofia State Girls' High School. The history of girls' secondary education in Bulgaria began here. In 1882-1883, with the opening of a special pedagogical class, the gymnasium reached its full development. Designed by Mara Zaharieva, herself a graduate of the high school and one of the first female architects in the country, it managed to incorporate many of the European architectural examples of the era.</p> <p>Dr. Anastasia Golovina (1850 - 1933) worked at the First Sofia State Girls' High School as a doctor. She was the first Bulgarian doctor to graduate with a doctorate and the first Bulgarian female doctor.</p> <p>In 1879 Anastasia was the first Bulgarian woman with a university degree and the first Bulgarian woman doctor.</p> <p>Her innovations in Bulgaria related to the autopsy of the deceased to specify and confirm the cause of death. Anastasia was among the founders of the Physico-medical Society, the first association of physicians in Bulgaria. She took part in the Balkan wars and World War I as a doctor in Varna.</p> <p>Later, Anastasia became the first Bulgarian psychiatrist and one of the founders of Bulgarian balneotherapy and physiotherapy, introducing walks for the patients outside the psychiatric ward and improving the conditions of stay.</p> <p>Who was the architect of the First Sofia Girls' High School building?</p>

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Elena Markova-Bosilkova 2. Mara Zaharieva [Correct] 3. Elisaveta Konsolova-Vazova <p>Famous graduates of First Sofia Girls' High School are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Elizaveta Karamihailova and Mara Zaharieva 2. Yana Yazova and Elizaveta Bagryana 3. Stoyanka Mutafova and Blaga Dimitrova 4. All the above [Correct] <p>Dr. Anastasia Golovina became:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first Bulgarian doctor to graduate with a doctorate 2. The first Bulgarian female doctor 3. One of the first 6 women graduates of the Faculty of Medicine in Paris 4. The first Bulgarian psychiatrist 5. All the above [Correct] <p>Which wars did Anastasia take part in as a medic?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. World War I [Correct] 2. World War II 3. Balkan wars [Correct] <p>Throughout her life Dr. Anastasia Golovina introduced the following medical innovations in Bulgaria:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Balneotherapy and physiotherapy 2. Autopsy of the deceased to specify and confirm the cause of death 3. Walks for the patients outside the psychiatric ward 4. All the above [Correct]
6	Ekaterina Karavelova's Grave	<p>Ekaterina Karavelova (1860-1947) was a famous educator, translator, writer, publicist, suffragist and women's rights activist. She also played an active role in protecting Bulgaria's Jewish population from deportation to concentration camps during World War II. Ekaterina became the long-time president of the Union of Bulgarian Women Writers, which she initiated, and represented Bulgaria at the Fourth Congress of the International Women's League for Peace and Freedom in 1924 in Washington, DC.</p> <p>What is Ekaterina Karavelova famous for:</p>

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It was her own initiative that 1 June was celebrated as Children's Day for the first time in 1927 2. She played an active role in protecting Bulgaria's Jewish population from deportation to concentration camps during World War II [Correct] 3. She was nominated 3 times for a Nobel Prize in Literature 4. All the above
7	Ekaterina Karavelova's Memorial plaque	<p>She was the founder of the cultural women's organization "Maika" and its chairwoman in 1899-1929. Active as a teacher, Ekaterina took an early part in the debate on women's education and the status of teachers.</p> <p>Ekaterina Karavelova was:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. One of the founders of the Bulgarian Women's Union in 1901 2. A long-time president of the Union of Bulgarian Women Writers 3. An educator, translator, writer, publicist, suffragist and women's rights activist 4. All the above [Correct]
8	Elisaveta Bagryana's Memorial plaque	<p>Elisaveta Bagryana (1893-1991) was a prominent Bulgarian poet who lived most of her life in Sofia. She is regarded as one of the most significant Bulgarian poets, often referred to as 'the first lady of Bulgarian women's literature'. Known both for her lyrics and for her unconventional views on the role of women in society, the poet was an active figure in literary and social life in Bulgaria in the 1920s. Elisaveta was nominated three times for the Nobel Prize in Literature and made a significant contribution to the country's literary heritage.</p> <p>Somewhat arguing for her unconventional behaviour, she confronted the idea of women according to patriarchal norms and interpreted the problem of freedom of choice and the will of a person to assert herself in a different way. Other leading themes in Bagryana's work are love, travel, loneliness and memories.</p> <p>Elisaveta Bagryana was:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nominated three times for the Nobel Prize in Literature [Correct]

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Often referred to as 'the best among all Bulgarian women poets' 3. A renowned translator who knew 7 languages <p>Elisaveta's works revolve around the central topics of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. confronting the idea of women according to patriarchal norms 2. the problem of freedom of choice and the will of a person 3. love, travel, loneliness and memories 4. All the above [Correct]
9	Yana Yazova's Memorial plaque	<p>Yana Yazova (1912-1974) was a 20th century writer and intellectual. Her poetry has been translated into Esperanto, Czech, Serbian and Ukrainian. She traveled widely in Europe and the Middle East and wrote about her travels.</p> <p>After the communist regime she was not printed, published or invited to literary readings. In almost complete solitude, she created the trilogy "Balkans", including the novels "Levski", "Benkovski" and "Shipka" - a colossal work for which she spent years in libraries and archives, wandering in monasteries. Her historical novel "Alexander the Great", the trilogy "Balkans" and the anti-communist novel "The Salt Bay" were published after her death.</p> <p>Yana Yazova did the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Devoted years of her life in almost complete solitude to create the trilogy "Balkans" [Correct] 2. Traveled widely in Europe and the Middle East and wrote about her travels [Correct] 3. Was published in various magazines: "The Woman's Herald", "Lyk", "Contemporary", "Zlatorog", "Izkustvo" 4. All the above
10	Bulgarian Womens' Union building and Anna Karima's workplace	<p>The Bulgarian Women's Union was a women's rights organization, active in Bulgaria from 1901 to 1944. In 1901 the association was founded by Vela Blagoeva, Ekaterina Karavelova, Anna Karima, Kina Konova, Julia Malinova and Zheni Pateva. The organization united the 27 local women's associations established in Bulgaria since 1878. It was founded in response to restrictions on women's education and access to university studies in the 1890s.</p> <p>Anna Karima (1871-1949) was a writer, translator, editor and journalist, suffragist and women's rights</p>

		<p>activist. In 1897 she founded the Women's Educational Association "Consciousness", through which Anna, with her persistent letters to the government, managed to convince it in 1901 to allow women to study at university. Anna became the first president of the Bulgarian Women's Union and organized the first congress of feminist organizations.</p> <p>Throughout her life, she was constantly engaged in translating and writing her own material, all of it devoted to women's issues - from the education of children to opposition to arranged marriages, to the free expression of emotions - her works challenged the traditional notions of the time, combating stereotypes and influencing attitudes towards women.</p> <p>The Bulgarian Women's Union:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. was founded by Vela Blagoeva, Ekaterina Karavelova, Anna Karima 2. united the 27 local women's associations 3. was active in Bulgaria from 1901 to 1944 4. All the above [Correct] <p>Why was The Bulgarian Women's Union founded:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To establish a matriarchy in Bulgaria 2. To support women in their professional fulfillment 3. To fight the restrictions on women's education and access to university studies in the 1890s [Correct] <p>Whose letters managed to convince the government in 1901 to allow women to study at university?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ekaterina Karavelova's 2. Anna Karima's [Correct] 3. Konstantsa Lyapcheva's 4. All the above <p>Anna Karima became:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A writer, translator, editor and journalist, suffragist and women's rights activist [Correct] 2. The first president of the Bulgarian Women's Union [Correct] 3. The first woman to graduate from Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" 4. All the above
--	--	--

		<p>The works of Anna Karima were devoted to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The education of children [Correct] 2. The approval of arranged marriages 3. Combating stereotypes and influencing attitudes towards women [Correct] 4. All the above
11	Teodora Peykova's Workplace	<p>Teodora Peykova (1892-1972) was a writer, editor and social activist, founder of the women's magazine Economy and Household, which was published for 25 years. Through the magazine, Teodora spread European tendencies and ideas throughout the country and used it to introduce women to various social problems or inventions made by other women, to offer recipes and medical advice, weight-loss diets, press reviews, family advice, child-rearing tips, fashion, historical events, gymnastics, reports from Paris and other cities, advertisements, sewing, embroidery, needlework courses, and more.</p> <p>She also became the first Bulgarian woman to teach herself to drive her husband's car. During socialism, the Economy and Household magazine was declared bourgeois and banned, the complicated and beautiful European dishes and eating habits were replaced by simple and "folk" ones, and Teodora Peykova sank into oblivion.</p> <p>What materials and topics were included in Economy and Household magazine?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical literature regarding cheap household repairs 2. Poetry written by women 3. Inventions made by women [Correct] 4. All the above <p>Teodora Peykova became:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The founder of the women's magazine Economy and Household 2. A writer, editor and social activist 3. The first Bulgarian woman to teach herself to drive 4. All the above [Correct]
12	Mara Belcheva's Home	<p>Mara Belcheva (1868-1937) was a poet, teacher, translator and philologist. She published three collections of poetry, Steps on the Threshold, 1918, Sonnets, 1926, and Selected Songs, 1931. In 1925, Mara</p>

		<p>published a biography of her late partner, the poet Pencho Slaveykov. She also translated Friedrich Nietzsche's Thus Spake Zarathustra and Gerhart Hauptmann's Die versunkene Glocke into Bulgarian.</p> <p>Mara Belcheva translated:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Her late partner, the poet Pencho Slaveykov's works into German 2. Friedrich Nietzsche's Thus Spake Zarathustra into Bulgarian [Correct] 3. Gerhart Hauptmann's Die versunkene Glocke into Bulgarian [Correct] 4. All the above
13	Dimitrana Ivanova's Home	<p>Dimitrana Ivanova (1881-1960) was a Bulgarian educational reformer, suffragist and women's rights activist. She was president of the Bulgarian Women's Union from 1926 to 1944. From 1928 she published and edited the monthly magazine "The Woman" (1929-1931), which dealt with the legal aspects of women's subordinate position. Dimitrana collaborated with many newspapers on issues related to women's lives and futures.</p> <p>Throughout her life she fought for gender equality in education, and for the right of women lawyers to practice their profession as lawyers and judges. After a long struggle, she became one of the first Bulgarian women to have this right recognized. Dimitrana's big dream is that Bulgarian women should have the right to vote and be equal in different spheres of life. Thanks to many years of activism and with the help of Queen Joanna, a new electoral law was promulgated in January 1938, partially guaranteeing this right to married, divorced or widowed women.</p> <p>Dimitrana Ivanova was:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The president of the Bulgarian Women's Union from 1926 to 1944 [Correct] 2. The first president of the Bulgarian Women's Union 3. The founder of the women's magazine Economy and Household <p>What did Dimitrana fight for throughout her life?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Equal voting rights for Bulgarian women 2. Gender equality in education 3. The right of women lawyers to practice their profession

		4. All the above [Correct]
--	--	-----------------------------------

In Bulgarian

Град, държава: София, България		
Начална точка: Софийски университет „Св. Климент Охридски“		
Номер	Място за търсене на съкровища	Тест
1	Софийски университет "Свети Климент Охридски"	<p>Софийският университет "Свети Климент Охридски" е държавен изследователски университет в София, България. Учебните занятия започват скромно и без шум на 1 октомври 1888 г.</p> <p>В началото студентите са 43, само мъже. Първите жени са приети след дългогодишни петиции до Народното събрание, през 1901 г. Така България става сред първите страни в света, в които жените са допуснати до университетско образование. По този начин занапред значително се увеличава потенциалът на нацията за реализиране на научни иновации и нововъведения и въобще за развитието на българската наука.</p> <p>През коя година жените започват да посещават университети в България?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1901 [Правилно] 1888 1903 <p>Софийският университет „Свети Климент Охридски“ е:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Най-голямото висше учебно заведение в България Най-старото висше учебно заведение в България [Правилно] Най-модерното висше учебно заведение в България Всичко изброено
2	Мемориалната плоча на Елисавета Карамихайлова	<p>Елисавета Карамихайлова (1897-1968) е първата жена ядрен физик в България. Тя създава първите практически курсове по физика на елементарните частици и става първата жена с професорска титла в страната.</p> <p>През 1917 г. тя заминава за Виена, за да учи</p>

		<p>електротехника и радиотехника във Виенския университет. Нейните изследвания върху гама лъчите и полония са актуални и до днес и се смятат за значителен напредък в съвременната физика.</p> <p>Елисавета се дипломира като доктор по физика и математика във Виена. Успехът ѝ я мотивира да се върне в България, за да даде своя принос към научната общност. Тя превръща кабинета си в лаборатория, за да осигури на учениците си практическо обучение чрез съвременни научни методи. През 1939 г., след дългогодишни усилия, тя най-накрая е назначена за редовен доцент по експериментална атомна физика в Софийския университет.</p> <p>През 1945 г. Елисавета става ръководител на новосъздадената катедра по атомна физика в университета, което бележи още един етап в нейната забележителна кариера. Въпреки че заема длъжността ръководител на катедрата до 1955 г., след 1944 г. статутът ѝ на "надежден" учен е поставен под съмнение поради "буржоазния ѝ произход" и връзките ѝ с учени отвъд Желязната завеса.</p> <p>Елисавета Карамихайлова е:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Първата жена ядрен физик в България 2. Ръководител на Катедрата по атомна физика в Софийския университет „Свети Климент Охридски“ 3. Доцент по експериментална атомна физика в Софийския университет 4. Първата жена професор в страната 5. Всичко изброено [Правилно] <p>По време на следването си във Виенския университет Елисавета Карамихайлова прави изследвания в областта на:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. урана 2. предаването на радиосигнали 3. гама-лъчите и полония [Правилно] <p>Българската академия на науките третира Елисавета като:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ненадежден учен [Правилно] 2. Известен учен в своята област
--	--	--

		3. Буржоа
3	Домът на Констанца Ляпчева	<p>Констанца Ляпчева (1887-1944) е светска дама, която се занимава с благотворителност за деца в неравностойно положение (бежанци, сираци и др.). По време на Балканските войни (1912-1913г.) като милосърдна сестра тя помага на ранените войници и на бежанците, а в мирно време се превръща в закрилница на българските деца. За човеколюбивите си дела бива наградена с “Голям кръст” на Българския червен кръст и с Дамския орден за гражданска заслуга на цар Борис Трети. През 30-те години на XX век Констанца става първата жена, която активно се ангажира с проблеми като трафика на хора, домашното насилие, закрилата на децата. До самия си край тя е председател на Съюза за закрила на децата в България. Била е член на почти всички останали благотворителни организации в София, в много от тях - като част от ръководния орган. Няма област на социалното подпомагане, в която да не е участвала. Благодарение на Констанца дейностите по отглеждането и възпитанието на децата получават законодателна защита, а майчинството става признато за изключително важна социална функция. По инициатива на Констанца през 1927 г. 1 юни за първи път се чества като Ден на детето. Тя основава първите приюти за деца в беда в страната, центрове за обучение на социални работници, летни лагери и детски площадки.</p> <p>Констанца Ляпчева участва активно в следните сфери:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Трафик на хора 2. Домашно насилие 3. Закрила на детето 4. Всичко изброено [Правилно] <p>Кои награди е получила Констанца Ляпчева през живота си?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Голям кръст на Българския червен кръст [Правилно] 2. Нобелова награда за мир 3. Дамски орден за граждански заслуги на цар Борис III [Правилно] 4. Всичко изброено
4	Български парламент	На 15 януари 1938 г. българските жени получават законното право да гласуват, което е кулминацията

		<p>на един продължителен и сложен път към изборителното право на жените в страната. За съжаление, това право е ограничено само до жени над 21 години, които са омъжени, разведени или вдовици.</p> <p>Едва през 1944 г. жените в България получават равни изборителни права, а през 1945 г., по време на 26-ата сесия на Народното събрание, първите 16 жени са избрани за депутати. След изборите за 49 Народно събрание, включените в него 57 жени в съставляват едва 23,8% представителство. По данни на Интерпаламентарния съюз средният процент за представителството на жените в парламента по света е 26,5%, а в същата класация България е на 97-мо място по участие на жени в парламента.</p> <p>Кога българските жени получават равни изборителни права?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1944 [Правилно] 2. 1945 3. 1937 <p>От 15 януари 1938 г. кои български жени получават законно право да гласуват на парламентарни избори?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Жени над 21 години, които са били омъжени, разведени или вдовици [Правилно] 2. Жени над 18 години, които са майки 3. Жени с висше образование <p>Колко жени са избрани за депутати по време на 26-ата сесия на Народното събрание?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 3 2. 16 [Правилно] 3. 38
5	<p>Първа софийска девическа гимназия (сега 7. СУ "Св. Седмочисленици") и работно място на Анастасия Головина</p>	<p>7 СУ "Свети Седмочисленици" е основано през 1879 г. със специален указ на министъра на просветата Марин Дринов като Първа софийска девическа гимназия. Оттук започва историята на девическото средно образование в България.</p> <p>Д-р Анастасия Головина (1850 - 1933) работи в Първа девическа гимназия като лекар. Тя е първият български лекар, който завършва образованието си с докторска степен, и първата българска лекарка. Нейни са нововъведенията в България, свързани с аутопсията на починалия, за да се уточни и потвърди причината за смъртта. По-късно Анастасия става първия български психиатър и един от основателите</p>

		<p>на българската курортна медицина и физиотерапия като въвежда разходките на болните извън психиатричното отделение и подобрява условията за престой.</p> <p>Кой е архитектът на сградата на Първа софийска девическа гимназия?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Елена Маркова-Босилкова 2. Мара Захариева [Правилно] 3. Елисавета Консулова-Вазова <p>Известни възпитанички на Първа софийска девическа гимназия са:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Елисавета Карамихайлова и Мара Захариева 2. Яна Язова и Елисавета Багряна 3. Стоянка Мутафова и Блага Димитрова 4. Всичко изброено [Правилно] <p>Д-р Анастасия Головина става:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Първият български лекар, който се дипломира с докторска степен 2. Първата българска лекарка 3. Една от първите 6 жени, завършили Медицинския факултет в Париж 4. Първият български психиатър 5. Всичко изброено [Правилно] <p>В кои войни Анастасия участва като медик?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Първата световна война [Правилно] 2. Втората световна война 3. Балканските войни [Правилно] <p>През живота си д-р Анастасия Головина въвежда следните медицински иновации в България:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Балнеотерапия и физиотерапия 2. Аутопсия на починалия за уточняване и потвърждаване на причината за смъртта 3. Разходки за пациентите извън психиатричното отделение 4. Всичко изброено [Правилно]
6	Гробът на Екатерина Каравелова	<p>Екатерина Каравелова (1860-1947) е известна педагожка, преводачка, писателка, публицистка, суфражистка и активистка за правата на жените. Тя също така има активна роля в защитата на еврейското население на България от депортиране в концентрационни лагери по време на Втората световна война. Екатерина става дългогодишен</p>

		<p>председател на създадения по нейна инициатива Съюз на българските писателки и представлява България на Четвъртия конгрес на Международната женска лига за мир и свобода през 1924 г. във Вашингтон, САЩ.</p> <p>С какво е известна Екатерина Карavelова:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. По нейна инициатива през 1927 г. 1 юни за първи път е отбелязан като Ден на детето 2. Имала е активна роля в защитата на еврейското население на България от депортиране в концентрационни лагери по време на Втората световна война [Правилно] 3. Три пъти е номинирана за Нобелова награда за литература 4. Всичко изброено
7	Мемориалната плоча на Екатерина Карavelова	<p>Екатерина е една от основателките на Българския женски съюз през 1901 г. и негова председателка от 1915 до 1925 г. Убедена, че независимостта и равноправието на жените изискват те да могат да изкарват сами прехраната си, тя твърдо подкрепя тяхното професионално обучение.</p> <p>Екатерина Карavelова е била:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Една от основателките на Българския женски съюз през 1901 г. 2. Дългогодишен председател на Съюза на българските писателки 3. Педагог, преводач, писател, публицист, суфражист и борец за правата на жените 4. Всичко изброено [Правилно]
8	Мемориалната плоча на Елисавета Багряна	<p>Елисавета Багряна (1893-1991) е изтъкната българска поетеса, която през по-голямата част от живота си живее в София. Смятана е за една от най-значимите български поетеси, често наричана "първата дама на българската женска литература". Елисавета е номинирана три пъти за Нобелова награда за литература и има съществен принос към литературното наследство на страната.</p> <p>Елисавета Багряна е:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Номинирана три пъти за Нобелова награда за литература [Правилно] 2. Често наричана „най-добрата сред българските поетеси“. 3. Известен преводач, владеещ 7 езика

		<p>Творбите на Елисавета са свързани с централните теми за:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Противопоставянето на представата за жената според патриархалните норми 2. Проблемът за свободата на избора и волята на човека 3. Любовта, пътуването, самотата и спомените 4. Всичко изброено [Правилно]
9	Мемориалната плоча на Яна Язова	<p>Яна Язова (1912-1974) е писателка и интелектуалка от XX век. Поезията ѝ е преведена на есперанто, чешки, сръбски и украински език. След настъпването на комунистическия режим не я печатат, не я издават, не я канят на литературни четения. В почти пълна самота, тя създава трилогията “Балкани”, включваща романите “Левски”, “Бенковски” и “Шипка” – колосален труд, заради който години наред прекарва в библиотеки, архиви и манастири.</p> <p>Яна Язова е извършила следното:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Посветила е години от живота си в почти пълна самота, за да създаде трилогията „Балкани“ [Правилно] 2. Пътувала е много из Европа и Близкия изток и е писала за пътванията си [Правилно] 3. Публикувала е свои произведения в различни списания: „Вестник на жената“, „Лик“, „Съвременник“, „Златорог“, „Изкуство“ 4. Всичко изброено
10	Сградата на Българския женски съюз и работното място на Анна Карима	<p>Българският женски съюз е организация за защита на правата на жените, която действа в България от 1901 до 1944 г. През 1901 г. сдружението е основано от Вела Благоева, Екатерина Каравелова, Анна Карима, Кина Конова, Юлия Малинова и Жени Патева. Организацията обединява общо 27-те местни женски асоциации, създадени в България от 1878 г. насам. Основана е в отговор на ограниченията за образованието на жените и достъпа им до университетско обучение през 90-те години на XIX век.</p> <p>Анна Карима (1871-1949) е писателка, преводачка, редакторка и журналистка, суфражистка и активистка за правата на жените. През 1897 г. тя основава Женското образователно сдружение "Съзнание", чрез което Анна с постоянните си писма</p>

	<p>до правителството успява да го убеди през 1901 г. да разреши на жените да учат в университет. Анна става първата председателка на Българския женски съюз и организира първия конгрес на феминистките организации. През целия си живот тя непрекъснато се занимава с преводи и писане на собствени материали, всички те посветени на женски теми - от образованието на децата, през противопоставянето на уредените бракове, до свободното изразяване на емоциите - нейните произведения предизвикват традиционните за онова време разбирания, борят се със стереотипите и влияят върху отношението към жените.</p> <p>Българският женски съюз:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. е основан от Вела Благоева, Екатерина Каравелова, Анна Карима 2. обединявал 27-те местни женски сдружения 3. е действал в България от 1901 до 1944 г. 4. Всичко изброено по-горе [Правилно] <p>Защо е основан Българският женски съюз:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. За да установи матриархат в България 2. За да подкрепи жените в професионалната им реализация 3. За да се бори срещу ограниченията върху образованието на жените и достъпа им до университетско обучение през 90-те години на XIX в. [Правилно] <p>Чи писма успяват да убедят правителството през 1901 г. да разреши на жените да учат в университет?</p> <p>Екатерина Каравелова</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Анна Карима [Правилно] 2. Констанца Ляпчева 3. Всичко изброено <p>Анна Карима става:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Писателка, преводачка, редакторка и журналистка, суфражистка и активистка за правата на жените [Правилно] 2. Първата председателка на Българския женски съюз [Правилно] 3. Първата жена, завършила Софийския университет „Свети Климент Охридски“ 4. Всичко изброено <p>Творчеството на Анна Карима е посветено на:</p>
--	--

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Образованието на децата [Правилно] 2. Одобряването на уговорените бракове 3. Борба със стереотипите и влияние върху отношението към жените [Правилно] 4. Всичко изброено
11	Работното място на Теодора Пейкова	<p>Теодора Пейкова (1892-1972) е писателка, редакторка и обществена деятелка, основателка на дамското списание "Икономия и домакинство", което излиза в продължение на 25 години. Чрез списанието Теодора разпространява европейския вкус и идеи в цялата страна и го използва, за да запознава жените с различни социални проблеми или изобретения, направени от други жени, да предлага рецепти и медицински съвети, диети за отслабване, преглед на пресата, семейни съвети, съвети за отглеждане на деца, мода, исторически събития, гимнастика, репортажи от Париж и други градове, реклами, курсове по шиене, бродерии, ръкоделие и др. Тя става и първата българка, която сама се научава да кара колата на съпруга си. По времето на социализма списание "Икономия и домакинство" е обявено за буржоазно и е забранено, сложните и красиви европейски ястия и навици за хранене са заменени с прости и "народни" такива, а Теодора Пейкова потъва в забрава.</p> <p>Какви материали и теми са включени в списание „Икономика и домакинство“?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Техническа литература за евтини ремонти в домакинството 2. Поезия, писана от жени 3. Изобретения на жени [Правилно] 4. Всичко изброено <p>Теодора Пейкова става:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Основателка на женското списание „Икономика и домакинство“ 2. Писателка, редакторка и социална активистка 3. Първата българка, която сама се научава да шофира 4. Всичко изброено [Правилно]
12	Домът на Мара Белчева	<p>Мара Белчева (1868-1937) е поетеса, учителка, преводачка и филоложка. Публикува три стихосбирки: "Стъпки на прага", 1918 г., "Сонети", 1926 г., и "Избрани песни", 1931 г. През 1925 г. Мара</p>

		<p>публикува биография на покойния си партньор, поета Пенчо Славейков. Тя превежда на български език и "Тъй рече Заратустра" на Фридрих Ницше и "Die versunkene Glocke" на Герхарт Хауптман.</p> <p>Мара Белчева превежда:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Творби на покойния си партньор, поета Пенчо Славейков, на немски език 2. „Тъй рече Заратустра“ на Фридрих Ницше на български [Правилно] 3. Die versunkene Glocke на Герхарт Хауптман на български [Правилно] 4. Всичко изброено
13	Домът на Димитрана Иванова	<p>Димитрана Иванова (1881-1960) е българска реформаторка в областта на образованието, суфражистка и активистка за правата на жените. Тя е председател на Българския женски съюз от 1926 до 1944 г. От 1928 г. издава и редактира месечното списание "Жената" (1929 - 1931), в което разглежда правните аспекти на подчиненото положение на жените. Димитрана сътрудничи на много вестници по въпроси, свързани с живота и бъдещето на жените. През целия си живот тя се бори за равенство между половете в областта на образованието, както и за правото на жените юристи да упражняват професията си на адвокати и съдии. След дълга борба тя става една от първите българки, на които това право е признато. Голямата мечта на Димитрана е българските жени да имат правото да гласуват и да са равноправни в различните сфери на живота. Благодарение на дълги години активна дейност и с помощта на царица Йоана, през януари 1938 е обнародван нов изборителен закон, частично гарантиращ това право на омъжени, разведени или вдовици.</p> <p>Димитрана Иванова е била:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Председател на Българския женски съюз от 1926 до 1944 г. [Правилно] 2. Първата председателка на Българския женски съюз 3. Основателка на женското списание „Икономика и домакинство“ <p>За какво се е борила Димитрана през живота си?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Равни изборителни права за българските жени

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Равенство между половете в образованието 3. Правото на жените юристи да упражняват професията си 4. Всичко изброено [Правилно]
--	--	--

3.6. Velenje, Slovenia

In English

City, Country: Velenje, Slovenia		
Start point: Miner's statue at Titov trg or Museum of Mining Velenje		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	Miner's statue at Titov trg	<p>What role does the fictional miner's wife represent in the mining communities of Velenje?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Political leader 2. Household manager [Correct] 3. School teacher 4. Nurse <p>What qualities does the statue of the miner's wife symbolize in the mining community?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strength and resilience [Correct] 2. Wealth and luxury 3. Independence and adventure and culture
2	Library Velenje	<p>What is Jelka Reichman best known for?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sculptures 2. Children's book illustrations [Correct] 3. Abstract paintings 4. Photography <p>Which of these books was illustrated by Jelka Reichman?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "Harry Potter" 2. "The Seamstress and the Scissors" [Correct] 3. "Lord of the Rings" 4. "The Great Gatsby"

3	Rod Jezerski zmaj (or red hall Velenje)	<p>What major contribution did Herma Groznik make to the schools in Velenje?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introducing modern technology 2. Integrating scouting into primary schools [Correct] 3. Establishing art programs 4. Organizing international exchanges <p>What award did Herma Groznik receive for her community contributions in 2005?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nobel Prize 2. Coat of arms of the Municipality of Velenje [Correct] 3. National Teacher Award 4. Scout of the Year
4	Velenje Health Centre/Ljudska univerza Velenje	<p>In which year did Urška Stropnik Šonc publish her first book illustration?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1995 2. 1997 [Correct] 3. 1999 4. 2001 <p>For which of the following institutions did Urška Stropnik Šonc create illustrations for a children's guide?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. National Gallery of Slovenia 2. Slovenian Museum of Natural History 3. Museum of Contemporary Art Ljubljana 4. Maribor Regional Museum [Correct]
5	Municipality Šoštanj	<p>What profession did Antonija Sternad pioneer in Šoštanj?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Doctor 2. Midwife [Correct] 3. Teacher 4. Engineer <p>Approximately how many babies did Antonija Sternad help deliver during her career?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 500-1000 2. 1000-2000 3. 2000-3000 4. 3000-4000 [Correct]

6	Alma Karlin statue in city Celje	<p>What was Alma Karlin renowned for?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Painting 2. Writing and traveling [Correct] 3. Political activism 4. Teaching <p>Which of the following books was written by Alma Karlin?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "In the Land of Silent" [Correct] 2. "To Kill a Mockingbird" 3. "War and Peace" 4. "1984"
7	Castle in city Celje or Celje Library	<p>Who was Barbara of Celje married to?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. King Władysław II of Poland 2. King Sigismund of Hungary [Correct] 3. Emperor Charles V 4. King Henry VIII <p>In which year did Barbara of Celje marry King Sigismund of Hungary?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1392 2. 1401 3. 1405 [Correct] 4. 1410

In Slovenian

City, Country: Velenje, Slovenija		
Start point: Kip rudarjeve žene na Titovem trgu ali Muzej rudnika Velenje		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	Kip rudarjeve žene na Titovem trgu	<p>Kakšno vlogo predstavlja fiktivna rudarska žena v velenjskih rudarskih skupnostih?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Politični vodja 2. Gospodinja [Pravilno] 3. Učiteljica v šoli 4. Medicinska sestra <p>Katere lastnosti simbolizira kip rudarjeve žene v rudarski skupnosti?</p>

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Moč in odpornost [Pravilno] 2. Bogastvo in razkošje 3. Neodvisnost in pustolovščina 4. D. Umetnost in kultura
2	Knjižnica Velenje	<p>Po čem je najbolj znana Jelka Reichman?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Skulpture 2. Ilustracije otroških knjig [Pravilno] 3. Abstraktne slike 4. Fotografije <p>Katero od naslednjih knjig je ilustrirala Jelka Reichman?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. „Harry Potter“ 2. "Šivilja in škarje " [Pravilno] 3. „Gospodar prstanov“ 4. „Veliki Gatsby“
3	Rod Jezerski zmaj (ali Rdeča dvorana Velenje)	<p>Kaj je Herma Groznik največ prispevala k razvoju šolstva v Velenju?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Uvajanje sodobne tehnologije 2. Vključevanje taborništva v osnovne šole [Pravilno] 3. Vzpostavitev umetniških programov 4. Organiziranje mednarodnih izmenjav <p>Katero nagrado je Herma Groznik prejela leta 2005 za svoj prispevek k skupnosti?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nobelova nagrada 2. Grb Mestne občine Velenje [Pravilno] 3. Nacionalna nagrada za učitelje 4. Tabornik leta
4	Zdravstveni dom Velenje/Ljudska univerza Velenje	<p>V katerem letu je Urška Stropnik Šonc objavila svojo prvo knjižno ilustracijo?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1995 2. 1997 [Pravilno] 3. 1999 4. 2001 <p>Za katero od naslednjih ustanov je Urška Stropnik Šonc ustvarila ilustracije za otroški vodnik?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Narodna galerija Slovenije 2. Prirodoslovni muzej Slovenije 3. Muzej sodobne umetnosti Ljubljana 4. Pokrajinski muzej Maribor [Pravilno]

5	Občina Šoštanj	<p>Kakšen poklic je opravljala Antonija Sternad v Šoštanju?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Doktor 2. Babica [Pravilno] 3. Učiteljica 4. Inženirka <p>Približno koliko otrok je Antonija Sternad v svoji karieri pomagala roditi?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 500-1000 2. 1000-2000 3. 2000-3000 4. 3000-4000 [Pravilno]
6	Kip Alme Karlin v Celju	<p>Po čem je slovela Alma Karlin?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Slikanje 2. Pisanje in potovanje [Pravilni odgovor] 3. Politični aktivizem 4. Poučevanje <p>Katero od naslednjih knjig je napisala Alma Karlin?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. „V deželi tišine“ [Pravilni odgovor] 2. „Ubiti ptiča“ 3. „Vojna in mir“ 4. „1984“
7	Celjski grad ali celjska knjižnica	<p>S kom je bila poročena Barbara Celjska?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Poljski kralj Vladislav II. 2. madžarski kralj Sigismund [Pravilni odgovor] 3. cesar Karel V. 4. kralj Henrik VIII. <p>Katerega leta se je Barbara Celjska poročila z ogrskim kraljem Sigismundom?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1392 2. 1401 3. 1405 [Pravilni odgovor] 4. 1410

3.7. Vilnius, Lithuania

In English

City, Country: Vilnius, Lithuania		
Start point: Lukiškės Square		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1.	Museum of Occupations and Freedom Fights	<p>What was Adele's profession?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lawyer 2. Teacher [Correct] 3. Doctor
2.	Žemaitė square	<p>Which group of women did Žemaitė support in her life and writings?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Peasant women [Correct] 2. Women factory workers 3. Elderly single women
3.	A. Vienuolio st. 12	<p>Listen to the song performed by Grincevičiūtė. Who treated the sick mosquito in the song?</p> <p>Link extra: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ko13T98-6iM&ab_channel=Muzikama%C5%BEEiausiams</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Frogs 2. Children 3. Flies [Correct]
4.	Gediminas ave. 13	<p>Felicija never became a president. However, in 2009 Lithuanians elected first ever woman president. What is her name?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vilija Blinkevičiūtė 2. Kazimiera Prunskienė 3. Dalia Grybauskaitė [Correct]
5.	Kudirka square	<p>When was Eliza Orzeszkowa nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature first time?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1905 [Correct] 2. 1900 3. 1911

6.	Gedimino ave. 12	How old was Aleksandra when she photographed the Council of Lithuania in this studio in 1917? She was born in 1895. Estimate number answer option: 22 [Correct]
----	------------------	--

In Lithuanian

City, Country: Vilnius, Lietuva		
Start point: Lukiškių aikštė		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1.	Okupacijų ir laisvės kovų muziejus	Kokia buvo Adelės profesija? 1. Teisininkė 2. Mokytoja [Correct] 3. Daktarė
2.	Žemaitės skveras	Kokią moterų grupę savo gyvenime ir kūryboje palaikė Žemaitė? 1. Moteris valstietės [Correct] 2. Moteris – fabriky darbuotojas 3. Vienišas, senyvas moteris
3.	A. Vienuolio g. 12	Pasiklausykite Grincevičiūtės atliekamos dainos. Kas dainoje gydė sergantį uodą? Nuoroda: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ko13T98-6iM 1. Varlės 2. Vaikai 3. Musės [Correct]
4.	Gedimino pr. 13	Felicija taip ir netapo prezidente. Tačiau 2009 m. lietuviai išrinko pirmąją istorijoje moterį prezidentę. Koks jos vardas? 1. Vilija Blinkevičiūtė 2. Kazimiera Prunskienė 3. Dalia Grybauskaitė [Correct]

5.	Kudirkos aikštė	<p>Kada Eliza Orzeszkowa pirmą kartą buvo nominuota Nobelio literatūros premijai?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1905 [Correct] 1900 1911
6.	Gedimino pr. 12	<p>Kiek metų buvo Aleksandrai, kai ji 1917 m. šioje studijoje fotografavo Lietuvos Tarybą? Ji gimė 1895 m.</p> <p>Pasirenkamo atsakymo variantas:</p> <p>22 [Correct]</p>

3.8. Lecco, Italy

In English

City, Country: Lecco, Italy		
Start point: Monte Marengo		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	COMUNE DI MONTE MARENZO; Piazza Municipale, 5, 23804 Monte Marengo LC	<p>Where did Paola Colombo spend her time studying abroad?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> In Australia In London In Spain In the U.S. [Correct]
2	ISTITUTO D'ISTRUZIONE SUPERIORE LORENZO ROTA; Via Lavello, 17, 23801 Calolziocorte LC	<p>What did the young men and women of the Rota Institute do within HerStory?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> They shared reflections, ideas, knowledge, desires, aspirations with respect to the theme of gender [Correct] Nothing They got to know their European partners They wrote lyrics

3	L'ISOLA DELLA STUPIDERA: Via Ca' Romano, 23854 Olginate LC	<p>What does Alessandra Maggi think is useful to be more in schools?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More hours dedicated to art 2. More hours dedicated to English 3. A greater presence of male figures [Correct] 4. A greater presence of young people
4	COMUNE DI OLGINATE; Piazza Volontari del Sangue, 1, 23854 Olginate LC	<p>What does Marina suggest to young women?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To play sports 2. To get involved in politics 3. To be reliable and tenacious [Correct] 4. Not to listen to others
5	LIONS LECCO: Via Maggiore, 19, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>What does Marina suggest to young women?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To take your time 2. Not to live subject to the judgment of others [Correct] 3. To go on trips 4. To write and document
6	SEDE SOCIALE "HOTEL NH PONTEVECCHIO" di Lecco. Via Azzone Visconti, 84, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>What is Fulvia's job?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. She is a primary school teacher 2. She's a doula 3. She is an entrepreneur [Correct] 4. She's an actress
7	QUESTURA DI LECCO. Corso Promessi Sposi, 40, 23900 Lecco LC.	<p>What does Luisa do?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Psychotherapy 2. Primary prevention of child abuse and maltreatment 3. Hearing of minors for the Judicial Police 4. All of the above [Correct]
8	Via Cadorna, Lecco, LC, 23900	<p>What region is Lea from?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lombardy 2. Campania 3. Calabria [Correct] 4. Veneto

9	TEATRO SOCIALE DI LECCO. Piazza Giuseppe Garibaldi, 10, 23900 Lecco LC	Aurora is: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Actress 2. Writer 3. Woman of the present from Lecco 4. All of the above [Correct]
10	via del Roccolo, Lecco, LC, 23900	Why did the municipal administration award Francesca the gold medal? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. For Medical Research 2. For the Resistance [Correct] 3. For social research 4. For his artistic contributions
11	CENTRO CIVICO SANDRO PERTINI; 23900 Lecco LC	Which place was named after Maria Calvetti? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hospital of Lecco 2. Sandro Pertini Civic Centre in Lecco [Correct] 3. Teatro della Società di Lecco 4. A square in Lecco
12	AMBITO DISTRETTUALE DI LECCO. Via Graziano Tubi, 43, 23900 Lecco LC	In which area is Romina a reference today? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local associations 2. Administration of the Municipality in which you reside 3. Provincial maternal and child care [Correct] 4. School environment
13	SALA CIVICA A SAN GIOVANNI; Via Don Luigi Orione, 8, 23900 Lecco LC	Where did Carla study art? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Academy of Fine Arts of Florence 2. Brera Academy of Fine Arts [Correct] 3. Academy of Fine Arts of Venice 4. Academy of Fine Arts of Naples
14	SALA CIVICA DI CASTELLO; Via Seminario, 39, 23900 Lecco LC	What was Gabriella's job? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Teaching 2. Cure Palliative [Correct] 3. Architecture 4. Entrepreneurship
15	via Bersaglio, Lecco, LC, 23900	Which of these positions has Nilde Iotti held?

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. President of the Chamber of Deputies 2. Chairmanship of the Parliamentary Committee 3. Vice-President of the Council of Europe 4. All of the above [Correct]
--	--	---

In Italian

City, Country: Lecco, Italy		
Start point: Monte Marengo		
Number	Treasure hunting spot	Quiz
1	COMUNE DI MONTE MARENZO; Piazza Municipale, 5, 23804 Monte Marengo LC	<p>Dove ha vissuto il suo periodo di studi all'estero Paola Colombo?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In Australia 2. A Londra 3. In Spagna 4. Negli Stati Uniti [Correct]
2	ISTITUTO D'ISTRUZIONE SUPERIORE LORENZO ROTA; Via Lavello, 17, 23801 Calolziocorte LC	<p>Cosa hanno fatto i giovani e le giovani dell'Istituto Rota all'interno di HerStory?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hanno condiviso riflessioni, idee, conoscenze, desideri, aspirazioni rispetto al tema del genere [Correct] 2. Nulla 3. Hanno conosciuto i partner europei 4. Hanno scritto testi
3	L'ISOLA DELLA STUPIDERA; Via Ca' Romano, 23854 Olginate LC	<p>Cosa ritiene utile che ci sia maggiormente nelle scuole Alessandra Maggi?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Più ore dedicate all'arte 2. Più ore dedicate all'inglese 3. Una maggiore presenza di figure maschili [Correct] 4. Una maggiore presenza di figure giovani
4	COMUNE DI OLGINATE; Piazza Volontari del Sangue, 1, 23854 Olginate LC	<p>Cosa suggerisce Marina alle giovani donne?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Di fare sport 2. Di occuparsi di politica 3. Di essere affidabili e tenaci [Correct]

		4. Di non dare ascolto agli altri
5	LIONS LECCO: Via Maggiore, 19, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>Cosa suggerisce Marina alle giovani donne?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Di prendersi il proprio tempo 2. Di non vivere assoggettate al giudizio altrui [Correct] 3. Di fare viaggi 4. Di scrivere e documentarsi
6	SEDE SOCIALE "HOTEL NH PONTEVECCHIO" di Lecco. Via Azzone Visconti, 84, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>Di cosa si occupa Fulvia?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. E' una docente di scuola primaria 2. È una doula 3. È un'imprenditrice [Correct] 4. È un'attrice
7	QUESTURA DI LECCO. Corso Promessi Sposi, 40, 23900 Lecco LC.	<p>Di che cosa si occupa Luisa?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Psicoterapia 2. Prevenzione primaria ad abuso e maltrattamento infantile 3. Audizione di minorenni per la Polizia giudiziaria 4. Tutte le precedenti [Correct]
8	Via Cadorna, Lecco, LC, 23900	<p>Di quale regione è originaria Lea?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lombardia 2. Campania 3. Calabria [Correct] 4. Veneto
9	TEATRO SOCIALE DI LECCO. Piazza Giuseppe Garibaldi, 10, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>Aurora è:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Attrice 2. Scrittrice 3. Donna del presente di Lecco 4. Tutte le precedenti [Correct]
10	via del Roccolo, Lecco, LC, 23900	<p>Per quale motivo l'amministrazione comunale ha conferito a Francesca la medaglia d'oro?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Per la ricerca medica 2. Per la Resistenza [Correct] 3. Per la ricerca sociale

		4. Per i suoi contributi artistici
11	CENTRO CIVICO SANDRO PERTINI; 23900 Lecco LC	<p>Quale luogo è stato intitolato a Maria?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ospedale di Lecco 2. Centro Civico Sandro Pertini di Lecco [Correct] 3. Teatro della Società di Lecco 4. Una piazza di Lecco
12	AMBITO DISTRETTUALE DI LECCO. Via Graziano Tubi, 43, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>In quale ambito Romina è oggi un riferimento?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Associazionismo locale 2. Amministrazione del Comune in cui risiede 3. Ambito materno-infantile provinciale [Correct] 4. Ambito scolastico
13	SALA CIVICA A SAN GIOVANNI; Via Don Luigi Orione, 8, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>Dove ha seguito gli studi artistici Carla?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accademia delle Belle Arti di Firenze 2. Accademia delle Belle Arti di Brera [Correct] 3. Accademia delle Belle Arti di Venezia 4. Accademia delle Belle Arti di Napoli
14	SALA CIVICA DI CASTELLO; Via Seminario, 39, 23900 Lecco LC	<p>Di cosa si occupava Gabriella?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Insegnamento 2. Cure Palliative [Correct] 3. Architettura 4. Imprenditoria
15	via Bersaglio, Lecco, LC, 23900	<p>Quali tra queste cariche ha ricoperto Nilde?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Presidente della Camera dei Deputati 2. Presidenza della Commissione Parlamentare 3. Vicepresidente del Consiglio d'Europa 4. Tutte le precedenti [Correct]